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CULTURAL SCIENCE

Полвон Качал - ўзбек анъанавий кўғирчоқ театрининг қаҳрамони

Полвон Качал – герой традиционного узбекского театра кукол.

Polvon Kachal is the hero of the traditional Uzbek puppet theater.

Қодирова Сарвиноз Мухсиновна,
санъатшунослик фанлари доктори,
профессор

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада ўзбек анъанавий кўғирчоқ театрининг қаҳрамони Полвон Качал ҳақида сўз боради.

Калит сўзлар. Театр, кўғирчоқ, кўғирчоқбоз, чодир, кўлқопли кўғирчоқ, марионетка, рассом, кўғирчоқ ўйнатиш.

Аннотация. В данной статье речь идет о герое традиционного узбекского театра кукол - Палван Качале.

Ключевые слова. Театр, кукла, кукловод, ширма, перчаточная кукла, марионетка, художник, кукловождение.

Annotation. This article is about the hero of the traditional Uzbek puppet theater Polvon Kachal.

Keywords. Theater, doll, puppeteer, screen, glove puppet, puppet, artist, puppeteering.

Ҳозирда ўзбек кўғирчоқ театри ҳақида гап борганда, авваламбор оғзаки драматургияга асосланган профессионал анъанавий кўғирчоқ театри ҳамда унинг асосий қаҳрамони - Полвон Качал кўғирчоғи кўз олдимизга келади. Ўзбек анъанавий кўғирчоқ театри икки асосий турдан иборат бўлган. “Чодир жамол” кўлга кийиб ўйнатиладиган кўғирчоқ тури ҳамда иплар воситасида ижро этиладиган “Чодир хаёл” театр тури. Бундан ташқари, XV асрларда яхши танилган, афсуски бизгача етиб келмаган яна бир тури бўлган. Бу “фонус хаёл” бўлиб, фонус ёруғида чарм ёки ёғочдан ишланган кўғирчоқларнинг сояси туширилган театрdir. Бу тур халқ орасида кенг оммалашмаган, сабаби томоша кўпроқ саройларда, аслзодалар учун кўрсатилган.

“Чодир жамол” театри одатда болани бешикка солиш, қорин сочини олиш, уйлантириш муносабати билан ўтказиладиган тўй маросимларида, халқ сайилларида кўрсатилган. “Чодир хаёл” театри томошаси асосан халқ байрамларида намоиш қилинган. Бошқарилишига қараб аталганида “Чодир жамол” “кўл кўғирчоқ” ёки “кичик кўғирчоқ”, “Чодир хаёл” эса “ип кўғирчоқ” ёхуд “катта кўғирчоқ” деб ном олган бўларди. Лекин уларнинг биронтасини ҳам атама деб бўлмайди.

“Чодир жамол” - бу кишиларнинг кундалик ҳаётидан олинган воқеаларни кўлга кийиб ўйнатиладиган кўғирчоқлар ёрдамида кундузи акс эттирувчи ўзига хос театрdir. “Чодир жамол” томошасида бир кўғирчоқ муҳим аҳамиятга эга бўлган, у ҳам бўлса - Полвон Качал. Шу сабабли уни ясашга алоҳида эътибор берилган. Унинг қиёфаси кўпинча бошқа кўғирчоқлардан ажралиб турган, қимматбаҳо ва рангли матолардан либослар тикилган, кўзлари ялтираб турган қоп-қора мунчоқлардан ясалган. Хуллас, Полвон Качал қандай ҳаётий вазиятлар бўлмасин ҳаминша хушчақчақ, шўх, меҳнаткаш халқ вакили, қаҳрамони. У бой ва судхўрларни масхара ва фош этиш орқали эзилганлар манфаатини ҳимоя қилган. Ҳақсизлик ва зулмдан ғзаби келган чоғларда уни на шайтон, на ялмоғиз кампир, на аждар кўрқита олган. Шайтонни минган, аждарнинг оғзидан кириб кетидан чиққан, ялмоғизни сочидан бураб туриб савалаган.

“Чодир жамол” театрида хушчақчақлик ва донолик, жасурлик ва шижоат каби ўзининг бир қанча фазилатлари билан халқ оммасининг меҳр-муҳаббатини қозонган Полвон Качалнинг бошидан кечирганларини шўх, жозибали ва самимий ҳикоя қилувчи, замон зўравонларини масхара ва фош этувчи ажойиб комедия намоиш қилинган. “Полвон Качал саргузаштлари” деб аталган бу комедия ва унинг вариантлари авлоддан авлодга ўтиб, ўзгаришларга учраб келган бўлса-да, ўз мавзулари, образлари, ғоявий мазмуни ва бадиийёти билан демократик ва халқчил бўлиб қолаверди.

Сир эмаски, умуман халқ кўғирчоқ театри илмий драмадан фойдаланмаган, фақат импровизация - оғзаки бадий тўқима асосида ишлаган. Аммо комедиянинг сюжет қурилишида, фабуласида маълум турғунлик мавжуд бўлган, барқарорлик сюжетдагина эмас, диалогда ҳам кўп учраган.

Иккала турда ҳам томошалар асосан икки киши - кўғирчоқбоз билан корфармон томонидан уюштирилган ва бошқарилган. Албатта томоша давомида кўғирчоқбозга шогирдлари чодир қўйишга, кўғирчоқларни олиб бериб туришда кўмак берган. Корфармон кўғирчоқларни гапга солган, томошани бошлаган, яқунлаган, шунингдек, созандалик вазифасини бажарган. Кўғирчоқбоз чодир ичида ёки парда орқасида сафил ёрдамида кўғирчоқлар тилидан гапирган, уларни ҳаракатга келтирган, томошабинга кўринмаган. Оддий томошабин кўз ўнгида кўғирчоқбозлар кўғирчоқлар воситасида ёмонларни жазолаган ва яхшиларни қўллаб - қувватлаган. Қадимда мазкур театр турида авваламбор, устоз-шогирд анъаналари бардавом бўлган, ўз миллий кўғирчоқ қаҳрамони мавжуд бўлган, ижрочиларнинг кўғирчоқ ўйнатишдаги маҳоратлари, бирламчи матнга бўлган ҳурмат ҳозирги кун кўғирчоқ театри ижод аҳлига ибрат бўлиши лозим.

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ECONOMICAL SCIENCE

Корхоналарнинг ишлаб чиқариш фаолиятини баҳолаш услублари

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Abstract. This article analyzes the methods of evaluation based on the network characteristics of business entities.

Keywords. Industrial network, industrial enterprises, internal environment, external environment, internal competitive environment, competitiveness, economic entities, rating evaluation methodology.

Ҳозирги вақтда бозорда рақобатбардош бўлиш учун бозорга фақат юқори сифатли товарларни етказиб бериш етарли бўлмайди. Истеъмолчилар учун юқори сифат билан бир қаторда, маҳсулотнинг умуман рақобатбардошлиги, ишлаб чиқариш ва бошқарувнинг юқори техник даражаси, корхона имиджи, корхонанинг товар сотиш имкониятлари каби омиллар ва бошқалар муҳим роль ўйнайди.

Умуман олганда, ҳар қандай баҳолаш, шу жумладан саноат, хусусан металлургия корхонасининг рақобатбардошлигини баҳолаш ҳам баҳолаш моделининг бир-бири билан боғлиқ бўлган бир нечта таркибий қисмларини ўз ичига оладик, ушбу моделга кўриб чиқиладиган вазифани ҳал қилиш билан боғлиқ равишда қуйидагилар киради:

- баҳолашнинг мақсади;
- баҳолаш объекти (маълум бир бозорда саноат корхонасининг рақобатбардошлиги – параметр ва кўрсаткичлар);
- баҳолаш субъекти (баҳолашни амалга оширувчи шахс);
- баҳолаш базаси (баҳолаш мақсадлари, тамойиллари ва усуллари, бозорда рақобатчиларнинг параметрлари ва кўрсаткичлари);
- баҳолаш натижаси.

Маълумки, рейтинг – бу таҳлил қилинадиган объектнинг кўрсаткичлар шкаласи бўйича баҳоси, шунингдек, конъюнктура ҳолатини тўғри акс

этирувчи ва унинг ўзгаришини аниқ прогноз қилишга имкон берувчи ишбилармонлик фаоллигининг кўрсаткичи ҳисобланади.

Корхоналарни рейтингли баҳолаш услуби тизимли-комплекс тусга эга бўлиб, уларни саралаш бўйича турли таҳлилий ёндашувларга асосланган. У универсал хусусиятга эга, лекин шу билан бирга ўрганилаётган корхоналарнинг тармоқ хусусиятларини ҳисобга олиши мумкин. Ушбу услубдан кўрсатилган усулларнинг ҳар бири учун алоҳида тарзда, шунингдек барча усулларни бир вақтда қўллаган ҳолда фойдаланиш мумкин.

Бир қатор кўрсаткичлар ёрдамида рейтинг тузиш усули нисбатан содда бўлиб, таҳлил қилиш учун танланган асосий кўрсаткичлар қийматига мувофиқ корхоналарни таснифлашга асосланган. Бу усул тўрт кўрсаткич - даромад, соф фойда, капиталлашув, инвесторнинг умумий даромади асосида қўлланилиши мумкин. Бироқ, шунини таъкидлаш керакки, танланган кўрсаткичлар корxonанинг молиявий ҳолатини тўлиқ тавсифламайди, капиталлашув ва инвесторнинг умумий даромади каби кўрсаткичлар эса кўпроқ, қимматли қоғозларни фонд индекслари асосида рейтингли баҳолаш кўрсаткичлари ҳисобланади. Молиявий ҳолатни баҳолашга тизимли комплекс ёндашув янада асосланган бўлиб, корхона фаолиятини ҳар томонлама баҳолашга имкон беради. Шу сабабли маълум бўлган усулларнинг умумий тавсифини беришга ҳаракат қиламиз.

1. Матрицали таҳлил услуби.

Матрицали таҳлил усули корхона фаолияти самарадорлигини умумий баҳолаш учун ишлатилади. Матрица усули ишлаб чиқариш жараёнини матрицали модел кўринишидаги кириш-чиқиш сифатида ифодалаш концепциясига асосланган. Киришда ресурслар истеъмол қилинади ва харажатлар шаклланади, чиқишда эса тайёр маҳсулот келиб тушади ва сотилади ҳамда қийматда ифодаланган фаолият натижалари аниқланади.

Келтирилган хўжалик фаолиятининг самарадорлик кўрсаткичлари матрицаси жуфтлашган маҳаллий самарадорлик кўрсаткичларидан ташкил топади. Ҳар

бир жуфтликда (масалан, харажатларнинг рентабеллиги ва фойданинг харажат сиғими) самарадорлик ошганда бир кўрсаткич (самарадорликнинг тўғридан-тўғри кўрсаткичи) ўсиши, бошқа кўрсаткич эса (тескари кўрсаткич) – пасайиши лозим. Самарадорлик кўрсаткичлари матричасини ишлаб чиқариш функциясининг воситалари билан таққослаш мумкин бўлиб, бу ишлаб чиқаришнинг иқтисодий ва техник жиҳатларини харажатлар, ресурслар ва натижаларнинг ўзаро боғлиқлиги асосида ўрганишга имкон беради.

2. Балли баҳолаш усули.

Бу усул нисбатан содда бўлиб, етакчи мутахассислар – экспертларнинг фикрига асосланган. Рейтинг кўрсаткичлар тизимига мувофиқ баллар йиғиндиси сифатида белгиланади. Барча кўрсаткичлар синфларга бўлинади:

- 1-синф – кўрсаткичларнинг қиймати белгиланган ёки назарий асосланган меъёрлардан ошади;
- 2-синф – кўрсаткичларнинг қийматлари меъёр даражасида;
- 3-синф – кўрсаткичларнинг қийматлари меъёр даражасидан паст.

Кўрсаткичлар тизими ликвидлик, молиявий барқарорлик, ишбилармонлик фаоллиги ва рентабеллик коэффициентларидан иборат.

Рейтингни ҳисоблашда кўрсаткичларни у ёки бу синфга киритишнинг турли вариантлари мавжуд бўлиши мумкин. Биринчи синфдаги кўрсаткич 3 балл, иккинчиси - 2 балл, учинчиси - 1 балл билан баҳоланади.

3. Қиёсий рейтингли баҳолаш услуби.

Корхонанинг молиявий ҳолатини қиёсий рейтингли баҳолаш услуби бозор муносабатлари шароитида молиявий таҳлил назарияси ва амалиётига асосланган. Ушбу услубни амалга ошириш тартибида қуйидаги босқичлар ажратилади: баҳоланаётган вақт муддати учун дастлабки маълумотларни йиғиш ва таҳлилий баҳолаш; молиявий ҳолатни рейтингли баҳолаш учун ишлатиладиган кўрсаткичлар тизимини асослаш ва уларнинг таснифи;

рейтинг баҳосининг якуний кўрсаткичларини ҳисоблаш; корхоналарни рейтинг бўйича таснифлаш.

Қиёсий баҳо қиймати энг паст бўлган компанияга энг юқори рейтинг берилади. Дастлабки маълумотлар таркибига бир вақтнинг ўзида ҳам лаҳзали, ҳам суръатли кўрсаткичларни киритиш мумкин бўлиб, бу корхона молиявий-хўжалик фаолиятининг ҳолати ва динамикасини тавсифловчи умумлаштирилган рейтинг баҳосини олишга имкон беради.

Бизнингча, кўрсаткичлар тизимининг ўзига хос хусусияти – бу деярли барча кўрсаткичларнинг бир хил йўналишга эгалигидир. Бу кўрсаткичнинг даражаси қанча юқори бўлса ёки унинг ўсиш суръати қанча юқори бўлса, баҳоланаётган корхонанинг молиявий ҳолати шунча яхши эканлигини англатади. Шу сабабли назарда тутилаётган тизимни унга янги кўрсаткичларни киритиш ҳисобига ҳал қилишда ушбу талаб бажарилаётганлигига ишонч ҳосил қилиш зарур.

4. Рейтингли молиявий таҳлил усули.

Корхонанинг молиявий ҳолати унинг фаолиятининг энг муҳим тавсифномасидир. У маблағларни ва уларни шакллантириш манбаларини жойлаштириш ва улардан фойдаланиш билан белгиланади. Молиявий кўрсаткичлар баҳолаш мезонлари сифатида хизмат қилади. Бу коэффициентлар ликвидликни баҳолаш; молиявий барқарорлик; ишбилармонлик фаоллиги; рентабеллик каби асосий йўналишлар бўйича гуруҳланади.

Шундай қилиб, интеграл кўрсаткични ҳисоблаш услубиёти асосини ташкил қилувчи мезонлар тизими рақобат муҳити шароитида саноат корхонасини позициялаштириш сифатига берилган баҳони энг тўғри акс эттиради ва юқори динамик ишбилармонлик муҳити шароитида корхонанинг рақобат устунлигига эришиш ва уни сақлаш вазифаларини самарали ҳал қилиш имконини беради.

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Туризм хизматлар бозори самарадорлигини оширишнинг йўллари

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Аннотация: ушбу мақолада туризм соҳасида давлат сиёсати истиқболда ҳудудлар ва уларнинг инфратузилмасини комплекс жадал ривожлантиришдаги долзарб ижтимоий-иқтисодий вазифаларнинг ечилиши, янги иш ўринларини кўпайтириш масалаларига алоҳида эътибор қаратилган.

Калит сўзлар: туризм бозори, давлат сиёсати, ҳудуд, туризм, саёҳат, дам олиш, хизматлар сифати.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена вопросам решения актуальных социально-экономических задач в комплексном динамичном развитии территорий и их инфраструктуры в сфере туризма в ракурсе государственной политики, увеличения новых рабочих мест.

Ключевые слова: туристический рынок, Государственная политика, Территория, Туризм, Путешествия, Досуг, качество услуг.

Abstract: This article is devoted to the issues of solving urgent socio-economic problems in the complex dynamic development of territories and their infrastructure in the field of tourism from the perspective of state policy, increasing new jobs.

Keywords: tourist market, State policy, Territory, Tourism, Travel, Leisure, quality of services.

Мамлакатимизда туризм бозорининг турли сегментларига йўналтирилган туризм маҳсулоти ва хизматларини диверсификация қилиш, уларнинг рақобатбардошлигини янада ошириш, мақбул ва қулай ички ва ҳудудий туризм муҳитини яратиш, транспорт йўналишларини кенгайтириш, транспорт хизматлари сифатини ошириш, туризм маҳсулотларини кенг тарғиб қилиш, шунингдек, мамлакатимизнинг саёҳат ва дам олиш учун хавфсиз манзил сифатидаги имижини мустақамлаш бугунги кунинг долзарб ва ечимини кутиб турган вазифаларидан биридир.

Ўзбекистон жуда катта туризм ва рекреация салоҳиятига эга, унда жами 7,4 минг маданий мерос объектлари мавжуд, улардан 209 таси тўртта музей шаҳарлар – “Хива шаҳридаги Ичан-қалъа”, “Бухоро шаҳрининг тарихий маркази”, “Шаҳрисабз шаҳрининг тарихий маркази”, “Самарқанд шаҳри” худудида жойлашган бўлиб, ЮНЕСКО бутунжаҳон мероси рўйхатиغا киритилган.

2010-2017 йиллар давомида туризм хизматлари экспорти ҳажми икки баравар ошди ва 2017 йилда 546,9 миллион АҚШ доллари, 2018 йилда эса - 1 041 миллион АҚШ долларини ташкил этди¹.

2016 йилгача хорижий ташриф буюрувчилар сонининг ўсиш суръати ўртача йиллик 8 фоизни, 2017 йилда - 7 фоизни ташкил қилиб, 2,69 миллион нафардан ошди. 2018 йил якунлари бўйича республикамизга 5,3 миллион хорижий туристлар ташриф буюрди. Хусусий секторни қўллаб-қувватлаш ва муҳофаза қилишга қаратилган чоралар қўрилгани натижасида, 2015 йилда 398 тани ташкил қилган туризм ташкилотлари сони 2018 йил якуни бўйича 950 тага, меҳмонхона хўжаликлари сони - 661 тадан 900 тага етди².

Сўнгги йилларда туризм инфратузилмасини ривожлантириш бўйича йирик инвестиция лойиҳалари амалга оширилди, шу жумладан Тошкент шаҳрида “Hyatt Regency Tashkent” ва “Lotte City Hotel Tashkent Palace” брендли меҳмонхоналар очилиши, Андижон, Урганч ва Тошкент шаҳрида маданий-қўнгилочар боғларнинг ташкил этилиши, “Ангрен-Поп” темир йўли очилиши, Бухоро, Қарши, Шаҳрисабз ва Хива шаҳарларига тезюар поездлар учун электрлаштирилган темир йўллари очилишини айтиб ўтиш жоиз.

Туризм соҳасида давлат сиёсати истиқболда ҳудудлар ва уларнинг инфратузилмасини комплекс жадал ривожлантиришда туризм соҳаси етакчилик қилиши, долзарб ижтимоий-иқтисодий вазифаларни ечиш, иш ўринларини кўпайтириш, ҳудудлар диверсификацияси ва ривожланишини

¹ stat.uz

²[https://nrm.uz/contentf?doc=574188_2019-2025_yillarda_o'zbekiston_respublikasida_turizm_sohasini_rivojlantirish_konceptiyasi_\(o'zr_prezidentining_05_01_2019_y_pf-5611-son_farmoniga_1-ilova\)](https://nrm.uz/contentf?doc=574188_2019-2025_yillarda_o'zbekiston_respublikasida_turizm_sohasini_rivojlantirish_konceptiyasi_(o'zr_prezidentining_05_01_2019_y_pf-5611-son_farmoniga_1-ilova))

таъминлаш, аҳолининг даромадлари, яшаш даражаси ва сифатини ошириш ҳамда мамлакатнинг инвестициявий жозибадорлиги ва имиджини яхшилашга қаратилган.

Шу жиҳатдан олиб қаралганда биринчи навбатда туристлар учун яшаш шароитларини яхшилаш, меҳмон уйларининг улушини кўпайтириш билан бирга жаҳон андозаларига мослаштириш муҳим вазифалардан биридир.

Ҳудудий туризм хизматлари бозорида меҳмон уйларининг ўрни ва улуши жуда катта аҳамиятга эга эканлиги бугунги кунда ҳеч биримиз учун сир эмас. Меҳмон уйлари бирор-бир экологик ёки ижтимоий муаммоларсиз катта иқтисодий фойда олишга имкон беради. Бунда комплекс ёндашувга алоҳида эътибор қаратиш зарур.

Ўзбекистоннинг халқаро туризм бозоридан мустаҳкам ўрин олиши учун туристлар учун юқори даражадаги қулайлик яратилиши, уларга хизмат кўрсатишнинг барча турлари бўйича стандартлар тизими, хавфсизлигини таъминлаш кафолатлари юзага келтирилиши шарт. Туризмни барқарор ривожлантириш мамлакат иқтисодиётини мустаҳкамлашга, бақувват туристик тармоқ яратишга, туризм инфраструктурасига давлат таъсирининг бошқарувини кучайтиришга, аҳолининг турмуш даражасини оширишга, экологик хавфсизликни таъминлашга, тарих ва маданият ёдгорликларини сақлаб қолишга, табиатни муҳофаза қилиш фаолиятининг даражасини оширишга, жамиятнинг маънавий салоҳиятини оширишга хизмат қилади.

Юқоридаги хусусиятидан келиб чиққан ҳолда меҳмон уйлари салмоғининг оширилиши, фақат технологияларни такомиллаштириш ва меҳнатни ташкил қилишни яхшилашгагина эмас, балки хўжалик юритишнинг энг самарали шакллари жорий қилишга, янги иш жойларини яратишга ҳам кўмаклашади.

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Economic thoughts of great people

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Annotation. Yusuf Has Hogiba's economic views to "Kutadgu Bilig" (Knowledge, granting happiness). He aspired to create the model of ideal Man and ideal society. In spite of such historical scantiness, the scientific work takes definite place in the history of economic thought in the early Middle Ages.

Key words: economic views, labor, development, knowledge, social ideal, reason
Economic thought has long existed not as a special, clearly limited field of science, but in inextricable connection with people's religious views, their legal concepts. Therefore, the economic thought of the early Middle Ages has to be studied according to the works of scientists, literary monuments, representing a chain of moralistic instructions and covering a wide range of philosophical, social, ethical, social, economic problems.

One of the outstanding sources of social thought of the peoples of Central Asia of the XI century is "Kutadgu bilig" (Knowledge that gives happiness).

Yusuf Khos Hadjib - who lived during the heyday of science and culture in Central Asia. He is one of the founders of written Turkish-language literature.

Being by its nature a philosophical and didactic work, "Kutadgu bilig" has absorbed essentially the foundations of the thinker's scientific worldview and represents both a political treatise and a code of public administration laws, principles of economic policy and a kind of encyclopedia of science.

The author, revealing the reasons for writing his book, vividly drew the socio-economic conditions for the creation of his work. He laments that virtue has died in his age and vice has triumphed, there is a constant struggle for the seizure of foreign lands by the riches of the world. The world began to be ruled by those who have money in their pocket. Money began to control people's relations to each other, people became slaves of money. Trade has become a source of gathering and accumulating wealth. Justice has been forgotten, the poor and orphans, the elderly

and widows have been forgotten. The earth was flooded with the blood of Muslims.

Under these conditions, in an edifying form, Yusuf Has Hadjib created his own science, aimed, in his opinion, at the triumph of justice and reason, and called it the science of being happy. His social ideal is the harmony of the interests of the classes of feudal society. He called on the common people to obey their masters, and advised the masters not to show extreme cruelty towards their slaves, excessive exploitation of them.

Yusuf Has Hadjib proposes the following principles of economic policy:

1. The state is strong with a strong army;
2. To do this, you need to collect a huge wealth;
3. In order to collect wealth, you need a rich people;
4. In order for the people to become rich, it is necessary to pursue a correct, fair policy. The absence of one of them excludes all four conditions. Without this, the kingdom will collapse. The people are a "great force", managing them is a difficult task. The Bek must protect his people from violence and robbery of their property, with a fair policy and compliance with the laws.

A rich treasury can be preserved with the establishment of correct accounting, keeping a book of receipts and expenditures, and control. The lack of control over income and expenditure weakens the state. The treasurer must be firm, economical, know the quality of goods, understand prices. He should be able to trade profitably. The treasurer must pay for the work of employees on time and in full. The payment must correspond to the position held. It should cover the needs for food and clothing. They should be rewarded for good service, because interest promotes servile service to their master. All living things are in motion for the sake of satisfying their interests. If there is no interest, even the hunter does not leave his house. A person living only by his own interest cannot be considered a person, he can be considered a person if he thinks about the interests of the people.

A commoner, the rabble thinks only about satisfying their need for food. They have no other worries than getting food. Therefore, the thinker asks the question whether he can be a beek if he cannot save his subjects from poverty. The bek should be generous, benevolent, fair, protecting the interests of his subjects.

Speaking about farmers - peasants, he glorifies them and says that the land is the breadwinner of society, society exists thanks to their work.

Yusuf Has Hadjib was a proponent of trade development. They go from one end to the other for the sake of profit, they contribute to improving relations between countries. Be always polite to them and keep the gates open, and "if there were no merchants, our life would be worse."

Yusuf Khas Hadjib calls for great respect for livestock breeders. From them comes milk, suzma, kimiz, butter, wool, felt. They are useful people for society. They deserve respect, it is necessary to always meet them halfway and establish good relations.

Another creator of wealth is artisans. He calls on the sovereigns to glorify artisan labor, to give more benefits to artisan people. Yusuf Has Hadjib writes:

Yusuf Khas Hadjib`s views are dominated by an approach based on the theory of labor value. He wrote that if the result is good, then the root is labor. We observe in his views an understanding of the measure of value. Which subject has spent more work, that subject becomes the favorite and most revered.

It should be emphasized that Yusuf Has Hadjib sought to create an image of an ideal person and an ideal society. But he did not understand the impracticability of his dream, especially in his ideal society, a lamb and a wolf were sewn to drink on the same path.

Despite such historical limitations, the scientist`s work occupies a significant place in the history of economic thought of the early Middle Ages.

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Перспективы совершенствования расчетов основных макроэкономических показателей

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Annotation. The purpose of this study is to identify ways to improve GDP by income and expenditure methods, and to understand the mechanisms that motivate the widespread use of GDP as a measure of development progress. The result of the study shows that GDP is used as an operationalization of a welfare indicator. It is also found that the prevalent use of GDP and the stability of this practice comes from the reconciliation of several factors and elements that create a configuration that supports and reproduces this practice.

Keywords: GDP, economic growth, GDP by income and expenditure methods, sustainable development, national development plan

Мировое статистическое сообщество совместно с научными деятелями на сегодняшний день проводят множество исследований по внедрению в статистическую практику расчетов современных видов деятельности во всех отраслевых статистических методологиях, включая интегрированное ведение счетов по внешнеэкономической статистике, статистике государственных финансов и финансовой статистики. Кроме того, предпринимаются усилия по учету воздействия экономики на экологическое состояние стран мира, как фактора снижающего благополучие населения и разного рода индексов, характеризующих уровень здоровья людей, их счастья и удовлетворенности жизнью в конкретных странах мира [3].

Как и другие сферы жизнедеятельности людей активно развиваются и приобретают новые формы и методы, так и статистика национальных счетов не стоит на месте. По состоянию на начало 2023 года работа по обновлению Системы национальных счетов издания 2008 года (СНС 2008) идет полным ходом, и СНС 2025 (название, под которым будет выпущена обновленная версия СНС 2008) начинает обретать форму. В процесс подготовки

обновленной версии вовлечено огромное число людей из большинства национальных статистических управлений, национальных центральных банков и многих международных организаций, а также другие эксперты.

Основываясь на сводном перечне областей исследования, выбранных для обновления СНС 2008, несколько целевых групп разработали множество руководящих записок, охватывающих каждый из вопросов. Целевые группы состояли из профильных экспертов, представляющих международные организации и национальные статистические управления. Было создано семь целевых групп по национальным счетам со следующими областями компетенции [2]:

1. благополучие и устойчивость,
2. глобализация,
3. цифровизация,
4. финансовые и платежные системы, коммуникации,
5. неформальный сектор экономики,
6. исламское финансирование.

Всего для обновления СНС готовится 65 руководящих записок. Когда подготовка всех руководящих записок будет завершена, будет составлен сводный перечень руководящих записок. Этот сводный перечень станет объектом глобальных консультаций в середине 2023 года, и страны получат возможность представить свои комментарии касательно согласованности и понятности рекомендаций. В начале 2024 года сводный перечень рекомендаций будет представлен для одобрения Статистической комиссии Организации Объединенных Наций.

Отличительной чертой СНС 2025 стало расширение рамочной основы национальных счетов, с тем чтобы лучше отразить элементы, влияющие на благополучие и устойчивость. Задача заключается в создании информационной основы для различных целей политики, в том числе для Повестки дня в области устойчивого развития на период до 2030 года, и

удовлетворении озвученной потребности улучшить учет уровня благополучия людей, сегодня и в будущем, в дополнение к оценке экономических показателей (концепция под названием «выход за рамки ВВП»).

Для выполнения этой задачи в новой главе (Национальные счета и оценка благополучия и устойчивости) будет представлено описание того, как национальные счета могут быть использованы для понимания уровня благополучия и устойчивости, в том числе будут указаны возможные направления расширения рамочной основы и области, требующие новой, зачастую дополняющей статистики, например из Системы эколого-экономического учета (СЭЭУ), чтобы обеспечить более комплексное понимание этих вопросов. Эта вводная глава будет сопровождаться двумя дополнительными главами, в которых вопросы благополучия и устойчивости будут рассматриваться более углубленно.

Также планируется включить новые главы, посвященные основным аспектам программы исследований СНС, лежащей в основе обновления СНС, а именно касающиеся цифровизации, глобализации и исламского финансирования [1].

Важной отличительной чертой СНС 2025 является то, что она будет доступна не только в традиционной печатной (бумажной) версии, но и в цифровом формате.

Для успешного применения СНС 2025 после ее согласования Статистической комиссией страны планирует более оперативно внедрить ее. При этом следует признать, что в нашей стране внедрение может быть сопряжено с некоторыми трудностями. В течение 2023 и 2024 годов особое внимание будет уделяться планированию внедрения обновленной СНС на основе уроков, извлеченных при внедрении СНС 2008. Этот процесс будет осуществляться в тесном сотрудничестве со всеми странами.

На сегодняшний день в процессе обновления обеспечивается тесное сотрудничество с ответственными за другие международные статистические стандарты в целях обеспечения максимальной согласованности стандартов. На первом месте отмечается масштабное сотрудничество с группой МВФ, ответственной за обновление РПБ, которое переросло в процессы принятия совместных решений по вопросам обновления с участием Консультативной группы экспертов по национальным счетам и Комитета по статистике платежного баланса МВФ. Кроме того, осуществлялось плодотворное сотрудничество с ответственными за статистику государственных финансов, денежно-кредитную и финансовую статистику, эколого-экономический учет, классификации товаров и отраслей, статистику занятости и использования времени.

Хотя еще предстоит проделать большой объем работы по подготовке СНС 2025, для нее была создана прекрасная основа, и мировое статистическое сообщество с уверенностью смотрит в последующие годы, продолжая трудиться над обеспечением актуальности этого ключевого международного статистического стандарта сегодня и в будущем.

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HISTORICAL SCIENCE

The history of development of Turkic tribes.

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Annotation

The article discusses the unknown historical developments in the history of the Turkic peoples.

“The Turkic hand, which uses the sword with unique skill, is also able to wrap the wounds of the defeated people”.

English writer - Lord Byron (George Gordon Byron)

The Turks, the people with a three-thousand-year history, had been inhabiting an area stretching from the Pacific Ocean to the Mediterranean Sea, from Beijing to Vienna and to Tunisia, Algeria. Despite the colossal territory between Western Europe and China, this area, part of Eurasia, with its natural resources, diverse population and unique culture remain unnoticed for a long time, as a result of which it was even considered as non-existent.

The heart of Eurasia - the Great Steppe stretching from the Chinese Steppe to the Carpathians, bordered from the north by a strip of Siberian taiga, and from the south - by the deserts of the Iranian plateau and also the oases of Persia.

In ancient times, the Greeks called the Great Steppe Scythia, the Persians called it Turan, and the Chinese - "the steppe of the northern barbarians.

As a result, China, the Middle East, and Byzantine Europe framed a picture - "Turkic-Mongolian steppe."

The history of the Great Steppe is the history of the Turco-Mongolian hordes, contesting the best pastures and moving with their herds for centuries, over vast expanses that nature has adapted to the physical constitution and way of life. In the prehistoric era, the movement of nomads was mainly from West to East. When the nomads of the Iranian race -the Indo-Europeans, whom the Greek historians called "Scythians" and "Sarmatians" (in Iranian texts - Saks), went very far to the

northeast to the Altai and Sayan, while the other Indo-Europeans settled on the Oases of Tarzhim from Kashgar to Kuch, Karashahr and Turpan.

However, since the Christian era, the trend has reversed in the opposite direction from the East to the West.

As a result, Indo-European dialects no longer dominate the oases of the future Turkestan, and as for "internal changes", there was a change in the hegemony of the nomadic clans of the Turks and Mongols, who always craved for power over other hordes: the Turks - Huns - 9th century BC, the Mongols - sien - Pei - 3rd century AD, Mongols - Jujans - 5th century, Turks - Tu-Kyu - 6th century, Turks - Uigurs - 8th century, Turks Kirkizes - 9th century, Mongol - Khitans - 10th century, Turks-Keraids or Naimans - 12th century, Turks - the Mongols - 13th century, and, finally, the Turks of Temurud - the 14th-15th centuries.

The same thing happened in the west as in the east. In Europe, in the Russian steppes, which continued the Asian steppe, groups of Attila, Bulgars, Avars, Hungarians (the latter were from the Finno-Ugric group, but were part of the Hun aristocracy), Khazars, Pechenegs, teams, Chingisids succeeded each other. The same can be said about the Islamic lands, where the process of Islamization and Iranization among the Turkic conquerors of Iran and Anatolia is an exact copy of the Sinicization of the conquerors of the Heavenly Empire - the Turks, Mongols, Tungus. The Khan here became the Sultan and Padishah, just as there - the Son of Heaven in Tengrism or the vicegerent of Allah on earth in Islami. Iran was alternately ruled and exterminated each other by the Ghaznavid Turks, the Seljuk Turks, the Harezm Turks, the Mongols Turks, the Temurid Turks, the Sheibenid Turks, not to mention the Ottoman Turks, who rushed across the Muslim lands like an arrow and defeated the weakened Seljuks in Asia Minor and then - unheard of! - rushed to conquer Byzantium. And this process has become one of the geographical laws in world history.

There is however another, opposite law of assimilation of nomadic conquerors by old civilizations and countries; this phenomenon has two sides: first

of all, demographic - the barbarian horsemen, having turned into the ruling class, assimilate in the general mass, in the human anthill; then cultural - the conquered Chinese or Iranian civilization seduces, lulls, conquers its conqueror, and, in the end, one way or another destroys him.

The Turks linked their fate with the fate of all the peoples of the ancient world. Granted that the history of mankind has not been researched well and there are many gaps in the history of the Eurasian steppe. It is nonetheless important to note with certainty the fact that the history of the Turks is replete with events of exceptional richness that radically changed the picture of the world: Atilla and the Huns, the empire of Tabgach in northern China, the construction of Samarra, the Abbasids, the peaceful coexistence of all major religions in Uyghur Central Asia, the Seljuks of Iran, Genghis Khan and the Turkic-Mongolian hegemony, the Mamluks of Egypt, the Golden Horde which enslaved Russia for two centuries, Amir Temur, the Temurid renaissance in Samarkand Herat, Babur and the creation of an empire The Great Moghuls, the Ottoman Empire - the leading world power in the 16th century, Ataturk and the world national revolution in Turkey.

The Turks are an original people, they are, at a minimum, passionate lovers and connoisseurs of art, antiquarians, patrons, but they are also great creators: it was under the rule of the Turkic Wei dynasty in China that one of the best cultural schools was formed in the caves of Yun-Kang and Long Men; The Turks created the most beautiful and expressive monuments of Asia - the Great Friday Mosque in Isfahan, the Taj Mahal in Agra, the Registan in Samarkand and the Sulaiman Mosque in Istanbul. So, in front of us now are the legacies of the nomads - a living organism with its own specific laws and manifestations, as part of humanity, consisting of very different elements, but forming a magnificent combination, which can be called the specific name of the Türks. There is this legendary tale about the Supreme Father of all Turks, Tengri. Tengri once presented to the Turks a Big Kazan, made of pure copper, which was mounted on an iron tripod. All large and small tribes of the Turks ate from this Big Kazan, which was also called

Tengri Kazan, all ate from the same Kazan, and no one complained about the lack of food. Huge herds of mares and countless cattle grazed on the lands of the Turks. The hunt had always been successful. Children were healthy, families were strong, old people were respected, and men knew how to do everything: raise cattle, protect their lands from enemies, get along with neighbors and entering into trade relations with them.

The Turkic old people were famous for their wisdom and talent for eloquence which was passed down from generation to generation. Turkic girls shone with beauty, grace and intelligence, and Turkic youths were the most unsurpassed warriors. All Turks valued freedom, honor and dignity above all else.

The Turkish multiply in the bosom of their Father - Tengri, but every day the Day of the Great Parting was approaching, when the grown-up son had to saddle a horse and, having said goodbye to his father, enter the unknown world to him. And that day has come. The Turks removed the Tengri-Kazan from the iron tripod and, placing it on a glazed hearth, began to prepare a farewell meal. Craftsmen melted an iron tripod and made from it a large number of battle axes, iron tips for arrows and horses living in any shell, stirrups that allow riders to deftly control their war horses and fight with both hands, fast as lightning, sabers, pointed helmets, symbolizing the arch heavenly dome, the house of his Father - Tengri. Turkic women sewed a large number of leather harem pants and short shirts - clothes for riding and dashed off a large amount of felt for camping yurts, the native home of nomads. The farewell meal of the Turks from Tengri-Kazan was plentiful, and many would have remembered the unique taste of the food of their native home. And this meal from Tengri-Kazan was really a farewell ball, because when people were sated, Tengri-Kazan shattered into billions of small pieces.

The upper scattered part of Tengri - Kazan ascended into the sky and formed around Temir Kazyk (Polar Star) the Circle of Times in the form of transdiocal constellations, according to which the Türks could be determined in an unceasing course of time. Pieces of the middle part of Tengri Kazan formed a milky way in

the sky, by which the Türks could determine their location in Space, no matter in what part of the Earth they were and wherever they moved. The lower part of Tengri Kazan, which has always been confirmed by the action of Fire, scattered into billions of copper drops, which fell into the heart of every Turk and, passing from father to son, kept in the heart of the Turks an ardent love for their native home, for the Big Tengri Kazan. The remains of food from Tengri-Kazan fell on the land of the Turks and, having seeped into its depths, turned into many minerals, which in the future were supposed to feed the distant descendants of the Turks.

Having spent the last night in their native land, the Turks set out on a campaign in the morning. But he was not aggressive - it was a movement of new thought and a new spirit. For on their way to the Land of Sunset, the Turks went to places whose peoples were just beginning to learn what iron was, and even the smallest piece of iron was worth much more than gold equal to it. These people did not know what stirrups were, and even a two-horned fork (shanyshka), with the help of which the Turks ate hot meat without burning themselves, aroused great interest in them. These peoples, dressed in long-skirted dresses that hide their nails, but absolutely not adapted for foot and equestrian combat, were amazed at the design of Turkic harem pants, convenient for riding and everyday life. In their movement, the Turks brought to the world a qualitatively new level of (iron) civilization: a horse decorated to the level of a combat unit, a curved saber, a more effective melee weapon than a straight sword; new tactics and strategy for the use of large, but light (flying) cavalry units; clothing adapted for equestrian and foot combat, and much more, which for that time represented the most advanced level of scientific and technological progress.

The Turks brought the symbol of the Cross to the West as a designation of four arrows flying from one point (from Tengri Kazan) to different directions of the world, carrying on their tip the knowledge of a new civilization. The round and pointed helmets of the Turks, symbolizing the shape of the firmament, became the prototype of the cupolas of the Orthodox churches and mosques of the Islamic

world. Among the wise sayings about the Turks, there is one that especially corresponds to the essence "The Turk is like a pearl in a sea shell, which has no value while living in its dwelling, but when it comes out of the sea shell, it becomes valuable, serving as an adornment of royal crowns."

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MEDICAL SCIENCE

Results of new domestic hemostatic film usage for spleen injuries

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Relevance: Abdominal surgery today demonstrates a trend towards organ-preserving surgical treatment of injuries of parenchymal organs (kidneys, liver, spleen) due to their high functional significance. Traditional methods of hemostasis, such as U-shaped sutures, packing with omentum, etc., are still relevant, as they provide compression of intraorganic vessels. However, in the presence of capillary, superficial bleeding, it is advisable to use alternative sparing methods, since suturing entails additional tissue damage. This substantiates the rationality of using seamless technologies for replacing organ defects and/or hemostasis in the damaged area. There are several drugs provided by both foreign and domestic manufacturers. Their effectiveness depends on the approach to the preparation of the morphological base of the samples, which is usually based on spongy structures of animal (collagen) or synthetic (cellulose salts) origin. This spongy structure has sticky properties; thus, the surface of the implant is fixed to the surface of the damaged organ without additional suture material and other means. High adhesive characteristics are a mandatory criterion for stopping bleeding. In addition to adhesive properties, there are other important factors, such as absorption and sorption, which depend on the chemical structure and organization of the spatial structure (porosity of hemostatic sponges). Despite the increase in the number of operations and the growing need of surgical departments for hemostatic implants used for local hemostasis, a unified algorithm for evaluating the effectiveness of these materials has not yet been developed.

Materials and methods: The totality of the results of the experimental and preclinical studies made it possible to obtain permission from the ethical committee to conduct the first clinical experiment and introduce a new hemostatic

implant into practice. For this purpose, two groups were formed. In the main group, the developed film implant was used as the final hemostasis on the wound surface of the spleen. In the comparison group, hemostasis was achieved only by flashing and (or) temporary compression of the area of the damaged surface. For a more adequate analysis, the hemostatic efficacy of the new film was considered separately for various injuries of the spleen (intraoperatively in operations on the spleen and traumatic injuries). The analysis included only limited in volume, no more than 3-4 cm, traumatic injuries of the spleen, without injuries of the main vessels. Unfortunately, with injuries of the spleen, it is not always possible to achieve effective hemostasis due to the anatomical features of this organ, therefore, in our material, it was possible only in 7 (63.6%) patients in the comparison group and 7 (87.5%) patients in the main group. In this situation, forced splenectomy has to be performed, which was done in 4 (36.4%) cases in the comparison group and in 1 (12.5%) case in the main group.

Discussion: The groups differed in time spent on hemostasis from the surface of the spleen wound: 35 ± 10.2 minutes in the comparison group and 20.6 ± 5.6 minutes in the main group ($t=3.91$; $p<0.05$). The total operation time in the comparison group - 105.9 ± 13.8 minutes was almost half an hour higher than the same indicator in the main group - 81.9 ± 16.2 minutes ($t=3.39$; $p<0.05$).

The amount of discharge during interventions on the spleen is less than with liver damage, so on the first day in the comparison group there was an average of 89.1 ± 29.8 ml of discharge, in the main group - 61.3 ± 20.3 ml ($t=2, 42$; $p<0.05$). On the third day, the amount of discharge is minimal: in the comparison group, on average, 50.5 ± 23.3 ml of discharge, in the main group - 27.5 ± 15 ml ($t=2.43$; $p<0.05$).

According to the amount of discharge from the drains, the duration of drainage was shorter in the main group - 3.1 ± 0.8 days versus 4.2 ± 1.0 ($t=2.53$; $p<0.05$). The terms of hospitalization differed slightly, but significantly: 7.9 ± 1.4 days in the comparison group, 6.6 ± 1.1 days in the main group ($t=2.23$; $p<0.05$).

Conclusion: The use of a new domestic implant for traumatic injury to the spleen made it possible to increase the efficiency of achieving hemostasis from 63.6% to 87.5%, to reduce the time to stop bleeding from 35 ± 10.2 to 20.6 ± 5.6 minutes ($t=3.91$; $p<0.05$) and total operation time from 105.9 ± 13.8 to 81.9 ± 16.2 minutes ($t=3.39$; $p<0.05$); reduce the volume of discharge through the drains from 89.1 ± 29.8 to 61.3 ± 20.3 ml on the first day ($t=2.42$; $p<0.05$) and from 50.5 ± 23.3 to $27, 5 \pm 15.4$ ml on the third day ($t=2.43$; $p<0.05$); to reduce the drainage time from 4.2 ± 1.0 to 3.1 ± 0.8 days ($t=2.53$; $p<0.05$) and the duration of the postoperative hospital period from 7.9 ± 1.4 to 6.6 ± 1.1 days ($t=5.10$; $p<0.05$).

Optimization of treatment methods for herniated discs

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Relevance. About 30% of the population of developed countries suffer from chronic back pain. One of the causes of back pain is degenerative-dystrophic changes in the spine and intervertebral disc with the formation of a hernia leading to a narrowing of the spinal canal and creating conditions for the development of compression or vascular spinal syndrome.

Purpose of the study. Improving the methods of treatment of herniated discs.

Materials and research methods. The object of the study were 120 patients aged 41 to 69 years, including 53 men and 67 women, who were operated on for a herniated disc in the lumbosacral spine using the posterior approach (interlaminectomy, removal of disc herniation, interspinous dynamic fusion using the Diam system) and were sent for rehabilitation 2-3 days after surgical treatment.

Research results. On the 2nd-3rd day after the operation, all patients had pain in the lumbar spine with irradiation to the lower extremity. Patients described pain in different ways: burning, cutting, twisting, shooting. Reflex syndromes were most often unilateral. The most frequent complaints were pains in the lumbosacral region with irradiation: in one lower limb - 94% (78 people), both lower limbs - 6% (5 people), in the buttock area - 81% (67 people), in inguinal region - 8% (7 people). According to the four-component visual analog scale of pain, the values ranged from 5.6±0.4 to 7.9±0.3 points. Changes in motor activity were expressed in a decrease in muscle strength of the toes or the entire foot, which was assessed in points: no change in muscle strength - in 76 people (0 points), decrease in muscle strength of the toe / toes in 33 patients (1 point), moderate foot paresis 11 people (2 points). Deep paresis was not identified. There was a violation of sensitivity according to the type of hypoesthesia in accordance with the level of damage in 74 people: along the entire lower limb - in 34% (25 people), a violation of sensitivity from the knee and below - in 45% (33 people), the back and plantar

surface of the foot, and also toes - in 19% (14 people), gluteal region - in 1% (1 patient), along the outer edge of the thigh - 1% (1 patient), inguinal region - 10% (7 people).

Conclusions: Thus, the use of interdiscal laminectomy is the least traumatic and the most effective method of treatment.

Results of new domestic hemostatic film usage for liver injuries

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Relevance: A wide variety of hemostatic agents are available to achieve hemostasis, the composition of which is determined by the surgical need as well as by their own advantages and disadvantages. Among hemostatic agents are considered to be dressings, sponges, meshes, or powders that can be applied to the bleeding area to facilitate coagulation. Physical and absorbable hemostatic agents such as bone wax, collagen, and cellulose are suitable for stopping bleeding at low pressure, but can cause embolism and prevent healing. Biological agents such as thrombin or fibrin sealants can elicit an immunological response and are costly, but they can be applied and act quickly. However, fibrin sealants are less useful in injuries due to their need in a dry field. They are most useful in patients with coagulopathy, since the anticoagulant effect is achieved through the direct formation of fibrin, the end product of the clotting process. Less effective in patients with coagulopathy are drugs based on an intact coagulation pathway, such as those containing collagen, cellulose, or gelatin. In terms of patient safety, polysaccharide haemostatics appear to provide the best safety profile and are also beneficial in injuries.

Materials and methods: The totality of the results of the experimental and preclinical studies made it possible to obtain permission from the ethical committee to conduct the first clinical experiment and introduce a new hemostatic implant into practice. For this purpose, two groups were formed. In the main group, a developed film implant was used as the final hemostasis on the wound surface of the liver or spleen. In the comparison group, hemostasis was achieved only by flashing and (or) temporary compression of the area of the damaged surface. For a more adequate analysis, patients within the groups were divided into types of operations on the liver, and the hemostatic effectiveness of the new film in

various injuries of the spleen (intraoperatively in operations on the spleen and traumatic injuries) was also considered separately.

Liver resections were performed mainly for hemangioma, in the comparison group - 24 (58.5%), in the main group - 15 (60%). With liver injury, in most cases, it was possible to stop bleeding with the help of local hemostasis, in the comparison group - 14 (34.1%), in the main group - 8 (32%). Only with a significant injury was the need for forced resection of the liver. During the analysis of the nature of the liver wound primary treatment, it becomes obvious that in the main group, in contrast to the comparison group, the need for stitching the injured surface of the liver was significantly less, 3 (12%) versus 14 (34.1%). In 88% of cases, hemostasis was achieved by coagulation of the injured liver surface ($\chi^2=3,983$; (df=1); p=0.046).

Discussion: If in the main group it was possible to achieve hemostasis only by coagulation of the injured surface of the liver in 21 (84%) cases, then in the comparison group it was possible only in 21 (51.2%) patients ($\chi^2=7.242$; (df=2); p=0.027). Hemostasis was achieved by coagulation and stitching of the injured surface of the liver in the comparison group in 16 (39%) cases, while in the main group it was required only in 3 (12%) patients. Doubtful hemostasis with the need to suture the liver wound was noted in both groups, but also prevailed in the comparison group - 4 (9.8%) versus 1 (4%). Plugging was performed in case of doubtful hemostasis after suturing in patients with traumatic liver injury.

The need to use several types of hemostasis, of course, was reflected in the time period spent on hemostasis from the surface of the liver wound, so in the comparison group, on average, it took 29.2 ± 11.2 minutes for liver resection, while in the main group only 15.3 ± 4.0 minutes. Even more time was spent with liver injury: 46.8 ± 15.9 minutes in the comparison group and 27.0 ± 6.3 minutes in the main group. In general, it can be stated that in the comparison group, hemostasis took more time - 36.5 ± 15.8 minutes than in the main group - 20.0 ± 7.6 minutes (t=5.67; p<0, 05). Due to the use of new methods of local hemostasis, it was

possible to significantly reduce the total operation time for interventions on the liver from 179.9 ± 47.8 minutes in the comparison group to 148.6 ± 39.0 minutes in the main group ($t=2.90$; $p<0.05$).

The drains were removed earlier in the main group - on day 4.0 ± 1.3 , in the comparison group - on day 6.2 ± 1.9 ($t=5.55$; $p<0.05$). As mentioned above, with injuries, the discharge was more, therefore, the duration of drainage exceeded the average: in the main group - 4.6 ± 1.4 days, in the comparison group - 6.9 ± 2.5 days. The timing of hospitalization depends on many factors, but the most important are the nature of the healing of the postoperative wound and the duration of drainage. It is not surprising, therefore, that the duration of hospitalization after liver surgery in the main group was 7.4 ± 1.1 days versus 9.0 ± 1.4 days in the comparison group ($t=5.10$; $p<0.05$).

Conclusion: The use of a hemostatic film implant in liver surgery showed good efficiency in stopping parenchymal bleeding, which was manifested by a reduction in the need for additional stitching of injured tissue from 39% (in 16 out of 41 patients in the comparison group) to 12% (in 3 out of 25 patients in the main group) and plugging from 9.8% (in 4 patients) to 4% (in 1 patient) ($\chi^2=7,242$; $(df=2)$; $p=0.027$), a decrease in the time to achieve hemostasis from 36.5 ± 15.8 to 20 ± 7.6 minutes ($t=5.67$; $p<0.05$), decrease in drainage volume from 128 ± 54.3 to 73 ± 21 ml on the first day ($t=5.81$; $p<0.05$) and from 67.8 ± 45.4 to 31.7 ± 16.8 ml on the third day ($t=4.56$; $p<0.05$), earlier removal of drains - 6.2 ± 1.9 vs. 4.0 ± 1.3 days ($t=5.55$; $p<0.05$) and shortening of the postoperative period from 9.0 ± 1.4 to 7.4 ± 1.1 days ($t=5.10$; $p<0.05$).

Composite hemostatic plate for parenchymatic bleeding from the liver

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Various physical, chemical and human factors can lead to tissue injury and cause bleeding. Injuries are responsible for 10% of all deaths worldwide, and blood loss is the most common preventable cause of death after injury. Bleeding and hemorrhagic shock are responsible for 30-40% of traumatic deaths. Thus, stopping bleeding at an early stage is a very suitable method to reduce mortality and morbidity. In addition, perioperative and examination-related procedures may lead to a risk of bleeding. In order to reduce the damage caused by bleeding or avoid bleeding, reduce the use of blood products, and improve patient survival and quality of life, methods such as compression or pressing, thermoelectric cautery, surgical ligation or suture, intravenous administration, and the use of local hemostatic agents have been used to stop bleeding.

Our team has developed a new version of a hemostatic film, which has a complex composition and is a composite material, its main composition is cellulose derivatives: a) a layer that provides high adhesion to the wet surface of biological tissues and is a film of Na-CMC (85%) + Ca^{2+} ions in a concentration (15%) with a thickness of 50 μm ; b) the second layer is a reinforced hemostatic layer, which includes Na-CMC (63%) + oxidized viscose (12%) + Ca^{2+} ions (25%). In the second layer there are fibers of oxidized viscose with a thread thickness of up to 25 microns, with a distance between the fibers of 500-1000 microns;

The outer layer is a hydrophobic film up to 10 microns thick made of vegetable oil (cotton oil). Viscose fiber is extracted by processing natural plant cellulose and is considered a modification of cellulose fiber called rayon cellulose. In our study, the native state of both fibers was assessed using a stereomicroscope (MBS-2 LOMO).

Under the influence of oxidants, both fibers changed in different ways. Cotton cellulose showed high resistance, the degree of fiber breakage decreased by only

1.5 times in 4 hours. Viscose fiber lost strength 3 times in 3 hours, completely disintegrated by 4 hours.

Visual and stereomicroscopic evaluation of the new composite coating shows that the fibers are distributed in the center of the composite film and form an integral whole with other components of the film. When viewed under a stereomicroscope, the gauze fibers completely retained their mesh structure. Film thickness 2 mm.

Ex vivo studies. To assess adhesion to biological tissues, isolated sheep liver with a shelf life of not more than 1 hour in saline was used. 1 cm² of hemostatic film was attached to the surface of the liver and the adhesion force was measured.

As a result of the tests, it was found that the adhesiveness of the prepared composite material using oxidized viscose is 961 Pa (Pascal), which is a sufficient indicator for covering the wound surface, tight fixation and non-separation from it. In general, in a comparative aspect, among various variants of cellulose-based biomaterials, it was found that the inclusion of oxidized viscose in the composition improves the physicochemical properties of the composite hemostatic film, including the best indicators in terms of tensile strength, adhesion to the surface of the isolated liver, and also in the presence of blood and plasma, hygroscopicity and bactericidal activity.

The effect of a hemostatic film on the blood coagulation system in in vitro experiments was evaluated - a composite hemostatic film reinforced with viscose fibers was used as a material for experimental studies. A plate reinforced with cotton cellulose fibers served as a control. In experiments in vitro, the study of the effect on the total coagulation activity of whole blood was carried out using native blood of 10 healthy volunteer donors. Research methods were carried out in accordance with the guidelines of the Research Institute of Hematology and Blood Transfusion (2005). In particular, the Lee-White blood clotting time was checked, which shows the overall coagulation activity of the blood. The studies were carried out with voluntary consent, observing the rules of asepsis and antisepsis, blood sampling was performed from the vein of the ulnar region into a test tube. The time

of blood clotting was considered the time from the moment of immersion of the hemostatic film into the test tube until the appearance of a clot, which was 5.27 ± 0.50 sec. Donor whole blood served as the study control. According to this study, the time of blood clotting in the control group was 11.2 ± 0.54 sec. Normally, according to this method of research, the time of blood clotting is from 4 minutes 55 seconds to 11 minutes 44 seconds.

The results of in vitro studies have shown that the composite hemostatic film shortens the clotting time, which indicates an increase in the overall coagulation activity of whole blood. This will allow it to be used as a local hemostatic agent. As a result of studies carried out in vitro conditions, it was proved that the developed hemostatic composite plate meets all the necessary requirements for this type of implant. The purpose of further studies was to evaluate the biological effect and study the timing of implant resorption in the proposed model of liver damage in experimental animals.

As a comparison group (control), studies were carried out using a composite plate with reinforcement from a mesh of oxidized cotton cellulose (12 animals). The second group (experimental) (12 animals) consisted of using a composite plate with a reinforced mesh of oxidized viscose.

Primarily, the hemostatic effect was studied by applying a composite plate reinforced with a mesh of oxidized cotton cellulose. The bleeding surface of the liver was dried and a 1.0x1.0 cm mesh was applied, which completely covered the wound defect. The hemostatic effect was manifested after the adhesion of the plate to the wound surface of the liver and the impregnation of the mesh fibers with blood, followed by gradual hemostasis. The hemostatic effect was not sufficiently pronounced; therefore, it was necessary to change the mesh implant from 2 to 3 times to achieve complete hemostasis. The adhesion of the plate to the surface of the liver is moderate; the plate is easily removed from the wound surface, but does not spontaneously move. The time to achieve final hemostasis ranged from 1 to 4 minutes, depending on the intensity of bleeding from the liver wound. The surgical

wound was sutured with double-row sutures without leaving drains and debridement of the abdominal cavity.

The postoperative period in the operated animals was uneventful. After awakening, the rats actively moved around the cage. 6 hours after the operation, they began to drink water and take food.

Assessment of the state of the implant 12 hours after fixation showed that complete hemostasis was achieved. The grid is adjacent to the surface of the liver, but is somewhat displaced (by 1/3). The mesh is impregnated with fibrin threads. The omentum is adjacent to the liver. The mesh is easily separated from the surface of the liver wound. There were no signs of infection.

One day after the operation, the animals are active. On the 3rd-7th day after the mesh implantation, the animals are active, the skin wound has completely healed. The abdomen is soft and painless. Physiological functions are not violated. Euthanasia of animals of this group revealed that the mesh implant had almost completely moved away from the wound surface, deformed and surrounded by dense fibrin overlays, soldered to the omentum. The mesh fibers are loose, easily torn when pulled with tweezers. The liver is not enlarged, the wound has practically healed.

On the 21-30th day after implantation of the plate on the surface of the liver, the experimental animals are practically healthy. During euthanasia, complete wound healing was established. There are no pathological changes in the abdominal cavity. The liver is not enlarged. The surface is smooth. The wound has healed. In the region of the edge of the liver, an area of limited fibrosis is determined, which is connected with the surrounding tissues and the omentum by thin adhesive bands. When dissecting the area of fibrosis, the remnants and fragments of the mesh are not determined.

In the process of observation, the adhesion of the plate is strong enough and it is not possible to separate it from the surface of the liver. In the postoperative period, the condition of the animals corresponds to the post-anesthesia period. Two hours

after the operation, the animals are active and move around the cage. Actively respond to stimuli. After 4 hours, they drink water and eat food.

One day after the operation, the condition of the animals is satisfactory. On the 7th day of the experiment, when using a composite material made of viscose, the wound area was clean, thin scars remained at the site of the wound. There are no infiltrates around various organs, the size of the liver is close to normal, there are no changes in other organs of the abdominal cavity. When attempting to separate the composite film with tweezers, the film does not come off. On the 14th day of the experiment, when using a composite material made of viscose, the wound area was clean, the signs of the adhesive process were not very pronounced. There are no infiltrates around the wound of the liver organs, the size of the liver returned to normal. The composite film is very thin, the film does not come off when you try to separate it with tweezers. Blood clots in and around the wound are not detected. On the 30th day, the remains of the composite plate are visible on the surface of the liver, fibrin layers in the process of resorption. There are no signs of inflammation or infiltration.

Conducted studies with hemostatic preparations and implants in liver surgery have shown that the most rapid effect of hemostasis can be achieved when using coatings with high adhesion to wet tissues, as well as sufficient tensile strength. Taking into account the dynamic indicators, the durability of the coating for 3-7 days and the preservation of adhesive properties are also quite important. At the same time, the wound dressing should not have an irritating property and not cause an extensive adhesive process involving surrounding organs.

On the 7th day in the animals of the experimental group, the subsidence of the inflammatory process was microscopically noted, the minimum fibrous layer, without a macrophage reaction; the capillary pattern was preserved.

On the 21st and 30th days of the experiment, the animals of the experimental group microscopically noted the complete absence of cellular elements of

inflammation and tissue reaction to the hemostatic implant. At the same time, no hemostatic implant was observed on the wound surface of the liver.

Сравнительный анализ результатов линейного протезирования и экзопротезирования восходящего отдела аорты в сочетании с заменой аортального клапана

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Цель: оценить эффективность супракоронарного и экзопротезирования восходящей аорты у больных с аортальными пороками сердца.

Материал и методы: В отделении хирургии сочетанной патологии сердца ГУ «РСНМПЦХ» им. В Вахидова с 2017 года по настоящее время выполнено 90 оперативных вмешательств с патологией восходящей аорты в сочетании с аортальным пороком. Больные были разделены на 2 группы: 50 пациентам выполнена протезирование аортального клапана и замена восходящей аорты (I группа, СП+ПАК), и 40 больным выполнено протезирование аортального клапана в сочетании с экзопротезированием восходящей аорты (II группа ЭП+ПАК). Большинство пациентов составили мужчины 69%. Средний возраст больных составил $42,2 \pm 17$ года. По этиологии порока АК больные распределились следующим образом: дегенеративный порок выявлен в 27,5% (11 из 40) случаев в группе больных СП+ПАК и 36% (18 из 50) – в группе ЭП+ПАК. Чуть более половина случаев как в группе СП+ПАК (52,5%; 21 из 40), так и в группе ЭП+ПАК (52%; 26 из 50) была представлена двустворчатым АК. В остальных случаях диагностирован ревматический порок АК: 20% в группе СП+ПАК и 12% в группе ЭП+ПАК. Стеноз АК был выявлен в большинстве 60% (24 из 40) случаев в группе СП+ПАК и 64% (32 из 50) в группе ЭП+ПАК ($p=0.827$). По данным ЭхоКГ конечно-диастолический объем левого желудочка в группе СП+ПАК в среднем был равен 152.72 ± 49.4 , а в группе ЭП+ПАК – 153.12 ± 42.98 мл, размер ФК АК в I группе $24,4 \pm 3,4$ мм и $23,9 \pm 1,7$ мм во II группе. Результаты: Длительность ИК составила в среднем в группе СП+ПАК 152.68 ± 48.87 мин, что было значимо больше, чем в группе ЭП+ПАК, где данный показатель составил в среднем

96.62±32.49 мин. Соответственно продолжительность окклюзии аорты составила в среднем в группе СП+ПАК 114.33±29.26 мин, что была также статистически значимо больше, чем в группе ЭП+ПАК, где длительность ОА составила в среднем 72.28±24.34 мин. Длительность искусственной вентиляции легких составила в среднем 20.58±8.05 часов в группе СП+ПАК и 15.7±9.65 часов, в группе ЭП+ПАК. При этом частота случаев с необходимостью применения продленного ИВЛ была также меньше в группе ЭП+ПАК, чем в группе СП+ПАК (20% против 55%). Общий объем послеоперационной кровопотери составил 252.5±68.83 мл в группе СП+ПАК и 305.4±81.12 мл в группе ЭП+ПАК. Частота выполнения реопераций в группе СП+ПАК была выше, чем в группе ЭП+ПАК – 8% (3 из 40) против 2% (1 из 50). Случаев с летальным исходом в группе СП+ПАК было 15% (6 из 40 больных), что было больше, чем в группе ЭП+ПАК – 4% (2 случая из 50).

Выводы: Сравнительный анализ результатов хирургического лечения пациентов с пороками АК и аневризмой ВоАо показал, что выполнение операции протезирования АК в сочетании с наружным окутыванием ВоАо синтетическим сосудистым протезом позволило получить хорошие ранние послеоперационные результаты, в частности, сократить длительность ИК, время окклюзии аорты, частоту случаев необходимости проведения продленного ИВЛ, а также снизить послеоперационную летальность в 3,5 раза.

Синдром Лоу у детей

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Аннотация. Рассмотрены вопросы клиники, лечения и исхода около-церебро-ренального синдрома Лоу у детей. Описано наблюдение двух мальчиков из одной семьи с синдромом Лоу, у которых поражение почек характеризовалось синдромом Фанкони.

Ключевые слова: дети, окуло-церебро-ренальный синдром, синдром Лоу.

Annotation. The issues of clinic, treatment and outcome of Lowe`s oculo-cerebro-renal syndrome in children are considered. The observation of two boys from the same family with Lowe`s syndrome, in which kidney damage was characterized by Fanconi`s syndrome, is described.

Key words: children, oculo-cerebro-renal syndrome, Low`s syndrome.

В мировой литературе заболевание известно под названием «окуло-церебро-ренальный синдром», или синдром Лоу (Lowe), Lowe-syndrom, OCRL; реже как синдром Lowe-Terry-McLachlan, синдром Lowe-Bickel, глазо-почечно-мозговой синдром Fanconi, крайне редко как синдром Ziyl. Причина синдрома Лоу — врожденная недостаточность фермента фосфатидилинозитол-4,5-бифосфат-5-фосфатазы, вызванная [мутациями](#) в гене OCRL. [Ген](#) картирован на длинном плече X-хромосомы (Xq25-q26).

Материал и методы. Под нашим наблюдением находился мальчик О, 8 лет. Поступил с жалобами со стороны матери на полиурию, полидипсию, беспричинное повышение температуры тела. Из анамнеза, ребенок от 4 беременности и родов, протекавших без явной патологии, от близкородственного брака (отец и мать двоюродные брат и сестра). До настоящего времени у ребенка отмечались невыясненной этиологии анемия, по поводу чего неоднократно лечился по месту жительства. Данные жалобы в течение последнего года, не обследован, не лечился. При осмотре мальчик

правильного телосложения, пониженного питания. Нарушений со стороны скелетной мускулатуры нет. Обращает на себя внимание светлая кожа, светлый цвет глаз, голубые склеры. Отмечается постоянный горизонтальный нистагм, расходящееся косоглазие, понижение зрения. Слизистые чистые, бледные. Консультация окулиста - тапеторетинальная абиатрофия. Атрофия зрительного нерва. Нистагм. Расходящееся косоглазие. По внутренним органам без особенностей. Со стороны нервной системы: мальчик замкнут, в контакт вступает неохотно, ответы односложные. Очень привязан к матери. Интеллект сохранен. В анализе крови выраженная анемия: эр.-3,0, Нв - 82г/л, ЦП.- 0,8, лейкоц.- 7,7, п/я - 0, с/я- 46, эоз.- 3, лимф.- 47, мон.- 4, СОЭ- 5мм/час. В анализах мочи: белок - следы, лейкоц. и эр. ед. Проба Нечипоренко: лейкоц.-3000, эр.-1000. В пробе Зимницкого относительная плотность мочи- 1002-1004, соотношение дневного диуреза и ночного 1:1. В моче глюкозурия, аминокислотурия, кальциурия, метаболический канальцевый ацидоз. Суточный диурез 5 литров (соответствует количеству выпитой жидкости). В сыворотке крови содержание мочевины- 6,2ммоль/л., креатинин - 0,05 ммоль/л. Общий белок-74,5 г/л. Кальций-2,0 ммоль/л, калий-3,0 ммоль/л, общий холестерин 7,1, триглицериды-1,3. НвSAg- отр. АСЛО-250, СРБ- отрицательный, сахар крови -5,0 ммоль/л. Температура тела постоянно 38,0-38,5 С. На УЗИ почек и МРТ: левосторонний гидронефроз. Из дополнительного анамнеза выяснено, что второй ребенок в семье, 12 лет, с 8 лет был оформлен в интернат для незрячих детей в связи с врожденной глаукомой, горизонтальным нистагмом. При диспансерном обследовании у мальчика выявлена анемия тяжелой степени, не поддающаяся лечению антианемическими препаратами. При углубленном обследовании у больного также выявлена патология со стороны почек (вторично сморщенная почка) и признаки почечной недостаточности, по поводу чего ребенок в течение последнего года получает сеансы гемодиализа 2 раза в неделю. Признаков выраженной умственной отсталости у обоих мальчиков не было. Первый

ребенок в семье также длительно страдал тяжелой формой железодефицитной анемии и в возрасте 12 лет умер от анемии неясной этиологии. Назначение препаратов индометацина в дозе 0,025+ гипотиазида 0,025 постоянно позволили нормализовать температуру тела, уменьшить полидипсию и полиурию до 1,5 литров в сутки. Мальчик в удовлетворительном состоянии выписан на амбулаторное лечение. Однако больной через год поступает вновь в тяжелом состоянии с признаками почечной недостаточности - мочевины в сыворотке крови 35,0ммоль/л, креатинин-0,4 ммоль/л., анемия тяжелой степени (Hb-60г/л). В моче протеинурия (белок-0,132%, единичные лейкоциты и эритроциты). АД - 120/80. Изменения со стороны зрения не прогрессировали. Ребенок в настоящее время также находится на гемодиализе.

Таким образом, у 2 членов мужского пола из одной семьи наблюдается одинаковая патология - синдром Лоу. Прогноз у данного заболевания неблагоприятный. Возможен летальный исход вследствие развития вторичных инфекционных осложнений, ацидемической комы, отека легких, мозга, терминальной почечной недостаточности.

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Хирургическая лечения килевидной деформации грудной клетки у детей

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Андижанский государственный медицинский институт, Узбекистан. Килевидная деформация грудной клетки является врожденным дефектом развития, который характеризуется выпячиванием вперед грудины и сочленяющихся с ней ребер. КДГК является второй по частоте после воронкообразной деформации. По данным авторов данная патология расценивается не только как косметический дефект, но и как причина функциональных нарушений со стороны органов дыхания, сердца и даже психологии детей. Выраженный косметический дефект у детей старшем возрасте приводит к замкнутости иногда агрессивности, нарушению социальной адаптацией в обществе. Основным методом лечение является хирургическое, т.е. корригирующая торакопластика.

Цель: обосновать методику коррекции в зависимости от типа килевидной деформации и определить оптимальный возраст операции.

Материал и методы: за последние 5 лет в клинику детской хирургии были госпитализированы для обследования и лечение 86 детей КДГК различного типа. Возраст детей от 4 до 14 лет. По полу детей распределили мальчиков - 61, девочек – 25. По типу (классификация Баирова Г.А., и Фокина А.А.) деформации: 1. Манубриокостальный тип 20-детей, этот тип характеризуется изгибам вперед рукоятки грудной клетки .2. Корпорокостальный тип: 45-детей отмечалась выпячивание средней и нижней трети грудины. 3. Костальный – 21 детей, наблюдался изгиб перед реберными хрящами парастернально в виде подковообразной деформации.

Анамнестические данные указывали на то, что почти у всех детей деформация грудной клетки были замечены вскоре после рождении. С возрастом у детей отмечалась болезненное ощущение за грудиной и нарушения психологического статуса. При психологическом обследовании выявлено, что дети младшего возраста комплексу неполноценности не

вызывали особых беспокойств. С возрастом нарастало влияние деформации, развивалась апатия, застенчивость, недовольство внешним видом. Все дети после предварительного обследования были оперированы, показанием явилась косметический дефект и функциональные нарушения со стороны органов грудной клетки, что подтверждает наличие утомляемости, одышки и сердцебиение при незначительной физической нагрузке. За основу метода торакопластики мы использовали метод Баирова которая заключалась в резекции деформированных ребер, поперечная стернотомия и фиксация давящей повязкой. Нами было дополнено к методике: а) миопластика над корригированной грудиной, б) продольная клиновидная стернотомия при корпорокостальном типе, в) максимальная укорочение нижних ребер:

Таким образом, КДГК у детей с возрастом прогрессируя, приводит к функциональным нарушениям органов грудной полости и нарушению психического статуса. Что является показанием к оперативной коррекции. Хирургическая лечения данной патологии с изменённым методом коррекции дает возможность, улучшить результаты в отдаленных сроках.

An integrated approach to the diagnosis of prostate cancer

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The purpose of the study: to improve the results of prostate cancer diagnosis

Materials and methods of research

The material of the study was a group of men in the number of 156 men examined in the period from 2020 to 2021, who were examined by a urologist of RSSPMCO and R MHRUz. The main group consisted of 120 people (76.9%) and 36 people (23.1%) – the control group. The bulk of the examined patients of the main group were men on average – 40 (33.33%) and the elderly – 54 people (45.00%).

In the main and control groups, we performed a finger rectal examination (FRE), determined the level of PSA in the blood serum, performed TRUSE (Transrectal Ultrasound Examination) of PG (with PDI and compression elastographic enhancement) and MRI of the pelvic organs, we used a targeted biopsy with histological verification of the process as the basis for diagnosis. The bulk – 54.17% were patients with prostate cancer, and the combination of prostate cancer+BPH (benign prostatic hyperplasia) – 24.17%, due to the predominant age of the examined individuals, it was on these patients that the possibilities of research methods in the diagnosis of prostate cancer were studied.

Conclusions

FRE is only one of the purely subjective methods of studying the PG, entirely dependent on the experience of the doctor conducting the research and can only be a starting point for further research of the patient.

The determination of blood PSA is a fairly effective marker in the diagnosis of prostate cancer in the screening examination in the age group up to 60 years, allowing to suspect prostate cancer at levels of total blood PSA within the "gray zone", i.e., at a PSA level from 4 to 10 ng /ml.

A comprehensive diagnostic approach (PSA>4ng/ml+ FRE+ TRUSE) with high sensitivity (94.2%) significantly increases specificity (83.9%) and accuracy

(78.4%). This makes it possible to more accurately refer patients to a pancreatic biopsy and reduce the frequency of its negative responses.

The final diagnosis of prostate cancer rightfully remains for transrectal multifocal biopsy of the PG under the control of TRUSE with a sensitivity of 86.1%, specificity – 98.3%, and accuracy – 99.4%.

Surunkali gastrit kasalligini davolash va profilaktik tadbirlarini tashkil etishda xalq tabobatining o`rni

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O`zbekiston Respublikasi. Respublika Xalq tabobati ilmiy - amaliy markazi
raxbari, tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi

Maxmudova Nilufar Maxamadjonovna

O`zbekiston Respublikasi. Respublika Xalq tabobati ilmiy - amaliy markazi ilmiy
tadqiqotlar bo`lim mudiri oliy toifali terapevt shifokor

Muammoning dolzarbligi. Xalq tabobati o`z nomi bilan halq uchun foyda
keltiruvchi va aholi foydalanishi qulay bo`lgan tibbiy yordamdir. JSST bergan
tarifga ko`ra "Xalq tabobati" uzoq tarixga ega bo`lgan, mahalliy xalqlar va turli
madaniyat vakillarining nazariyalari, e`tiqodlari asosida to`plangan bilim,
ko`nikma va amaliy tajribalarning umumiy xulosasi bo`lib, biz ularni tushuntira
olishimiz yoki tushuntira olmasligimizdan qat`iy nazar salomatlikni saqlashda,
shuningdek jismoniy va ruhiy buzilishlarda profilaktika, diagnostika va davolash
maqsadlarida ishlatiladi" (JSST, 2013y).

Bugungi kun, O`zbekistonda Xalq tabobati uslublarini zamonaviy tibbiyot
bilan uygunlashtirish izchil olib borilmoqda. Xukumat tomonidan Xalq tabobati
yo`nalishini nazorat etish va samarali xayotga tadbiriq etish chora-tadbirlari
O`zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018 yil 12 oktyabrdagi "O`zbekiston
Respublikasida xalq tabobati sohasini tartibga solish chora-tadbirlari to`g`risida"
№3968-sonli va 2020 yil 10 apreldagi "O`zbekiston Respublikasida xalq tabobatini
rivojlantirishga doir qo`shimcha chora-tadbirlar" №4668-sonli qarorlari asosida
olib borilmoqda. Xukumatning xalq tabobatiga ochib bergan yo`li O`zbekistondagi
ushbu yo`nalish sohasi mutaxassislari uchun keng imkon bo`lib, ushbu sohadagi
me`riy-huquqiy bazani shakllantirish hamda xalq tabobatining usullari va
yutuqlaridan samarali va xavfsiz foydalanish uchun shart-sharoit yaratishga zamin
yaratdi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Xalq tabobati aholi orasida keng tarqalgan kasalliklarni oldini
olish, davolash va taxshislash ishlarini keng miqyosda egallashni boshladi.
O`simliklardan tayyorlanadigan dorivor vositalar, o`zining tabbiyligi, inson

organizmi uchun kimyoviy vositalarga nisbatan zararsizligi bilan ajralib turadi. Kimyoviy vositalarning organizmga ijobiy yoki salbiy, nojuya ta`siri ko`pgina ilmiy tadqiqotlarda o`rganilgan bo`lib, tabiiy giyohlarning ijobiy yoki nojo`ya ta`siri kam o`rganilgan. **Tadqiqot uslublari.** Tadqiqot maqsadiga muvofiq klinik kuzatuv, surunkali gastrit bilan kasallangan bemorlarni klinik tashxislash, standart davo choralari bilan bir qatorda “Ventrap” biologik faol qo`shimcha bilan optimallashtirilgan davolash natijalarini solishtirma taxlili o`tkazildi. Tadqiqot statistik uslublari, guruxdagi natijalarning davo chora tadbirlari bilan korrelyatsion bog`liqligi va standart og`ish va xatoliklariga asoslangan xolda baholash bilan olib boriladi.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Tadqiqot 2022-2023 yillar davomida Toshkent Tibbiyot Akademiyasiga qarashli 2-klinik shifoxona qoshida 120 bemor tasodifiy tanlab olish uslubi bilan aniqlanadi. Klinik kuzatuvda tanlab olingan guruhlar shartli ravishda asosiy va nazorat guruxlariga ajratiladi. Ikkala gurux patsiyentlari uchun surunkali gastrit kasalligini davolash standart choralari qo`llaniladi. Birinchi guruxga standart davoga qo`shimcha xolda «Ventrap» biologik faol qo`shimcha belgilanadi. Klinik kuzatuv uch bosqichda olib boriladi. Birinchi bosqich anamnez yig`ish, kasallik tarixini, davomiyligi, asoratlari ya`ni patsiyentning barcha fiziologik-ruxiy-ijtimoiy xolati o`rganiladi. tadqiqotning ikkinchi bosqichida bevosita ikkita gurux orasida taqoslama davolash choralari o`tkaziladi va ma`lumot yig`ishgabag`ishlanadi. Uchinchi bosqich-yakuniy bosqich bo`lib, kasallikning turli xil yondoshuvlarda kechishi, asoratlari, ijobiy va salbiy oqibatlari taxlili o`tkaziladi.

Xulosa. rejalashtirilgan tadqiqot O`zbekiston xududida keng tarqalgan va katta yoshdagi aholini kasallanish darajasiga ta`sir ko`rsatuvchi surunkali gastrit kasalligini davolashda xalq tabobati uslublari qo`llagan xolda natijalarni solishtirma taqoslanishiga asoslanadi. Shu jumladan tadqiqotchi tomonidan surunkali gastritning birlamchi profilaktikasi, ya`ni o`tkir gastritni oldini olish, ikkilamchi profilaktikasi kasallikni surunkali ko`rinishga o`tishini to`xtatish va

imkon qadar uchlamchi profilaktika patsiyentning reabilitatsiyasi masalalarini xam qamrab oladi.

Tadqiqot natijalari kelajakda aholi o`rtasida keng tarqalgan boshqa noinfeksion yoki infeksiyon kasalliklarning davolash va oldini olishda xalq tabobati uslublaridan keng foydalanishga yo`l ochib beradi.

Клиническо-неврологические особенности микроцефалии различного генеза.

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Цель исследования: выявить клиничко-неврологические и параклинические особенности микроцефалии различного генеза. **Материал и методы:** исследовательская работа основана на проспективном и ретроспективном наблюдении 67 пациентов с диагнозом «МКБ-10 код Q02; Микроцефалия». Пациенты обратились в отделение медико-генетического консультирования Республиканского и Ферганского центра «Скрининг матери и ребенка» за период 2018-2022гг. Диагноз устанавливался на основании генеалогического, клиничко-неврологического и параклинических (МРТ головного мозга, ЭЭГ) методов исследования. По этиологическим факторам больные были распределены на две группы: в основную группу (23 больных из 9-и семей) составили больные дети с истинной наследственной семейной микроцефалией, вторую группу (44 больных) составляли больные с эмбриопатической и синдромологической микроцефалией. Возраст больных варьировал от 3 мес. до 14 лет. **Результаты:** родителей больных основной группы состояли в родственном браке во втором и третьем поколениях; при вторичной микроцефалии в анамнезе у больных отмечалась внутриутробная инфекция, тяжелая перинатальная и интранатальная асфиксия, имелись хромосомные aberrации. У больных группы сравнения клинические симптомы, особенно изменения со стороны черепно-мозговой иннервации, двигательной и когнитивной сферы были более выраженными, по сравнению с основной группой, по многим показателям выявлены значимые отличия. **Заключение:** на основании проведенного исследования выявлены различия клинического течения истинных и вторичных микроцефалий. Для верификации диагноза микроцефалии различного генеза, необходимо также

пройти кариотипирования и хромосомного матричного анализа, для
выявления спектр структурных изменений хромосом.

Observation in dynamics of children who have undergone intrauterine blood transfusion for hemolytic disease due to the Rh factor

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Relevance. The basis of the activity of medicine at the present stage is the reduction of not only perinatal mortality, but also, which is no less significant, perinatal morbidity. The leading place among the immunologically caused complications of pregnancy is occupied by hemolytic disease of the fetus (HDF) and the newborn, which affects both indicators.

Purpose of the study. Based on the results of a comprehensive clinical and laboratory examination, to study the structure of morbidity, the dynamics of hematological parameters, to assess the physical, neuropsychic development in children of the first year of life who underwent intrauterine intravascular blood transfusion (IBT) for fetal hemolytic disease by the Rh factor, to optimize tactics dispensary observation of children with hemolytic disease in an outpatient setting.

It has been established that in children who have undergone IBT, during the first year of life, there is a change in the morphological characteristics of erythrocytes in the form of a decrease in the total volume of erythrocytes, the average hemoglobin content in erythrocytes, which indicates the presence of erythrocytes of a donor (adult) in the population of circulating erythrocytes. Erythrocytes obtained from a donor as a result of IBT cannot ensure the complete utilization of oxygen from maternal blood, which contributes to the development of intrauterine hypoxia in the fetus. However, after birth, with the onset of spontaneous respiration, donor erythrocytes, which have a lower affinity for oxygen, improve the transfer of oxygen to tissues, preventing the development of severe tissue hypoxia in conditions of reduced hemoglobin content. An increased content of erythropoietin at birth was revealed, which is a compensatory-adaptive reaction of the body in response to long-term hypoxia associated with HDF, and the change in the morphological characteristics of erythrocytes persists throughout the first six months of life.

High levels of ferritin were found throughout the first year of life in children who received IBT, which indicates the absence of iron deficiency, in contrast to premature children without hemoconflict.

It is shown that during the first year of life there is a decrease and normalization of the level of erythropoietin, which indicates the adequacy of hematopoiesis by the end of the first year of life.

A method for predicting the development of severe anemia requiring additional blood transfusion in the first six months of life in children who received IBT has been proposed for practical public health.

Based on the forecast, an algorithm for monitoring children who received IBT in outpatient conditions in the first year of life is proposed.

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An approach for detection acute sinusitis and its features occurred on the effect of allergic rhinitis

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Introduction. Acute sinusitis occupies one of the first places among ENT pathologies in terms of negotiability. Over the past 10 years, acute sinusitis has become diagnosed twice as often, and the proportion of hospitalizations for diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses has increased annually, amounting to 28% -30% and from 0.5% to 14.7% in children. **Aim of the research.** To improve the complex treatment of acute sinusitis in children occurring against the background of allergic rhinitis, taking into account clinical, functional and morphological parameters. **Materials and methods.** The work included the results of a comprehensive examination and treatment of 96 patients with acute sinusitis. All patients were divided into two groups. The main group consisted of 60 children with OS, occurring against the background of allergic rhinitis. The comparison group included 30 children with only acute sinusitis. The control group consisted of 20 healthy children who had not previously experienced allergy symptoms in any manifestation, respiratory viral infections over the past 6 months, and had no bad habits. **Results and discussions.** In total, for the period 2016–2020, 12,083 children of the Republic of Azerbaijan aged 4–16 years were registered at the Andijan Regional Multidisciplinary Children`s Medical Center. Of the total number of patients with AR, 4954 (41%) had PAR and 7129 (59%). SAR. This contingent was formed from the number of 3867 patients who at the beginning of 2016 were on dispensary records at the Center and 96 who applied to the otorhinolaryngology department and the allergology room in 2016–2020. All patients underwent a comprehensive examination, including clinical-allergological, laboratory, radiological methods of research, and appropriate planned treatment for AR was carried out. If patients with AR had concomitant diseases, they were treated with the involvement of relevant related specialists. In most children of the

main group admitted to the hospital, the duration of the disease was from 11 to 30 days and amounted to 75.6%, and the number of patients in the second group during this period was 46.5%. In patients of the main group, the average rate of treatment from the moment the OS symptoms began to appear before contacting the Center was 23.11 ± 0.28 days, while in the comparison group it was 11.76 ± 0.33 ($P < 0.05$). The relatively later terms of treatment in children of the main group is due to the fact that in the early stages of the disease, AR or acute respiratory infections were treated and, given the small effect of the therapy, they applied to the Center. **Conclusions.** When analyzing the relationship between the duration of acute sinusitis and the form of AR, the following were revealed the frequency of visits of patients with various forms of acute sinusitis in children to some extent depends on the season.

The dynamics of growth in the frequency of Charcot foot in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2012 - 2021 years

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Background. Every year, DM 2 sucks about 3 million lives, and about 1 million amputations occurs annually, 90% of the sick suffer from DM 2. Recently, the group of chronic complications of DM 2 has increasingly include natological change in bone tissue [1, 2].

Keywords: Charcot foot, observation period, diabetes mellitus

Aim -to study the frequency of Charcot foot in the Republic Uzbeistan during 2012-2021 years

Material and Methods.Reports of regional endocrinological dispensaries of 13 regions of the country and the Republic of Karakalpakstan for the studied period were used. In total, in 2012, 2648 patients with a foot Charcot were registered.

All patients during the observation period were subjected to general clinical, biochemical (control of glycemia, HbA1C, et al), instrumental (ECG, X -ray of the foot, examination of the oculist other) research methods

Results. During the period 2012-2021, the frequency of Charcot foot in country increased by 4.3 times. So, if in 2012 2648 patients with a foot of Charcot consisted in the country, then in 2021 their number reached 11560.Among the leading regions was the Ferghana region: in 2012, 1430 patients were registered there, and in 2021 already 2145. It should be noted that in 2012 year, 116,517 patients with DM 2 were registered in the Republic Uzbekistan, and in 2021 year- 291 567 patients. Such an increase in the number of patients with a foot of Charcot foot can be explained both by an increase in the splash of DM 2 and an improvement in the detection of its complications

Conlusion During the period 2012-2021, the frequency of Charcot foot in the Republic of Uzbeistan increased by 4.3 times. Such an increase in the number of

patients with a foot of Charcot foot can be explained both by an increase in the splash of DM 2 and an improvement in the detection of its complications

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Clinical and immunological characteristics of bronchial asthma in children against the background of atypical pathogens

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Keywords: Chlamydophila pneumonia, Mycoplasma pneumonia, children, bronchial asthma

Relevance: Respiratory infections associated with atypical pathogens remain in the focus of attention of researchers in many countries. [1.2] Despite the successes achieved in the study of respiratory chlamydia (CHI) and mycoplasma infection (MI) caused by Chlamydophila pneumoniae (C. pneumoniae) and Mycoplasma pneumoniae (M. pneumoniae), problems associated with diagnosis and treatment persist. Mycoplasma pneumonia is an independent genus of microorganisms, having a small size (150-200 nm) and containing RNA and DNA. The pathogen is able to multiply on a cell-free medium and secrete a toxin (b-hemolysin). Mycoplasmas occupy an intermediate position by viruses, bacteria and protozoa. They can persist for years in a lipophilic ally dried state at a temperature of - 70 ° C. [2] Chlamydia, as is known, are obligate intracellular pathogens. In their structure, they are close to classical bacteria, but unlike the latter, they do not possess the metabolic mechanisms necessary for independent reproduction. Recently, a high frequency of respiratory chlamydia has been noted in patients with bronchial asthma (BA) (from 24 to 52%), especially with its severe course. Having examined 82 children from 2 to 16 years old with AD and 27 children of the control group using a serological method to detect AT to C. pneumoniae and M. pneumoniae and PCR for the diagnosis of respiratory viruses, the authors confirmed the high frequency of viral infection, especially entero- or rhinovirus, with exacerbation of AD. [2.3]

The aim of our study was to study the prevalence and role of C. Pneumoniae and M. pneumoniae infections in children with AD.

Materials and methods of research: Of the 64 examined children and adolescents from 3 to 18 years old (85% of them schoolchildren) with various chronic and

recurrent bronchitis, 54 patients were diagnosed with asthma of varying severity. The control group included 38 children of comparable age and who had no history, as well as at the time of examination of respiratory complaints and signs of respiratory tract damage. Diagnosis of C. Pneumoniae, M. pneumoniae infections was carried out on the basis of determination of AT classes IgG, IgA, IgM to C. Pneumoniae and M. pneumoniae using immunofluorescence analysis (MIF) and the use of SeroFIA test systems (Savyon, Israel).

Results and their discussion: Respiratory CHI and MI caused by C. Pneumoniae, M. pneumoniae was diagnosed in 23 (35%) of 64 examined patients with recurrent and chronic bronchitis. At the same time, IgG class AT was most common, found in 32.9% of patients. In the control group, AT to C. pneumoniae of the IgG class were detected in almost the same number of adolescents (31.4%), which indicates a sufficient prevalence of CHI in this age group. However, patients with bronchopulmonary pathology had higher IgG AT titers and more frequent detection of AT class IdA in 18.3% and 2.9%, respectively, reinfection is chronic infection. The general characteristics of patients with varying degrees of BA severity were comparable in age. Every 3rd child had signs of exacerbation of BA at admission, both in the general group and with varying degrees of severity.

Conclusion: When comparing the clinical manifestations of AD in children with laboratory signs of C. pneumoniae infection and without them, we found a tendency to increase the frequency of infection with CHI as the severity of AD increases. Often such results are associated with the direct influence of CHI and MI on the severity of AD. However, we should not forget that severe patients are more often hospitalized and they have more opportunities to infect CHI in a hospital setting. An indication for the appointment of treatment for C. pneumoniae infection is acute infection, reinfection or exacerbation of chronic infection. It is impractical to prescribe treatment for isolated detection of IgG AT in low titers, since this is associated with a "trace" reaction after an infection. However, with an increase in IgG AT titers or their initially high values, which may be due to

reinfection or chronic infection, patients should be treated. For the treatment of respiratory chlamydia and mycoplasmosis, only those groups of antibiotics are used that are able to penetrate into cells and act on intracellular pathogens: macrolides, tetracyclines, less often fluoroquinolones and rifampicin. Since when choosing an antibiotic for the treatment of a child, it is necessary to take into account not only the effectiveness, but also maximum safety.

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Состояние андроген чувствительных рецепторов при иммуногистохимическом анализе больных с акне.

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Актуальность. Роль андрогенов и андроген чувствительных рецепторов (АР) в патофизиологии вульгарных угрей представляется сложным явлением. Ранее предполагалось, что пероральное введение изотретиноина, препарата выбора при тяжелых формах акне, оказывает свое действие через АР, что весьма спорно. Цель состоит в том, чтобы изучить ответ рецептора андрогена (АР) в коже пациентов с вульгарными угрями при пероральном введении изотретиноина.

Материалы и методы исследования. Биопсия кожи была получена у нелеченых пациентов с тяжелыми случаями вульгарных угрей. Из них в исследование были включены 20 пациентов с гистологически подтвержденным диагнозом. Их лечили пероральным изотретиноином в дозе 0,5 мг/кг/день в течение 12 недель, после чего у них повторили биопсию кожи. Иммуноокрашивание на рецептор андрогена проводили с использованием мышинных моноклональных антител. Индекс рецепторов андрогенов (индекс AR) рассчитывали для пациентов с акне до и после лечения пероральным изотретиноином. Статистический анализ был проведен с использованием парного t-критерия.

Результаты исследования. Показатели АР в коже нелеченных больных акне были выше у женщин 30 лет ($26,62 \pm 20,74$) по сравнению с женщинами 42 лет ($7,5 \pm 10,61$). Показатели АР после 12 недель перорального лечения изотретиноином показали снижение как у женщин 30 и 43 лет ($20,55 \pm 16$ и $4,71 \pm 6,75$ соответственно). Однако снижение индекса АР после лечения было статистически значимым только у женщин 30 лет. Положительные случаи оценивались по шкале Н с медианой = 117 и диапазоном 3–285, а также по шкале Оллреда с медианой = 7 и диапазоном 3–8. Экспрессия АР была

выше у женщин пожилого возраста, и была значительная положительная корреляция между степенью выраженности АР (% АР, интенсивность АР и Н-показатель) и возрастом ($p=0,050,0,007, 0,033$ соответственно).

Выводы. Определение статуса АР может быть полезным при планировании методики лечения тяжелых случаев акне. Наше исследование также указывает на эффективность перорального приема изотретиноина у пациентов с акне благодаря его взаимодействию с рецептором андрогена.

Дилятацион кардиомиопатияларда морфологик ўзгаришлар

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Долзарблиги. Охирги йилларда Жахон Соғлиқни Сақлаш Ташкилоти маълумотлари бўйича ва эпителиологик тадқиқотлар кўрсатишича юрак-томир тизими касалликлари иқтисодий ривожланган давлатларда доминантлигича қолмоқда.

Тадқиқот мақсади. Дилятацион кардиомиопатияларда ўзига хос макро ва микроскопик ўзгаришларни аниқлаш.

Тадқиқот материали ва услублари. Материал сифатида Республика Патологик анатомия марказида 23 та аутопсия қилинган Дилятацион кардиомиопатия (ДКМП) ҳолатлари олинди. Аутопсия баённомаси ва касаллик тарихи таҳлил қилинди. Аутопсия материали қайта кўтарилиб, юракдан олинган бўлакчалардан қайтадан гистологик препаратлар тайёрланиб ўрганилди. Парафинли ғишчалардан қалинлиги 5-6 мкмли гистологик кесмалар олинди ва гематоксилин-эозинда, бириктирувчи тўқима толаларини аниқлаш учун ван-Гизон усусида бўялди.

Тадқиқот натижалари ва уларнинг муҳокамаси. Морфологик жиҳатдан ДКМП эксцентрик гипертрофия ва юрак бўшлиқларининг дилятацияси билан намоён бўлади. Одатда юракнинг чап қисми зарарланганлиги аниқланди, фақат айрим ҳолларда, яъни 1,7% да ўнг қоринча ўзгарганлиги кузатилди. Гистологик жиҳатдан тарқоқ ҳолда кардиомиоцитларга тарқалувчи интерстициал склероз борлиги, кардиомиоцитларнинг гидропик дистрофияси аниқланди. 50% ҳолларда кардиомиоцитларнинг атрофияси кузатилди.

ДКМП ҳолатларида юрак тўқимасини гистологик текшириш натижалари шуни кўрсатдики, миокард ва эндокарда қуйидагича турдаги патоморфологик ўзгаришлар мавжудлиги аниқланди. Асосий морфологик ўзгаришлар оралик тўқимадалиги, яъни бириктирувчи тўқиманинг ҳаддан ташқари кўп миқдорда ўсганлиги, айрим жойларида миксаматоз, липоматоз

ривожланганлиги кузатилди. Қон томирлари деворида ҳам худди шунга ўхшаш морфологик ўзгаришлар, яъни перичитларнинг пролиферацияланишидан склероз ривожланганлиги, базал мембранаси ва эластик толалари миксаматозга учраганлиги аниқланди. Оралиқ бириктирувчи тўқимадаги ўзгаришларни ўрганиб таҳлил қиладиган бўлсак, авваламбор кўзга ташланадиган ўзгаришлардан оралиқ модданинг шишга ва миксаматозга учраганлиги кўзга ташланади. Бунга қўшимча оралиқ тўқимада лимфоид ҳужайралар пайдо бўлганлиги, макрофагларнинг кўпайганлиги, яъни аутоиммун жараёнга хос морфологик ўзгаришлар ривожланганлиги кузатилади. Оралиқ бириктирувчи тўқима ҳужайралари таркибида ҳар хил кўринишдаги метаплазия ва дисплазия каби ўзгаришлар ривожланганлиги аниқланади. Энг аҳамиятлиси шундан иборатки, бириктирувчи тўқима гистиобласт ва гистиоцитларининг ёғ ҳужайраларига айланиши аниқланади. Бунда оралиқ бириктирувчи тўқима кучли шишга учраганлиги, **хам** толалари, ҳам ҳужайралари бетартиб жойлашганлиги, айрим гистиобласт ҳужайралар цитоплазмаси кенгайиб, ёғ пайдо бўлиш ҳисобига вакуоллашгани кузатилади. Натижада, миокард оралиқ; туцимасида ёғ туцимаси **усиб** купайиши ва унинг атрофида лимфоид ҳужайралар инфильтрацияси пайдо булиши кузатилади.

Ушбу патоморфологик ўзгаришлар натижасида миокард оралиқ тўқимасида аутоиммун жараёнга хос лимфоид инфильтрация ўчоқлари ҳамда липоматоз ўчоқлари пайдо бўлганлиги аниқланади. Оралиқ тўқимада ривожланган патоморфологик ўзгаришлар таъсирида албатта мушак толалари, яъни кардиомиоцитларда **хам** ўзига хос морфологик ўзгаришлар ривожланганлиги аниқланади. ДКМПга хос дастлабки ўзгаришлардан асосийси мушак толаларининг дилатацияланиб чўзилиши, яъни мушак толаларининг ингичка тортиши, ундаги кардиомиоцитларнинг кендаланг тарғил чизикларининг сийраклашиши, парчаланиб гомогенлашиши,

ядроларининг бетартиб жойланиши ва атрофдаги ўзгаришлар таъсирида деформацияга ва дистрофияга учраши кузатилади.

Хулоса. ДКМПда гистологик жиҳатдан миокард ва эндокардда оралик туқима бириктирувчи туқиманинг ҳаддан ташқари кўп миқдорда ўсганлиги, айрим жойларида миксаматоз, липоматоз ривожланганлиги кузатилди. Бириктирувчи туқима гистиобласт ва гистиоцитларининг ёғ ҳужайраларига айланиши, яъни айрим гистиобласт ҳужайралар цитоплазмаси кенгайиб, ёғ пайдо бўлиш ҳисобига вакуоллашгани кузатилади, натижада, миокард оралик туқимасида ёғ туқимаси ўсиб кўпайиши ва унинг атрофида лимфоид ҳужайралар инфильтрацияси пайдо бўлиши аниқланди. Дастлабки ўзгаришлардан асосийси мушак толаларининг дилатацияланиб чўзилиши, яъни мушак толаларининг ингичка тортиши, ундаги кардиомиоцитларнинг кендаланг тарғил чизиқларининг сийраклашиши, парчаланиб гомогенлашиши, ядроларининг бетартиб жойланиши ва атрофдаги ўзгаришлар таъсирида деформацияга ва дистрофияга учраши кузатилди.

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Ишемик инсултни ўткир даврини реабилитация қилишда акупунктуранинг аҳамияти.

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Тиббиёт ходимларининг касбий малакасини ривожлантириш маркази

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Аннотация. Ҳозирги кунда инсулт касаллиги ногиронликни ва меҳнатга лаёқатсизликни асосий сабаби бўлиб қолмоқда, бу эса давлат бюджетига ва беморлар иқтисодига сезиларли таъсир кўрсатади. Шунинг учун ҳам инсултни реабилитация қилишда, реабилитацияни эрта бошлаш, самаралироқ ва нисбатан камроқ маблағ сарфланадиган усуллари ишлаб чиқиш мақсадга мувофиқ ҳисобланади. Бунинг учун дунё тиббиётида етакчи ўринда бораётган мамлакатларда инсултни реабилитация қилишда дастлабки босқичларида кинезотерапия, даволовчи гимнастика, акупунктура (асосан Хитой, Кореяда) ва бошқалардан фойдаланмоқдалар. Биз ишемик инсултни ўткир даврини эрта реабилитация қилишда, Хитой анъанавий тиббиётини асосий даволаш усуллари билан акупунктурани таъсирини кўриб чиқамиз.

Кириш. Ҳозирги кунда инсулт касаллиги кенг тарқалаётган ва давлат бюджетига катта зарар келтираётган касаллик ҳисобланади. Статистик маълумотларга таянадиган бўлсак: инсулт касаллигида ўлим кўрсаткичи 40-50% ни ташкил этади, омон қолганларнинг 70-75% ида турли даражадаги ногиронлик ривожланади. Миллий инсулт реестри маълумотларига кўра инсултга чалинган беморларни 75% и бутунлай ишлаш ва касбий маҳоратини йўқотади. Уларни 31% и ўзларига ғамхўрлик қилиш учун ташқаридан ёрдамга муҳтож. Омон қолганларнинг 8% и аввалги ишларига тўлиқ қайта оладилар. Бу статистикадан кўриниб турибдики, инсулт асоратлари билан самарали курашиш кераклигини кўрсатади. Инсулт

касаллигини асоратларини олдини олишда ва камайтиришни асосий усулларида бири бу реабилитацияни эртароқ бошлашдир. Албатта бу даврда реабилитация қилишни ўзига хос қийинчиликлари ва асоратлари мавжуд, яъни артериал қон босимнинг ностабил бўлиши, беморнинг руҳияти носоғлом бўлиши ва ҳаказо. Шунинг учун ҳам инсультни эрта реабилитация қилишда хавфсиз ва самарали усуллари қўллаш керак. Бундай хавфсиз ва самарали усулларида бири бу акупунктура ҳисобланади. Шарқий Осиё давлатларида инсульт билан боғлиқ касалликларни даволашда акупунктура муҳим роль ўйнайди. Ғарб мамлакатлари ва кўплаб ривожланган мамлакатларидаги кўплаб шифокорлар беморлардаги турли хилдаги неврологик касалликларни даволашда акупунктура муқобил терапия сифатида киритишни бошладилар, чунки бу инсультни реабилитациясида муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Инсультни реабилитация қилишда ҳам жисмоний, ҳам психологик муаммоларни бартараф этишда меридиан нуқталари акупунктурасини афзалликларини тушунтирувчи тадқиқотлар мавжуд. Бу тезис ишемик инсультни реабилитация қилишда акупунктурани аҳамиятини таҳлил қилиш ҳақида ёзилган.

Асосий қисм. Ишемик инсультда марказий нерв тизимида зарарланган 2 та зона пайдо бўлади: улардан биринчисидан нейронларни ўлими дарҳол содир бўлади (ишемик ядро зонаси), иккинчисидан эса дастлабки зарар ва дисфункцияга қарамай (пенумбра зонаси ёки ишемик пенумбра), тўқималарни тузилиши зарар кўрмайди. Ишемик инсультни ўткир давридаги терапиянинг асосий мақсади, айнан пенумбра зонаси, унда юзага келадиган патологик жараёнларни орқага қайтаришга эришишдир. Акупунктура қўлланилганда бир қатор биомолекуляр ва биофизик реакциялар содир бўлади ва улар 4 та асосий механизмга бирлаштиради, яъни нина тешилган жойда яллиғланиш, ҳужайралараро ўтказувчанлик ошиши, тери-сомато-висцерал ўтказувчанликни ошиши, нерв-мушак ўтказувчанлигини ошиши кабилар. Ишемик инсультни ўткир даврида ижобий таъсирга эришишга

ёрдам берадиган акупунктурани таъсир механизмларининг асосий таркибий қисмларини қуйидагича ифодалаш мумкин. 1) Марказий нерв тизимида шикастланган ишемик ядро ва пенумбра зонасида нейрогенез ва хужайра пролиферациясини рағбатлантиради (латерал қоринчаларнинг субвентрикуляр зонасида ва гиппокампусдаги тишли гийрус ва ишемик тармоқларда). 2) Ишемик соҳада мия қон оқимини тартибга солиш (вазоактив модуляция ва тишли гийрус ва латерал қоринчаларда янги қон томирларини шаклланиши). 3) Апаптозни ўзига хос ва ўзига хос бўлмаган йўллари модуляция қилиш орқали ишемик зарарни камайтиради (ишемик зонадаги антиапаптоз). 4) Нейромедиатор алмашинувни нормаллаштириш, яллиғланиш ва оксидловчи стресс медиаторларини тартибга солиди (нейрохимёвий тартибга солиш): а) нейромедиатор ва рецепторлар, б) антиоксидант ферментлар, в) яллиғланиш медиаторлари, г) нейротроп омиллар, д) анаэроб моддалар алмашинуви. 5) Ишемик инсультдан кейин бузилган гиппокампуснинг бир қатор соҳаларида узок муддатли потенцияни ва хотирани оширади. 6) Бузилмаган нейронларнинг функционал тикланиши (нейропластикликни рағбатлантириш), инсультдан кейин йўқолган функцияси учун компенсацияни келтириб чиқаради. 7) Гематоэнцефалитик тўсиқни ўтказувчанлигини оширади.

Акупунктура ва нейрогенез. Акупунктура 2 хил механизм орқали ишемик инсультда марказий нерв тизими хужайраларини рағбатлантиради: биринчидан бу нейрогенез нейроген соҳа (латерал қоринчанинг субвентрикуляр зонаси ва гиппокампуснинг тишли гийруси) билан чегараланади, иккинчидан акупунктура ишемик тўқималарда, шунингдек, жарохатга қўшни бўлган бир қанча жойларда хужайра кўпайишини оширади. Акупунктурани неврологик касалликларда функционал бузилишда терапевтик таъсири акупунктура маълум нуқталарда огохлантирувчи таъсири билан изоҳланади, бу периферик нервларни фаоллаштириши ва миёда турли хил нейротрофик омилларни ишлаб чиқарилишини стимуллайтиди, бу эса ўз

навбатида нейрогенезни рағбатлантирадиган автокрин ёки паракринни ишлаб чиқарилиши ортади. Сичконлар миясида сунъий ишемия чақирилганда ўтказилган тадқиқотлар шуни кўрсатдики, перфузиядан 3 соат ўтгач амалга оширилган акупунктура аралашуви натижасида маҳаллий мия ишемияси ва реперфузия билан боғлиқ бўлган ультраструктурал нейрон шикастланишидан химоя таъсирига эга эканлиги исботланган.

Акупунктура ва цереброваскуляр захира. Цереброваскуляр захира бу артериал стеноз туфайли келиб чиққан перфузияни пасайишига жавобан мияда қон оқимини етарли даражада таъминлаш учун мия томирларининг вазодилатация қилишидир. Хитойлик тадқиқотчиларни фикрига кўра бош соҳасида қилинган акупунктура цереброваскуляр захирани ошириши, ишемик инсультни ривожланишини, прогрессиясини ва такрорланишини олдини олишда муҳим ҳисобланади.

Акупунктура ва ёшга боғлиқ қон томир ўзгаришлари. Ўткир цереброваскуляр ва юрак қон томир касалликларини патогенезида артериал қаттиқлик ва эндотелиал дисфункцияси муҳим роль ўйнайди. Ушбу гипотеза асосида Гонгкунгда Хитойлик олимлар Zu Sanli ST-36, Tai Chun LR-3 нуқталаридаги электроакупунктура оксидловчи стрессни пасайиши ва азот оксидини ошириш орқали гипертензиядаги эндотелиал функцияга таъсир кўрсатишини аниқладилар.

Ишемик инсультда асосий акупунктур нуқталарнинг патофизиологик механизмларга таъсири. Асосий акупунктур нуқталарнинг ишемик инсультдаги патофизиологик механизмларга таъсирини ўрганиш учун кўплаб тадқиқотлар ўтказилган. Hegu LI-4 нуқтасига нина киритиш миянинг префронтал кортексининг ишлашига сезиларли фаоллаштирувчи таъсир кўрсатади. Мия ишемияси бўлган каламушларда Baihui GV-20 нуқтасига лазерли акупунктура қилиш малондиалдегид миқдорини пасайтириш, глутатион пероксидаза фаоллигини ошириш орқали миядаги ишемия ҳажмини камайтиради. PC-6, GV-20, ST-36, ST-37 нуқталаридаги

акупунктура гомологик оқсил ва каспаза-12 m RNK нинг камайтириши ва хужайра апаптозини тормозлаш орқали инфаркт ҳажмини камайтиради. GV-20 ва GV-14 нуқтасида акупунктура иммунорегулятив таъсир қилиб, сарум интерлейкинлари IL-6 ва IL-8 даражасини, периферик қонда яллиғланишга қарши цитокин ўсимта некроз омили ва яллиғланишга қарши цитокин IL -10 ўртасидаги мувозанатни тартибга солиш орқали яллиғланиш реакциясини осонлаштириш туфайли неврологик етишмовчиликни ва мия инфаркти ҳажмини камайтириши мумкин. LI-11,ST-36 нуқталарида акупунктура миянинг мотор функцияси билан боғлиқ соҳаларни нейронал фаоллигини оширади. Шунингдек, бу нуқталарда ишемик инсультни 3-кунли таъсир қилиш GFAP нестин мусбат реактивининг қўпайиши, астроцитлар, реактив астроцитлардан BDNF секрецияси, PTEN йўли орқали апаптозни тормозлаш йўли билан нейропротексияни келтириб чиқаради, бу эса неврологик етишмовчилик ва мия инфаркти ҳажмини пасайишига олиб келади. PC-6 нуқтадаги акупунктура астроцитларни фаоллашувини тартибга солади. GV-24 ва GV-20 нуқталаридаги акупунктура сигнализация йўллари тартибга солиш орқали хужайра апаптозини тормозлайди.

Хулоса.

Юқоридагилардан хулоса қилиб шуни айтиш мумкинки, ишемик инсультни ўткир даврида акупунктура қилиш ишемик инфарктни ҳажмини камайтиради, ишемик пенумбра соҳадаги чалажон нейронларни тикланишига ижобий таъсир қилади ва шунинг натижасида бузилган функцияларни тикланишига ижобий таъсир кўрсатади. Шундай қилиб ишемик инсультни ўткир даврини эрта реабилитация қилишда акупунктура ҳам самарали, ҳам хавфсиз ва кам маблағ талаб қиладиган усул ҳисобланади.

**Тиббиёт ходимларида covid-19 кечишининг айрим клиник
эпидемиологик жихатлари**

**Некоторые клинико-эпидемиологические аспекты течения covid-19 у
медицинских работников**

Some clinical and epidemiological aspects of covid-19 in medical professionals

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1 Тиббиёт ходимларининг касбий малакасини ривожлантириш маркази,

2 Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт институти,

3 Республика ихтисослаштирилган эпидемиология, микробиология, юқумли
ва паразитар касалликлар илмий-амалий тиббиёт маркази,

4 Андижон давлат тиббиёт институти

Интенсивность профессионального заражения COVID-19 в медицинских учреждениях зависит от таких факторов, как пропорциональность возможностей ЛПУ и числа пациентов, подготовленность, осведомленность и бдительность населения и медицинских работников, карантин, социальная защита и масочный режим. Строгое выполнение от обращения до госпитализации пациентов на всех этапах установленных режимов, обеспечение готовности, повышение бдительности населения и персонала, дистанционное предоставление медицинских услуг и консультаций, соблюдение социальной дистанции, использование средств индивидуальной защиты, а также внедрение надлежащего инфекционного контроля в ЛПУ, в частности, в стационарах для пациентов с COVID-19, значительно снизит распространение заболевания среди медицинских работников. Установлено, что 77,6% заболевшие медицинские работники были инфицированы COVID-19 в связи с профессиональной деятельностью.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19, медицинские работники, госпитальная инфекция, клинико-эпидемиологические особенности.

The intensity of occupational infection with COVID-19 in medical facilities depends on factors such as the matching of the capacity of medical facilities and the number of patients, preparedness, awareness and vigilance of the population and health workers, quarantine, social protection and mask regime. Strict meeting to requirements from admission to hospitalization of patients, ensuring preparedness, increasing the vigilance of the population and personnel, remote provision of medical services and consultations, adherence to social distance, the use of personal protective equipment, as well as the introduction of proper infection control in health care facilities, in particular, in hospitals for patients with

COVID-19 will significantly reduce the spread of the disease among healthcare workers. It was found that 77.6% of sick medical workers were infected with COVID-19 during implementation their professional activities.

Key words: COVID-19, healthcare workers, hospital infection, clinical and epidemiological features.

Сўнги эпидемиологик тадқиқотлар COVID-19 инфекциясида пациентларни интенсив терапия бўлимларига госпитализация қилиш заруриятининг юқори частотада эканлигини кўрсатмоқда [1,7]. Ўз хизмат бурчларига кўра тиббиёт ходимлари SARS-CoV-2 юқишига нисбатан хавф гуруҳига мансуб. Бу ҳолат кўпгина омиллар билан белгиланади: соғлиғига доир муаммоси мавжуд шахслар, жумладан коронавирусли инфекцияга чалинганлар, аввало (COVID-19 касаллиги ташхис этилгунига қадар ҳам, ташхис қўйилганидан кейин ҳам) тиббиёт ходимларига мурожаат этишади, уларнинг иш жойларибевосита COVID-19 пациентлари тўпланган эпидемик ўчоқда жойлашган, тиббиёт ходимларига нисбатан чеклов тадбирлари тадбиқ этилмайди, хизмат кўрсатиш (фаолият юритиш) жадаллигининг ўсиши узок муддат иш жойида – эпидемик ўчоқда бўлишларини ва сурункали чарчоқ, стресс бошдан кечирилишини тақазо этади [2]. Буларнинг барчаси, ҳаттоки шахсий ҳимоя воситаларидан фойдаланилганида ҳам, тиббиёт ходимларига инфекция юқиш эҳтимоллигини оширади [7]. COVID-19 пациентларига мўлжалланган госпиталларда фаолият юритувчи тиббиёт ходимлари касалланиши борасидаги дастлабки ва салмоқли маълумотлар Италияда эълон қилинди – 2020 йилнинг февраль-апрель ойлари мобайнида 12680 нафардан кўпроқ тиббиёт ходимида мазкур инфекция қайд этилиб, қарийб 100 нафар врач ва 26 нафар ҳамширада ўлим ҳолати кузатилди. Буюк Британияда 2020 йил 25 март 13 май оралиғидаги давр мобайнида 147 нафар тиббиёт ходимларида ўлим ҳолати қайд этилган бўлиб, шулардан врачлар 19,1%, ҳамширалар 42,9% ва бошқа ёрдамчи тиббиёт ходимлари 38,0% ни ташкил этишган [3,5]. Ҳар 1000 нафар врачга умумий ўлим кўрсаткичи 0,15 ни, 1000 нафар ҳамширага 0,17 ни ва 1000 нафар ёрдамчи тиббиёт ходимларига 0,10 ни ташкил этди [8]. Россиянинг Кемерово вилоятида 2020 йил 9 апрелдан 31 августга қадар давр мобайнида тиббиёт муассасаларининг 420 нафар ишловчиси касалланишган бўлиб, шулардан 353 нафар киши – бевосита тиббиёт ходимларидир (врачлар, ўрта ва кичик тиббиёт ходимлари) [6]. Тиббиёт жамоатчилиги томонидан, иш фаолияти жараёнида тиббиёт ходимларининг SARS-CoV-2 ни юқтириш муаммоси, нафақат уларнинг касалланиши ҳолатидангина иборат хусусий ҳодиса эмаслиги таъкидланади.

Биринчидан, тиббиёт ходимлари ҳамкасблари ва ўз оила аъзолари учун инфекция манбаи бўлиб хизмат қилишлари мумкин. Иккинчидан, айти пандемия авжига чиққан паллада тиббиёт ходимларининг касалланиши, ходимлар тақчиллигига олиб келади. Зеро, Rosario Barranco таъкидлаганидек, “тиббиёт ходимлари ҳозир жаҳонда энг муҳим ресурс ҳисобланади” [2]. Шу боисдан, тиббиёт ходимларига SARS-CoV-2 юқишини ва COVID-19 билан касалланиш ҳолатларини клиник-эпидемиологик жиҳатдан тадқиқ этиш муҳим илмий-амалий аҳамиятга моликдир. Материаллар ва усуллар 2020 йил 20 мартдан 2020 йил 31 декабрга қадар Самарқанд вилоят юқумли касалликлар шифохонаси ва вилоят Соғлиқни сақлаш Бош бошқармаси буйруғи билан коронавирус инфекцияси пациентлари учун қайта мослаштирилган муассасаларга COVID-19 инфекцияси ташхис этилибгоспитализация қилинган 125 нафар тиббиёт ходимларининг тиббий ҳужжатлари - даволовчи шифокорлар томонидан расмийлаштирилган бирламчи тиббий ҳужжатлар “Беморнинг амбулатор тиббий картаси” (025-х/ш), “Стационар беморининг тиббий картаси” (003-х/ш) ҳамда “Касалхонадан чиқарилган беморнинг чиқарув статистик картаси” таҳлил этилди. Тиббиёт ходимлари гуруҳига киритиш учун врач, тиббиёт ҳамшираси, кичик тиббиёт ходими касб-корига эга эканлиги, даволаш-профилактика муассасасида фаолият юритиши ва касалланиш олдиан пациентлар билан мулоқот натижасида юқтирганлик эҳтимоли мавжуд ҳолатлар мезон сифатида қабул қилинди. COVID-19 ташхиси ва унинг клиник кўринишлари пациентлар томонидан билдирилган шикоятлар, эпидемиологик анамнез, хос лаборатория таҳлиллари, объектив маълумотлар ва қўшимча текширув (функционал, ускунали, лаборатория усуллари) натижалари асосида қўйилган. Ташхис Жаҳон соғлиқни сақлаш ташкилотининг (ЖССТ) 2020 йил январь ойида янгиланган КХТ-10 «Фавкулудда ҳолатларда қўлланиладиган кодлар» бўлимига мувофиқ расмийлаштирилган бўлиб, тадқиқотга киритилган барча пациентлар COVID-19 U07.1 махсус код рубрикасига (сарлавҳасига) мансуб, яъни SARS-CoV-2 га нисбатан лаборатория текширувида мусбат натижага эга. COVID-19 ташхиси полимераза занжир реакцияси усулида SARS-CoV-2 РНК сини детекция қилишорқали тасдиқланди. Пациентларда COVID-19 кечишининг оғирлик даражаси ЖССТ йўриқномалари, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Соғлиқни сақлаш вазирлигининг “COVID-19 коронавирусли инфекция билан касалланган беморларни бошқариш бўйича тавсиянома” лари асосида баҳоланди. COVID-19 пациентларида зотилжамни ташхислаш, ўпканинг зарарланиш даражасини ва динамикасини баҳолаш ўртача оғир, оғир ва ўта

оғир ҳолатларда касаллик бошланганидан 6-7 кун ўтгач нур ташхисот усуллари – рентгенография, ультратовуш текшируви, компьютер томографиясини (КТ) қўллаб амалга оширилди. Бу ҳолатда кўкрак қафаси аъзоларининг компьютер томографияси (амбулатория ва стационар шароитида), клиник ва лаборатория маълумотларини ҳисобга олган ҳолда, асосий усул сифатида қабул қилинди. Натижалар ва муҳокамаси Самарқанд вилоятида 2020 йил 20 мартдан 2020 йил 31 декабрга қадар COVID-19 ҳолати 2506 нафар шахсларда, жумладан 125 нафар тиббиёт ходимларида (4,9%) қайд этилган. Самарқанд вилоятида COVID-19 билан касалланган тиббиёт ходимларининг маъмурий ҳудудлар бўйича тақсимланиши, 2020 й., %. Вилоят аҳолиси ўртасида COVID-19 ҳолатларининг қайд этилиши апрель ойида бошланган бўлиб, айнан мазкур ойда (47 нафар) касалланганлар орасида тиббиёт ходимларининг ҳиссаси (17 нафар) энг юқори кўрсаткич – 36,1% ни ташкил этган ва бошқа ойларга қараганда ишонарли тафовутга эга (Бунинг боиси, бу пайтга келиб COVID-19 га гумон этилаётган пациентларнинг муружаат этишидан тортиб, ташхислаш ва госпитализация қилунгунига (ёки уйда ажратилгунига) қадар барча босқичларнинг қатъий белгиланган тартиблари ишлаб чиқилиб, шу асосда амалга оширила бошланганлиги, тиббиёт муассасаларининг шайлиги такомиллашганлиги, аҳоли ва ходимларда эҳтиёткорлик ошганлиги, масофавий алоқа воситалари орқали тиббий хизматлар ва маслаҳатлар йўлга қўйилганлиги, ижтимоий масофани сақлаш, шахсий ҳимоя воситаларидан фойдаланиш кабиларга тўғри риоя этилганлиги билан изоҳланади. Шу билан бирга бу ҳолат, бу пайтга келиб ДПМ ларда, жумладан COVID-19 пациентларига мўлжалланган стационарларда тўғри йўлга қўйилган инфекцион назорат тадбирлари ҳамда тиббиёт ходимлари томонидан шахсий ҳимоя воситаларидан фойдаланилиши сезиларли самарали таъсирга эга эканлигини кўрсатади. Пациентларнинг жинс таркибида эркаклар (48,8%) ва аёлларнинг (51,2%) ҳиссаси жиддий тафовутга эга эмас. Пациентларнинг 91,2 фоизини 30 ёшдан юқори ёшдаги шахслар ташкил этади. Ёш таркибида 50-59 ёш гуруҳидаги (28,0%) ва 60 ёшдан юқори ёш гуруҳидаги (23,2%) шахслар устувор мавқега эга, 2020, %. Касб-кор таркибига кўра пациентлар таҳлили шуни кўрсатадики, врачларнинг ҳиссаси 29,6% дан иборат. Беморларнинг 43,2 фоизини ўрта тиббиёт ходимлари, 16,0 фоизини кичик тиббиёт ходимлари ва 11,2 фоизини ДПМ ларда ишловчи бошқа ходимларташқил этишган. Бу ҳолат, врачларга қараганда ўрта тиббиёт ходимларининг пациентлар билан давомлироқ ва такрор-такрор мулоқотда бўлишлари оқибати сифатида баҳоланиши мумкин, ҳамда муайян даражада адабиётларда келтирилган маълумотларга ҳамоҳанг.

Самарқанд вилоятида COVID-19 билан касалланган тиббиёт ходимларининг малакавий касб-кор таркиби, 2020 й., %. 172 ISSN 2181-7812 www.tma-journals.uz COVID-19 ҳолати қайд этилган тиббиёт ходимларидан эпидемиологик суриштирув ўтказилиб анамнез йиғилганида, уларнинг аксарияти – 77,6% ҳолатда касаллик уларнинг касбий фаолиятлари билан боғлиқ ҳолда, яъни иш жойларида юққанлигини қайд этишган. Пациентларнинг 22,4 фоизи касалликни маиший шароитларда (оилада, турли оммавий тадбирларда, таниш-биМаиший ҳолатда касалликнинг юқиши аксарият оилавий шароитда (42,8%) ва турли оммавий тўпланишлар (тўй-ҳашамлар, маросимлар, байрамларни нишонлаш ва ҳ.) (35,8%) пайтида содир бўлган. Шунингдек, пациентларнинг клиник ҳолати ҳам динамик баҳоланди. Пациентларни барча тегишли клиник, инструментал ва лаборатор усулларни мажмуавий қўллаб динамик кузатиш натижасида касалликнинг клиник кечиши 5,6% ҳолатда енгил, 51,2% – ўртача оғирлик, 26,4% – оғир ва 16,8% ҳолатда эса ўта оғир кечиш сифатида ташхис этилган. Пациентларнинг 50,4% ида зотилжам, жумладан 28,8% ида икки томонлама полисегментар зотилжам, 21,6% ида бир томонлама зотилжам қайд этилган. Хулоса Шундай қилиб, тадқиқот натижалари тиббиёт ходимлари, коронавирус инфекцияси билан курашишнинг энг қайноқ нуқтасида бўла туриб, касалликни юқтириш нуқтаи назаридан ўта хавфли гуруҳга мансуб эканлигини кўрсатмоқда. Пациентларнинг муружаат этишидан тортиб то госпитализация қилунгунига қадар барча босқичлардаги ҳатти-ҳаракатларнинг қатъий белгиланган тартиб асосида амалга оширилиши, шайлик таъминланиши, аҳоли ва ходимларда эҳтиёткорлик ошиши, масофавий алоқа воситалари орқали тиббий хизматлар ва маслаҳатлар тақдим этилиши, ижтимоий масофани сақлаш, шахсий ҳимоя воситаларидан фойдаланиш ҳамда ДПМ ларда, хусусан, COVID-19 стационарларида рисоладагидек инфекцион назорат йўлга қўйилиши тиббиёт ходимларига касаллик юқишини сезиларли даражада пасайтиради. Олинган натижалар COVID-19 пандемияси шароитида инфекцион хавфсизликни таъминлаш учун янгича ташкилий ва услубий ёндошувлар, ечимлар ишлаб чиқирилиши ва қўлланилиши зарурлигини тақазо этади.

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Калит сўзлар: COVID-19, тиббиёт ходимлари, госпитал инфекция, клиник-эпидемиологик хусусиятлар

Autonomic nervous system dysfunction in dentists with burnout syndrome

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Abstract. Intense rhythm of practical activities leads to a restructuring of functioning autonomic nervous system. In most of the examined dentists, the dominance of the ANS dysfunction was revealed, which indicates a pronounced fatigue of the medical workers.

Key words: autonomic nervous system, dentists, burnout.

In the study of the prevalence of burnout among dentists, a questionnaire by A.M. Wayne, which aims to identify the state of the autonomic nervous system (ANS) was used. The results of the study are presented in table 1.

Table 1. The level of ANS dysfunction in dentists with burnout syndrome

Specialists	ANS dysfunction level, points							
	Norm		Light		Medium		Severe	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
All dentists, 150	5	3.33	51	34.0	56	37.33	38	25.33

Persons with a score of less than 15 were taken as the norm. The number of such persons was only 3.33%. A mild degree corresponds to 16 - 29 points, an average - 30-45 points, and a severe one - from 46 to 67 points.

The first two categories of dentists were characterized by: significant work stress, often conflicts with patients, difficulties in relationships with colleagues, a sense of insecurity when they perform medical manipulations. At the same time, dentists noted various neurotic symptoms.

Dentists most often noted such complaints as: low mood (41.7%), irritability (49.0%), general weakness and fatigue (54.8%), insomnia (69.5%), frequent awakenings in the middle of the night (39.1%), inability in the evenings to get rid of the experiences of the day (58.6%), short-term dizziness and palpitations (31.2%).

Thus, the Wayne questionnaire initially revealed that 96.67% of dentists have ANS disorders. According to the literature, in everyday life, this figure for the

population, on average, should not exceed 73%, i.e., dentists need to correct autonomic dysfunction.

The correlation between ANS dysfunction and the severity of burnout was determined

Table 2. Correlations between ANS dysfunction and the degree of burnout.

	Burnout degree	ANS dysfunction, Pearson correlation coefficient, CI 95%
he	Low	0.13
reve	Medium	0.35
aled	High	0.88
corre		

lations indicate that the degree of burnout, regardless of severity, leads to ANS dysfunction ($P < 0.001$).

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCE

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada buyuk sharq mutafakkiri ikkinchi muallim Abu nasr Farobiy hayot yo`lining qisqacha mazmuni va asarlaridagi ta`lim-tarbiyaga oid qarashlarining o`ziga xos jihatlari haqidagi fikrlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: Ta`lim va tarbiya, axloq, dunyoviy bilish, o`quv faoliyati.

Sharq xalqlarining, jumladan o`zbek xalqining o`tmishdan yetib kelgan boy ma`naviy-madaniy merosi, o`lmas qadriyatlari ajdodlarimizning, tarixda sahifalaridan o`rin olgan buyuk mutafakkirlarimizning yuksak darajadagi intellektual qobiliyati va salmoqli mehnatlarining natijasidir.

Mutafakkirlarimizning yaratgan ilmiy asarlari, pedagogik qarashlari va g`oyalari bugungi kunda ko`plab rivojlangan mamlakatlarning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, siyosiy taraqqiyotida o`zining muhim ahamiyatini yo`qotmasdan kelmoqda.

Bugungi kunda ilmiy texnik-taraqqiyotning jadal sur`atlar bilan rivojlanishi axborot hajmining keskin ko`payishi, shuningdek fanlar integratsiyasi natijasida yangi fanlarning yuzaga kelishi, jamiyatda raqobat muhitini yuzaga keltirdi. Ushbu vazifalar asosida jamiyatning ta`lim tizimiga qo`ygan asosiy vazifalaridan biri – yuksak ma`naviy axloqli, jamiyat taraqqiyoti uchun munosib hissa qo`shadigan, rivojlangan davlatlar darajasidagi yuqori malakali, raqobatbardosh kadrlar tayyorlash masalasi deb belgilandi.

Ushbu vazifalarni samarali amalga oshirishda buyuk mutafakkirlarning ilmiy va hayot faoliyatini o`rganish, ularning hayot yo`llaridan saboq olish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Jumladan, O`rta asr ijtimoiy – falsafiy fikr taraqqiyoti mutafakkir Abu Nasr Forobiy nomi bilan bog`liq bo`lib, uning inson kamoloti haqidagi ta`limoti ta`lim – tarbiya sohasida katta ahamiyatga ega. Mashhur Yunon faylasufi Arastudan keyin

Sharqda o`z bilimi, fikr doirasining kengligi bilan nom chiqargan Forobiyni yirik mutafakkir – «Muallimiy soniy» – «Ikkinchi muallim» deb ataydilar.

Abu Nasr Forobiy (to`liq nomi Abu Nasr Muhammad ibn Muhammad ibn Uzlug` ibn Tarxon al-Forobiy) hijriy 260 yil (milodiy 873 yil)da Shosh – Toshkentga yaqin Forob (O`tror) degan joyda harbiy xizmatchi oilasida tug`ilgan.

Forobda boshlang`ich ta`limni olgach, Shoshda, Buxoroda, Samarqandda ta`lim olganligi haqida ma`lumotlar bor. Lekin arab xalifaligining yirik madaniy markazi Bag`dodga xalifalikning turli tomonlaridan kelgan olimlar yig`ilganligi, uning yirik ilmiy markazga aylanganligi tuyfayli Forobiy ham ilm olish istagida Bag`dodga jo`naydi. Bag`dodda Forobiy o`rta asr fanini, turli fan sohalarini o`rganadi. Masalan, unga Yunon tilida Abu Bashar Matta (Matta ibn Yunus), tibbiyot va mantiqdan Yuxanna ibn Haylon (Jilon) ta`lim bergan. Umuman, Forobiy Bag`doda matematika, mantiq, tibbiyot, ilmi-nujum, musiqa, tabiiyot, huquq, tilshunoslik, poetika bilan shug`ullandi, turli tillarni o`rgandi.

Ba`zi manbalarda Forobiy 70 dan oshiq tilni bilganligi haqida gapiriladi. Abu nasr Forobiy qomusiy olim hisoblanadi. Tadqiqotchilar uning 160 dan ortiq ilmiy asarlar yaratganligini qayd etadilar.

Forobiy tahminan 941 yillardan boshlab Damashqda yashaydi. Shahar chekkasidagi bog`da qorovul bo`lib ishlaydi va faqirona hayot kechirib, ilmiy ish bilan shug`ullanadi. 943-967 yillarda esa Halabda yashaydi. 949-950 yillarida Misrda ham bo`lgan. So`ng yana Damashqqa qaytib, shu yerda 950 yilda vafot etgan. Damashqdagi «Bob as – sag`ir» qabristoniga dafn qilingan. Rivoyatlarga ko`ra Abu Nasrning hikmat falsafani o`qishiga bir kishi sabab bo`lgan ekan. O`sha kishi unga Arastuning bir necha kitobini, shu yerda tura tursin, keyin olib ketaman deb qo`yib ketgani sabab bo`lgan, deyishadi. Ittifoqo, kitoblarga ko`zi tushib, ularning Abu Nasrning ko`nligiga ma`qul bo`lib qoladi va o`qishga kirishadi natijada yetuk faylusufga aylanadi. Haqiqatdan ham Abu Nasr Forobiy o`rta asr davri ilm-fani taraqqiyotiga katta hissa qo`shgan olim, Forobiy tabiiy, ilmiy va ijtimoiy bilimlarning barcha sohalarida ilmiy ish olib borgan. Forobiy o`zidan

keyin juda boy ilmiy meros qoldirgan. Falsafa, musiqa, filologiya va boshqa tabiiy, ilmiy bilimlarning turli sohalarida asarlar yaratgan.

Forobiy inson baxt – saodatga erishuvi uchun ularni baxtli – saodatli qila oladigan jamoa rahbari bo`lishi kerak deydi. U fozil shaharni boshqaradigan Hokim tabiat bo`lib, o`zida quyidagi xususiyatlarni jamlashi lozimligini aytadi:

- sog`-salomat bo`lib, o`z vazifasini bajarishda hech qanday qiyinchilik sezmaligi;
- tabiati nozik, farosatli; xotirasi mustahkam, zehni o`tkir, o`z fikrini tushuntira oladigan notiq, bilim-ma`rifatga havasli bo`lishi;
- taom yeyishda, ichimlikda, ayollarga yaqinlik qilishda ochofat emas, aksincha, o`zini tiya oladigan bo`lishi, qimor yoki boshqa o`yinlardan zavq, huzur olishdan uzoq bo`lishi,
- haq va haqiqatni, odil va haqgo`y odamlarni sevadigan, yolg`onni va yolg`onchilarni yomon ko`radigan bo`lishi,
- o`z qadrini biluvchi va oriyatli bo`lishi,
- mol dunyo ketidan quvmaydigan, adolatparvar, qatiyatli, sabotli, jur`atli, jasur bo`lishi muhimligini qayd etadi.

Forobiy bu fazilatlarni har bir yetuk insonda ko`rishni istaydi.

Forobiy o`zining fozil jamoasida odamlarni turli belgilarga qarab guruhlarga bo`ladi. Bunda u, kishilarning diniy mashabiga, millatiga, irqiga qarab emas, balki tabiiy hususiyatlariga, qobiliyatlariga, aqliy iqtidoriga, bilim ko`nikmalariga e`tibor berishlik zarur deydi. U o`zning “Baxt saodatga erishuv yo`llari haqida risola” asarida “Davlatning vazifasi insonlarni baxt – saodatga olib borishdir, – deb yozadi. Bu esa ilm va yaxshi axloq yordamida qo`lga kiritiladi”. Forobiy davlatni yetuk shaxs boshqarishi lozim deydi; ya`ni jamoani idora etuvchi adolatli, dono bo`lishi, qonunlarga rioya etishi va qonunlarni yarata olishi, kelgusini oldindan ko`ra bilishi, boshqalarga g`amxo`r bo`lishi lozim deydi.

Forobiy ta`lim tarbiyaga bag`ishlangan asarlarida ta`lim – tarbiyaning muhimligi, unda nimalarga e`tibor berish zarurligi, ta`lim – tarbiya usullari va uslubi haqida fikr yuritadi. “Fozil odamlar shahri”, “Baxt-saodatga erishuv to`g`risida” “Ixso –

al-ulum”, “Ilmlarning kelib chiqishi”, “Aql ma`nolari to`g`risida” kabi asarlarida ijtimoiy – tarbiyaviy qarashlari o`z ifodasini topgan.

Forobiy o`z ishlarida ta`lim – tarbiyani uzviy birlikda olib borish haqida ta`lim bergan bo`lsa ham, ammo har birining insonni kamolga yetkazishda o`z o`rni va xususiyati bor ekanligini alohida ta`kidlaydi.

Forobiy “Baxt – saodatga erishuv to`g`risida” asarida bilimlarni o`rganish tartibi haqida quyidagicha fikr bayon etgan. Uning ta`kidlashicha, avval bilish zarur bo`lgan ilm o`rganiladi, bu – olam asoslari haqidagi ilmdir. Uni o`rgangach, tabiiy ilmlarni, tabiiy jismlar tuzilishini, shaklini, osmon haqidagi bilimlarni o`rganish lozim. Undan so`ng, umuman, jonli tabiat o`simlik va hayvonlar haqidagi ilm o`rganiladi, – deydi. Forobiy ta`lim-tarbiyaning asosiy vazifasi jamiyat talablariga javob bera oladigan va shu jamiyat uchun xizmat qiladigan yetuk insonni tarbiyalashdan iborat deb biladi.

Abu nasr Forobiy yana aytadiki: “Ta`lim – degan so`z xalqlar va shaharliklar o`rtasida nazariy fazilatni birlashtirishdir, tarbiya esa shu xalqlar o`rtasidagi tug`ma fazilat va amaliy kasb hunar fazilatlarini birlashtirish degan so`zdir.

Ta`lim faqat so`z va o`rgatish bilangina bo`ladi. Tarbiya esa, amaliy ish tajriba bilan, ya`ni shu xalq, shu millatning amaliy malakalardan iborat bo`lgan ish-harakat, kasb-hunarga berilgan bo`lishi, o`rganishidir”, – deydi.

Forobiy nazariy bilimlarni egallashga kirishgan har bir kishi xulq-odobda ham qay darajada pok bo`lishi kerakligini “Falsafani o`rganishdan oldin nimani bilish kerakligi to`g`risida”gi risolasida shunday ta`riflaydi: “Falsafani o`rganishdan avval o`zingizni hirs-havaslardan shunday tozalashingiz lozimki, sizda maishiy va shahvoniyat kabi noto`g`ri tuyg`ularga emas, balki kamolotga bo`lgan hirs-havas qolsin.

Bunga xulq axloqni faqat so`zdagina emas, balki haqiqatda (amalda) tozalash orqali erishish mumkin. Shundan so`ng xato va adashishdan saqlovchi, haqiqat yo`lini tushunib olishga boshlovchi (notiq – so`zlovchi, fikrlash ma`nosida) nafsini, jonini, ruhini tozalash zarur”.

Forobiy axloqiy fazilatlar deganda bilimdonlik, donolik va mulohazali bo`lish, vijdonlilik, kamtarlik, ko`pchilik manfaatini yuqori qo`yish, haqiqat, ma`naviy yuksaklikka intilish, adolatlilik kabi hislatlarni tushunadi. Ammo bu hislatlarning eng muhumi har bir insonning bilimli, ma`rifatli bo`lishidir. Shuning uchun ham Forobiy axloq tushunchasiga aql bilan uzviy bog`liq holda, tafakkurga asoslangan axloq sifatida qaraydi. Bundan biz Forobiyning axloqni xulq meyorlari ifodasi sifatidagina emas, balki kishilarning aqliy faoliyatining natijasi sifatida ham talqin etganligini ko`ramiz. Forobiyning “Aql ma`nolari haqida” nomli risolasida aql masalasini tahlil qilib, aql bilish haqidagi ta`limotida mantiq (logika) ilmi muhim o`rin tutadi deydi. U mantiq ilmi bilan grammatika o`rtasidagi mushtarakligini qayd etib, mantiqning aqlga munosabati, grammatikaning tilga munosabati kabidir – deb ta`kidlaydi. Grammatika odamlar nutqini tarbiyalagani kabi, mantiq ilmi ham tafakkurni tarbiyalaydi va haqiqiy yo`lda olib borish uchun aqlni to`g`rilab turadi deydi.

Forobiy “Musika haqida katta kitob” degan ko`p jildli asari bilan o`rta asrning yirik musiqashunosi sifatida ham mashxur bo`lgan. U musika ilmini nazariy, amaliy jihatdan yoritib, musiqani inson axloqini tarbiyalovchi sihat- salomatligini mustahkamlovchi vosita deb qaragan. Uning musika sohasida qoldirgan merosi musika madaniyati tarixida muhim ahamiyatga molikdir.

Forobiyning ta`lim-tarbiya yo`llari, usullari vositalari haqidagi qarashlari ham qimmatlidir. U insonda go`zal fazilatlar ikki yo`l – ta`lim va tarbiya yo`li bilan hosil qilinishini ta`kidlaydi. Ta`lim nazariy fazilatlarini birlashtirsa, tarbiya esa tug`ma fazilat – nazariy bilimlar va amaliy kasb-hunar, xulq odob fazilatlarini birlashtiradi. Ta`lim so`z va o`rganish bilan tarbiya esa amaliy ish, tajriba bilan amalga oshiriladi, deydi. Har ikkalasi birlashsa yetuklik namoyon bo`ladi, ammo bu yetuklik bilim va amaliy ko`nikmalarni qay darajada o`rganganligiga qarab paydo bo`ladi, deb ko`rsatadi.

Forobiy ta`limda barcha fanlarning nazariy asoslari o`rganilsa, tarbiyada ma`naviy-axloqiy qoidalar, odob me`yorlari o`rganiladi, kasb-hunarga oid malakalar hosil qilinadi, deb uqtiradi.

Bu muhim vazifa tajribali tarbiyachilar tomonidan ta`lim-tarbiyaning turli metodlari yordamida amalga oshiriladi. Forobiy ta`lim – tarbiya ishlarini ikki yo`l bilan amalga oshirishni nazarda tutadi.

“Amaliy fazilatlar va amaliy san`at (kasb-hunar)lar va ularni bajarishga odatlanish masalasi”ga kelganda, bu odat ikki yo`l bilan hosil qilinadi: bulardan birinchisi – qanoatbaxsh so`zlar, chorlovchi, ilhomlantiruvchi so`zlar yordamida odat hosil qilinadi, malakalar vujudga keltiriladi, odamdagi g`ayrat, qasd-intilish harakatga aylantiriladi.

Ikkinchi yo`l (yoki usul) – majbur etish yo`li. Bu usul gapga ko`nmovchi, qaysar shaharliklar va boshqa sahroyi xalqlarga nisbatan qo`llaniladi. Chunki ular o`z istaklaricha so`z bilan g`ayratga kiradiganlardan emaslar. Ulardan birortasi nazariy bilimlarni o`rganishga kirishsa, uning fazilati yaxshi bo`ladi. Kasb hunarlarni va juz`iy san`atlarni egallashga intilish bo`lmasa, bunday odamlarni majbur etmaslik kerak. Chunki shahar xalqlariga tarbiya berishdan maqsad – ularni fazilat egasi qilib va san`at ahllariga aylantirishdir.

Demak, Forobiy ta`lim – tarbiyada rag`batlantirish, odatlantirish, majbur etish metodlarini ilgari surgan. Har ikkala usul ham pirovardida insonni har tomonlama kamolga yetkazish maqsadini ko`zlaydi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda Forobiy pedagogik ta`limotining asosida komil insonni shakllantirish, insonni o`z mohiyati bilan ijtimoiy, ya`ni faqat jamiyatda, o`zaro munosabatlar jarayonida komillikka erishadi, degan falsafiy qarashi yotadi.

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Чет тилларини ўқитишда суггестопедия методининг афзалликлари

Мақтабгача таълим ташкилотлари директор ва
мутахассисларини қайта
тайёрлаш ва уларнинг малакасини
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А Н Н О Т А Ц И Я

Мақоладан кўзланган мақсад хорижий тилларни ўрганиш борасида самарали методлардан бири саналган суггестопедиянинг афзалликларини кўриб чиқиш ва унинг методик қийматини баҳолаш кўзланган. Унда муаллиф томонидан амалиётда тез ва самарали тил ўрганиш борасида таклифлар берилганлиги илмий ишнинг ютуғи ҳисобланади.

А Н Н О Т А Ц И Я

Цели статьи – рассмотреть возможность использования методов суггестопедии, которые успешно применяются при обучении иностранному языку и определен методическая ценность с точки зрения её эффективности и результативности в обучении иностранным языкам. Успех научной работы заключается в том, что автор дал некоторое приглашение для изучения иностранных языков быстро и эффективно на практике.

A N N O T A T I O N

The purpose of the article is to consider the use of the methods of suggestion therapy, which are successfully used in teaching a foreign language and have determined the methodological value in terms of its effectiveness and effectiveness in teaching foreign languages. The success of the scientific work lies in the fact that the author has given some invitation for studying foreign languages quickly and effectively in practice.

Калит сўзлар: гипермнезия, интенсив метод, метод, таълим, педагогика, суггестология, суггестопедик метод.

Ключевые слова: гипермнезия, интенсивный метод, метод, обучение, педагогика, суггестология, суггестопедический метод.

Key words: hypermnnesia, intensive method, method, education, pedagogy, suggestology, suggestopedic method.

“Суггестопедия” лотинча сўз бўлиб, “suggestio” сўзи “таъсир ўтказиш”, “paideia” эса “таълим” деган маъноларни англатади³. Методнинг асосчиси болгариялик врач Георгий Лозанов (Dr. Georgi Lozanov)дир⁴. Методга кўра, ўқувчилар фикрни жамлаш учун аутоген машғулотларни ўтказиши зарур. Улар паст овозда янграётган мусиқа орқали хотиржам ҳолатга келтирилади.

Суггестопедия методига асосланган дастлабки дарс уч қисмдан иборат⁵: тушуниб олиш, хотира билан ишлаш машқлари, амалиётда қўллаш машқлари.

Тушуниб олиш босқичи матндаги сўзларнинг грамматик ва лексик хусусиятларини тушунтиради. Чет тилидаги аксарият матнларда варроқнинг чап ярмида матннинг таржимаси, иккинчи ярмида эса ўша хорижий тилнинг ўзида берилади. **Хотира билан ишлаб босқичи** эса фаол ва нофаол қисмларга ажратилади. Фаол қисмда ўқитувчи матнни одатдаги тезликда ўқийди, айрим ҳолатларда баъзи сўзларга урғу беради, буни эса ўқувчилар такрорлайди. Нофаол қисмда эса ўқувчилар матнни мусиқа жўрлигида тинглайди. **Тайёргарлик босқичида** ўқувчилар ўрганган грамматик қоидалари ва нотаниш сўзларни сахна кўриниши, қўшиқ ва ўйин ёрдамида қайта такрорлайди.

Суггестопедия методига асосланган анъанавий дарс уч қисмдан иборат⁶: кириш қисм, хотира билан ишлаш, тайёргарлик, амалиётда қўллаш.

Кириш қисм орқали ўқитувчи мавзунини ўйин тарзида тунунтиришга ҳаракат қилиши лозим. Акс ҳолда ўқувчи зеркиб қолади. Шу сабаб грамматик ва лексик таҳлил ўтказилмайди. **Фаол ва нофаол хотира машқлари** ҳам бироз мураккаблашади: ўқитувчи матнга мос келувчи мусиқа жўрлигида матнни ўқиб беради. Ўқувчи ҳам у билан бирга матнни ўқийди ва ўқитувчи тўхтаган

³ Комлев Н.Г. Словарь иностранных слов. – Москва: ЭКСМО-Пресс, 2000. – 672 с.

⁴ ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Лозанов,_Георгий

⁵ en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Suggestopedia

⁶ Ўша манба.

вақтдагина янграётган мусиқани тинглайди. Нофаол қисм эса ўқувчидан тинч ҳолатда бўлишни талаб этади. **Тайёргарлик босқичи**да ўқувчилар классик кўшиқни айтади ва мавзу билан боғлиқ бирор қизиқарли ўйин ташкил этилади. Ўқитувчидан эса нафақат интерактивлик, балки назарияни ҳам яхши тушунган ҳолда болаларга билим бериш кўникмаси талаб этилади. **Амалиётда қўллаш босқичи**да ўқувчининг нутқи бўлинмайди, хатолари эса тўғирланмайди. Ўқитувчи мазкур усул билан ўқувчининг ўзига бўлган ишончини синдирмасликка ҳаракат қилади. Бунда ўқувчи эмас, ўқитувчи ўз-ўзини назорат қилиши зарур. Чунки улар шогирдининг ҳамкорига айланади ва машғулотларда уларга ёрдам беришга ҳаракат қилади. Бирок унинг ўзи ўтказилаётган ўйинларда иштирок этмайди. Мазкур ҳолатда ўқувчини кўпроқ рағбатлантириш назарда тутилади.

Суггестопедия тил ўргатиш ва уни амалиётга жорий этиш масаласини куйидаги омилларга боғлаш лозимлигини таъкидлайди:

биринчидан, ўқувчида ишонч уйғотиш, яъни бажариб бўлмайди, деган онг остида сақланиб қолган тўсиқни олиб ташлаш орқали унинг ўрнини ўзи бераётган билим билан тўлдириш. Бунда инсоннинг ички қўрқув ўрнини тилшунос берадиган билим эгаллаши лозим, деган назария илгари сурилади; **иккинчидан**, мулоқот жараёнини дўстона ташкил этиш. Бунда гапга нўнок инсонни ҳам муҳокамага чорлаш, уни турли йўллар билан қизиқтириш мақсади ётади;

учинчидан, тил ўрганувчилар ўртасидаги ёш тафоввутини олиб ташлаш (мазкур тизим кўпроқ тил ўқитиш марказларида ишлаб чиқилади), яъни энг кичик ёшдаги ўқувчидан тортиб тил ўрганиш хоҳишида бўлган максимум ёшдаги инсонгача билим қаршисида тенглаштириш, имкониятини холис баҳолаш, ҳар иккисида ҳам руҳий мувозанатни ушлаб туриш масаласи кўриб чиқилади.

Суггестопедия инсоннинг руҳий ҳолати билан боғлиқ бўлгани сабаб камчиликлардан ҳам ҳоли эмас. Лозановнинг таъкидлашича, ўқувчи, аввало,

руҳий томондан энгил, соғлом ва бошқа фанларда сезиларли ютукқа эришган, бир сўз билан айтганда, ўз кучига ишонган ҳолатдагина метод орқали муваффақиятга эришади. Яна бир тадқиқотчи Д.Аветисяннинг таъкидлашича⁷, методнинг асосий камчиликлари сирасига педагогга тушадиган юкломани киритади. Унда ўқитувчи чет тили бўйича кучли мутахассис бўлиш билан бирга интерактив тарзда дарсни ташкил этиш кўникмасини шакллантириш вазифаси кўндаланг туради. Шунингдек, машғулотда 2—3 нафар ўқувчи, максимум эса 5—7 киши қатнашиши мумкин. Бундай таълим олиш эса молиявий томондан бироз ноқулайлик туғдиради.

Замонавий педагогика ва психология суггестопедиянинг самарасини кўйидагиларда деб баҳолайди:

- катта ҳажмдаги ахборотни тез ва самарали усулда ўзлаштириш;
- ахборот базасини ошириш ва кўпроқ билим олиш;
- таълим жараёнида ўқувчидаги мотивацияни шижжат билан ошириш;
- психологик тўсиқлар, хусусан, шубҳа, қўрқувни бартараф этиш кабилар⁸.

Юқоридагилардан келиб чиқиб хулоса қиладиган бўлсак, суггестопедия методига интенсив тил ўқитиш мақсадида кўп бора муружаат қилинмоқда. Унинг имкониятларидан тўлиқ фойдаланган ҳолда педагогик жараёнда яхши натижага эришилади.

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⁸ <http://para.by/articles/text/izuchem-inostrannye-yazyki-metod-lozanova>

Structure of boards of trustees in otmls in malaysia

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In Malaysia, the structure and powers of the Boards of Trustees in HEIs are regulated by the relevant law, and their rights and powers are determined. According to it, all members of the Board of Trustees, with the exception of the vice-chancellor, are appointed by the Minister of Education for a three-year term with the right to reappointment. The Vice-Chancellor is an ex-officio member of the Board, appointed by the Minister of Education after consultation with the Board of Trustees. It should be noted that if the Minister of Education is not satisfied with the activities of the educational institution, he has the right to appoint additional members of the Board of Trustees, as well as to dismiss them from their positions at any time. The amount of fees paid to the members of the Board of Trustees is determined by the Minister of Education of the country.

The Board of Trustees has wide powers and is the main executive body in the Malaysian HEIs. The Council determines and appoints the powers and working conditions of the officials of the HEI, such as the Registrar, Treasurer and Librarian. The Council regulates the issues of disposal of the property of the higher educational institution, as well as the issues of attracting loans and investing the free funds of the educational institution. It should be noted that borrowing and investment funds require the prior approval of the Malaysian Minister of Finance.

The board`s responsibilities include, among others, the discipline of HSE employees. According to it, the Council should exercise disciplinary control over all employees and officials of the Higher Education Institution. For this purpose, the Council may establish special disciplinary committees for different categories of employees. Disciplinary committees can exercise their powers on all issues related to the discipline of each member of the faculty, official or employee under the jurisdiction of the committee. At the same time, the Malaysian law stipulates

that the activity of the disciplinary committee does not apply to the Rector, Vice-Chancellors and Vice-Chancellor of Higher Education Institutions.

The Board of Trustees may, at its discretion, develop disciplinary rules to ensure the internal discipline of faculty members, officials, staff and students of the Higher Education Institution. Disciplinary measures may include the dismissal or demotion of an HEI employee, as well as expulsion from the ranks of students if these measures are taken against students.

Quorum is a necessary condition for decision-making by the Board of Trustees. The quorum is reached at the meeting of the Board of Trustees with the attendance of the chairman and three of his members. If the chairman of the Council is unable to fulfill his duties, the Minister of Education appoints one of the members of the Council to the position of chairman.

The structure and powers of the Senate of higher education institutions in Malaysia are also regulated by relevant laws. The Senate is the main scientific body within HEIs.

The Vice-Chancellor is one of the important links of management in Malaysian higher education institutions. According to the educational legislation of this country, the vice-chancellor is the highest executive and official scientific employee of the higher education institution. The role of the Vice-Chancellor of a Malaysian institution of higher education is the same as that of the President in US and European HEIs. The Vice-Chancellor is appointed by the Malaysian Minister of Education on the recommendation of the Higher Education Institution's Board of Trustees. The reference and other working conditions of the Vice-Chancellor are also determined by the Minister of Education after consultation with the Board of Trustees. The Vice-Chancellor has broad powers. He is a person who exercises general control over scientific research, financing, management, internal order and discipline in a higher education institution.

Thus, it is wrong to conclude that the activities of higher education institutions in Malaysia are mainly regulated by state bodies, and that the

administrative autonomy of HEIs will be limited. For example, only two of the eight members of the Board of Trustees are government representatives in name only, while in fact 7 members of the Board (excluding the Vice-Chancellor) are appointed by the Minister of Education. However, the Vice-Chancellor, who must be a member of the Council by virtue of his position, is also appointed by the Minister.

Sociolinguistic Competence as a Linguistic Problem in Teaching Foreign Languages to B2 Level Students

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Abstract

Sociolinguistic competence is an essential aspect of foreign language learning, particularly for B2 level students. This competence refers to the ability to use language appropriately in different social contexts and cultural settings. However, teaching sociolinguistic competence can be challenging due to the complex nature of language use and cultural differences. This research article aims to explore sociolinguistic competence as a linguistic problem when teaching B2 level students' foreign languages. The article discusses the importance of sociolinguistic competence in foreign language learning, the challenges of teaching sociolinguistic competence, and the strategies that can be used to enhance sociolinguistic competence among B2 level students.

Introduction

Language is a communication tool that enables people from different cultural backgrounds to interact with each other. Language proficiency is essential for successful communication between people who speak different languages. Sociolinguistic competence is an essential component of communication proficiency as it relates to the social and cultural context of language usage. In language teaching, sociolinguistic competence requires learners to understand the social and cultural contexts in which language is used. The learning of sociolinguistic competence can present a linguistic problem in teaching B2 level students in foreign languages, and this paper explores this issue.

Background

Sociolinguistic competence is the ability to use language appropriately and effectively in various social and cultural contexts. It enables learners to communicate effectively in different situations and with different people. To

acquire sociolinguistic competence, learners need to learn not only the grammatical rules of the language but also the social and cultural conventions that govern its use.

B2 level is an intermediate level in the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), which measures language proficiency levels. At this level, learners are expected to have a good understanding of the language and be able to communicate in various contexts. Learners are expected to have a good grasp of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation, as well as the ability to understand and produce moderately complex texts.

The learning of sociolinguistic competence presents a linguistic problem in teaching B2 level students. Sociolinguistic competence is not only about knowing the rules of the language but also about understanding the context in which language is used. B2 level students need to learn not only the language structures but also the cultural norms of the target culture.

Contextualization

Contextualization is an essential aspect of sociolinguistic competence. It involves the ability to understand and use language appropriately in different situations and with different people. In language teaching, contextualization requires learners to understand how language is used in different social and cultural contexts.

B2 level students need to learn how to contextualize language use appropriately. They need to understand the cultural norms and expectations of the target culture to communicate effectively in different contexts. For example, in some cultures, it is considered impolite to address someone by their first name unless they are close friends or family members. B2 level students need to learn such cultural norms to avoid causing offense or misunderstanding.

Pragmatics

Pragmatics is another essential aspect of sociolinguistic competence. It refers to the ability to use language appropriately and effectively in various social and cultural

contexts. Pragmatics involves the knowledge of various speech acts, such as requesting, apologizing, thanking, and offering.

B2 level students need to learn the pragmatics of the target language to communicate effectively in different situations. For example, in some cultures, it is common to use indirect language when making requests or giving instructions. B2 level students need to learn such pragmatic conventions to communicate effectively in the target culture.

Cultural Awareness

Cultural awareness is an essential aspect of sociolinguistic competence. It refers to the ability to understand and appreciate the cultural differences between the learner's culture and the target culture. Cultural awareness is crucial to avoid misunderstandings and to communicate effectively in different cultural contexts.

B2 level students need to develop cultural awareness to communicate effectively in the target language. For example, they need to learn the appropriate behavior and etiquette in different social and cultural situations, such as business meetings, social events, and family gatherings. Cultural awareness also involves understanding the values, beliefs, and customs of the target culture.

Teaching Strategies

Teaching sociolinguistic competence to B2 level students requires a variety of teaching strategies. Teachers need to create a supportive learning environment that encourages learners to experiment with the language and to use it in different social and cultural contexts. Some of the strategies that can be used include role-play activities, real-life scenarios, cross-cultural comparisons, authentic materials and collaborative learning.

1. Role-play Activities

Role-play activities involve learners in simulating real-life situations to practice language use in different contexts. This strategy helps learners to develop their sociolinguistic competence by allowing them to practice their language skills in a

safe and supportive environment. For example, learners can simulate a job interview, a business meeting or a conversation with a friend or family member.

2. Real-Life Scenarios

Real-life scenarios involve learners in problem-solving activities that help them to develop their sociolinguistic competence in a specific context. This strategy places learners in real-life situations that they are likely to encounter in their daily lives, such as reading street signs, ordering food in a restaurant or buying a ticket for public transportation. By practicing their language skills in a practical context, learners can develop their sociolinguistic competence in a way that is relevant to their daily lives.

3. Cross-Cultural Comparisons

Cross-cultural comparisons involve learners in comparing and contrasting the cultural norms and values of their own culture with those of the target culture. This strategy helps learners to develop their sociolinguistic competence by allowing them to understand the social and cultural context in which language is used. For example, learners can compare and contrast the ways in which people from different cultures greet each other, make requests, or express gratitude.

4. Authentic Materials

Authentic materials such as songs, videos, and literature written in the target language can expose learners to authentic language use in different contexts. This strategy helps learners to develop their sociolinguistic competence by exposing them to the natural rhythms and patterns of speech, as well as the idiomatic expressions and cultural references that are commonly used in the target language.

5. Collaborative Learning

Collaborative learning strategies such as group work, pair work, and peer discussions can help learners to develop their sociolinguistic competence by giving them opportunities to practice their language skills in a social context. Collaboration allows learners to learn from one another, share experiences, and

provide feedback on each other's language use. For example, learners can work in groups to prepare a presentation, discuss a topic or analyze a text.

Conclusion

Sociolinguistic competence is an essential component of communication proficiency in foreign language learning. However, teaching sociolinguistic competence to B2 level students can present a linguistic problem due to the complexity of social and cultural conventions involved in language use. Teachers need to use a variety of teaching strategies to create a supportive learning environment for learners to experiment with the language and to develop sociolinguistic competence. Developing sociolinguistic competence is essential for effective communication between people from different cultural backgrounds.

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Ilmiy tadqiqot mavzusini tanlash va uning dolzarbligini asoslash

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada tadqiqot mavzusini tanlash, ob'ektiv omillarni hisobga olish, tadqiqotchining qiziqishi, mayli, ongi, bilimi, dunyoqarashi, e'tiqodi, sensitiv kechinmalari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ilmiy tadqiqot, mavzu, mayl, ong, bilim, dunyoqarash, e'tiqod, sensitiv kechinmalar.

Ilmiy tadqiqot mavzusini tanlashgacha bo'lgan jarayonlarni tadqiqotchining «o'zini o'zi izlash», «o'zligini topish» davri deb atash mumkin. Bu davrda tadqiqotchi hali biror-bir mavzuni tanlashdan, uni biror muammo bilan bog'lashdan uzoq bo'ladi. Tajriba ko'rsatadiki, ilm sohasiga birinchi qadam tashlaganidayoq mavzu topib, uni biror muammo bilan bog'lay olgan tadqiqotchi deyarli uchramaydi. Demak, mavzu tanlashda ilm sohasidan, mavzuga oid izlanishlar va muammolardan yaxshi xabardor mutaxassisning yordami, maslahati zarur. Bunday mutaxassis mavzu tanlashga ta'sir etuvchi ob'ektiv omillardan xabardor bo'lgani uchun ham «ilmiy rahbar», «ilmiy maslahatchi», tadqiqotni ratsional olib borishni o'rgatuvchi «ustoz» deb ataladi.

Mavzuni tanlashga undovchi ob'ektiv omillar quyidagilardan iborat:

- ijtimoiy taraqqiyot talabi;
- ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyot talabi;
- ijtimoiy-siyosiy tuzum ehtiyoji;
- iqtisodiy rivojlanish omili;
- madaniy yuksalish ehtiyoji.

Ilm-fanning ijtimoiy taraqqiyotga xizmat qilishi aksiomadir. Shuning uchun tanlanadigan mavzu ijtimoiy taraqqiyot maqsadlari va vazifalari bilan bog'liq bo'lishi zarur.

Ijtimoiy taraqqiyot deganda umuminsoniy rivojlanish, umumbashariy qadriyatlarni asrash va ko'paytirish, ijtimoiy hayotni yanada insoniylashtirish, global

muammolarni hal etish, insoniyat erishgan yutuqlarni, pozitiv tajribalarni yanada ko`paytirish nazarda tutiladi. Mazkur maqsad va vazifalarga xizmat qilish orqaligina ilm-fan, o`tkaziladigan tadqiqot, tanlanadigan mavzu pozitiv ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Ijtimoiy taraqqiyotni bugun ilmiy-texnik kashfiyotlarsiz, ixtirolarsiz tasavvur etib bo`lmaydi. Inson mehnatini yengillash- tirish va samaradorligini oshirish, ijodiy salohiyatini to`la ro`yobga chiqarish imkoniyatini beruvchi vositalar, mexanizmlar va shart-sharoitlar yaratish ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyotning bosh vazifasidir. Bugun jon-jahd va fidoyilik bilan mehnat qilish yetarli emas, mehnatni, faoliyatni ratsional tashkil etish, samaradorligini oshirish yo`llarini izlash muhimdir. Jamiyatga ilmiy aqliy quvvatlariga tayanib, mehnatni, faoliyatni oqilona uyushtirishga, ijtimoiy ehtiyojlarni to`la qondirishga qaratilgan usullarga, vositalarga tayanadigan, ushbu usullarni va vositalarni kashf etadigan shaxslar kerak. Shuning uchun ham tadqiqot mavzusini ilmiy-texnik rivojlanish maqsadidan kelib chiqib tanlash talab etiladi.

Ilm-fan oldiga ijtimoiy-siyosiy tuzum ham o`z talabini qo`yadi. Ijtimoiy-siyosiy tuzum ichki institutlarini o`z maqsadiga muvofiq faoliyat olib borishini istaydi, aks holda tuzum bilan institutlar o`rtasida begonalashuv yuzaga keladi. Aniq strategik maqsadi va rivojlanish dasturiga, modeliga ega ijtimoiy-siyosiy tuzum barcha sohalarni institutlarni, shu jumladan ilm-fanni ham ana shu strategik maqsad va rivojlanish dasturiga, modeliga xizmat qilish- ga yo`naltiradi. Ushbu ob`ektiv, ijtimoiy talabga xizmat qilishga tayyor tadqiqotgina siyosiy tuzum tomonidan qo`llab-quvvatlanadi.

Iqtisodiy rivojlanish barcha davrlarda, barcha davlatlarda ilm-fan rivojlanishiga ta`sir etuvchi ob`ektiv omil bo`lib kelgan. Inson va jamiyatning moddiy ehtiyojlarini qondirish orqaligina ilm-fan, ilmiy izlanishlar o`zining ijtimoiy foydali mashg`ulot, faoliyat ekanini isbotlagan. Demak, ilmiy tadqiqot mavzusini tanlashda iqtisodiy rivojlanish omili unutilmasligi kerak. Hatto sof ilmiy-nazariy, diniy-transsendental, apriori mavjudligini asoslashga qaratilgan izlanishlar ham

pirovard natijada amaliyot, dunyoni mukammallashtirish, insonning ruhiy olamini yuksaltirishga oid o`zining empirik tavsiyalarini berishini esdan chiqarib bo`lmaydi.

Ijtimoiy taraqqiyot insonni o`rab turgan «sun`iy olam», artefaktlar, «madaniyat» deb ataluvchi moddiy va ma`naviy boyliklar orqali idrok etiladi, o`lchanadi. Ilm-fanning o`zi madaniyatga oid sohadir, shu bois madaniy yuksalishga xizmat qilish uning immanent xususiyatidir.

Tanlanadigan mavzu g`ayrimadaniy bo`lmasligi, ya`ni insoniyat tomonidan yaratilgan moddiy va ma`naviy boyliklarning pozitiv hodisa ekanligini inkor qilmasligi, hatto shubha ostiga olishi mumkin emas. Tanlanadigan mavzu madaniyatning pozitiv hodisaligini tasdiqlashi, moddiy va ma`naviy boyliklarni yanada ko`paytirish texnologiyasini ishlab chiqishi, aniq, ilmiy asoslangan yo`llarni ko`rsatishi zarur.

Tadqiqot mavzusini tanlashda ob`ektiv omillarni hisobga olish qanchalik muhim bo`lmasin, ular sub`ektiv omillar borligini inkor qilolmaydi. Ijod, shu jumladan, ilmiy ijod ham tadqiqotchining qiziqishi, mayli, ongi, bilimi, dunyoqarashi, e`tiqodi, sensitiv kechinmalari, reflektiv va gnoseologik tajribalarining mahsulidir. Tadqiqotchining ilmiy qiziqishini hisobga olmasdan mavzu berish noo`rin. Qiziqishiga zid bo`lgan mavzu tadqiqotchini ilmiy yangilik, kashfiyot qilishga yetaklamaydi. Vaholanki, ilmiy tadqiqot- dan maqsad ilm-fanga biror yangilik olib kirish, betakror g`oyalar, fikr-xulosalar bilan ilmiy merosni boyitishdir.

To`g`ri, ilmiy qiziqish ijtimoiy ehtiyojlarga muvofiq kelmasligi, hatto ularga zid kelishi mumkin. Bunday taqdirda, tadqiqotchining shaxsiy, ilmiy qiziqishi bilan ijtimoiy talablarni muvofiqlashtirish tavsiya etiladi. Biroq, buni alohida esda tutish darkor, ijtimoiy talablar bayrog`i ostida tadqiqotchining qiziqishini unutish uning ilm-fanga haqiqiy sodiq mutaxassis, mustaqil, erkin fikrlovchi olim sifatida shakllanishiga yordam bermaydi.

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The influence of literature on the formation of the student's personality

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The role of educational institutions in the formation of the student's personality has increased not only in our country, but also on a global scale in the last century. From this point of view, the determination of the specific content of each of the educational subjects for the state standards is not accidental. Formation of national and international outlook of students has been defined as one of the main directions of that content in the subject of literature. The process of assimilation of international values and formation of worldview in students can also be called the process of formation of planetary thinking in them.

Although the rapid development of scientific and technical progress leads to high achievements and progressive changes in real life, certain tendencies of this process to the cultural development of society and moral and spiritual values are also evident. At such a time, in the field of education of the young generation in the national context, returning to the roots, national self-awareness, moral and spiritual values are of great importance. Protecting the historically formed high moral and spiritual values of the people and directing the cultural development of the society as a whole is regulated both by the policy implemented by the state and by the cultural-intellectual and scientific-pedagogical principles put forward by the social sphere.

Moral and spiritual values, which are the main indicators of the people's existence, are its most valuable wealth. Every nation has a system of national and moral values. These national and moral values are our history, language, religion, traditions, mentality, national characteristics, culture, literature and art. Both the educational system and the cultural and spiritual life of young people should create such an environment that the ability of this environment to react to external influences is strong. That is, there should be a protective area between the person and the external influence. When there are gaps in the protective field between a

person and the cultural-spiritual environment, foreign influences affect memory. At this time, those with a low level of outlook, weak-willed, and those far from moral and spiritual values easily succumb to these influences. In this regard, the work carried out in the direction of raising the moral and spiritual development of the young generation, the level of national self-awareness, and voluntary abilities should be carried out in a systematic manner.

The role of educational institutions in the formation of the student's personality has increased not only in our country, but also on a global scale in the last century. From this point of view, the determination of the specific content of each of the educational subjects for the state standards is not accidental. Formation of national and international outlook of students has been defined as one of the main directions of that content in the subject of literature. The process of assimilation of international values and formation of worldview in students can also be called the process of formation of planetary thinking in them.

In addition to the acquisition of knowledge and skills during the educational activities of the students, the skills of thinking, analyzing, comparing, and making independent decisions are also formed. These cognitive processes encourage students to mature and become perfect human beings. Independent reasoning plays an important role in the formation of "student identity".

Cultivation of students' sense of attachment to the motherland, nation, country, development of their intellectual level, the process of more orderly and systematic formation of cognitive-cognitive and communicative communication skills is directly related to the form and content of instruction and promotion from Literary Examples.

Each work studied can be personalized with a new interesting aspect. Students express their opinions and judgments independently, at the same time in the direction directed by the teacher, compare with the opinions of their peers and finally acquire the ability to make independent decisions.

Creativity should be given ample space in the teaching process. Divide the work into parts, determine the title, put yourself in the place of the hero in the story, change the events, express the attitude of the characters, write an essay, etc. such qualities express the student's creative qualities.

Starting from oral folk literature, students who study examples of literature created until today can distinguish bad from good, straight from crooked. The legend "Mother Deer" taught in the 5th grade teaches students to love nature, and the fairy tale "Yetim Ibrahim" teaches that ingenuity and reason win. It is a great responsibility, duty and honor for every teacher to instill "Love of the Motherland" in young students. Similarly, in the epics "Kitabi Dada-Gorgud" and "Koroglu", our students are instilled with feelings of patriotism, love for the land, motherland, and mother.

While studying proverbs and issues, the student can analyze and compare contrasts between truth and lies, greed and kindness, love and hate. He is able to distinguish the negative and positive qualities of a person. Independently expresses a personal attitude to the image. In the debates, he becomes the representative of the character. It enhances and defends the characteristic features of images. This makes the teacher very happy. In other words, topics stimulate discussions around new problems.

Comparing and analyzing the main examples of our modern literature, analyzing and teaching them within the framework of the literature course of general schools can bring new successes to the Azerbaijani school. Of course, the teaching of literary examples should be treated with a certain sensitivity, the national and moral values that the student carries and the local psychological environment must be taken into account during the lesson. "The literature course has great opportunities to shape the student's personality, intellectual world and aesthetic taste. Pupils acquire an active life position by understanding and evaluating the complex events and life realities that are reflected in the artistic work. In this sense, literature classes should be treated as life and spirituality

classes, as a kind of cognitive activity. Fiction is a special form of spiritual communication. The student reader, reading a perfect example of art, reflects on the moral and aesthetic issues raised there, and comments on the hero's fate, the artist's position, becomes the interviewer of the powerful artist, is spiritually enriched by studying his ideas and thoughts, and allows school children to evaluate their activities, actions and behavior from moral and aesthetic norms.

Key words: pupil, national-moral values, people, epics, personality, literature

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PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCE

Language Maintenance and Bilingualism in Uzbekistan.

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Annotation:

Uzbekistan is a multilingual and multicultural country with a rich linguistic history. The country is home to more than 30 different ethnic groups, each with its unique language and culture. The official language of Uzbekistan is Uzbek, and it is the most widely spoken language in the country. However, the Russian language also holds significant importance in the country, particularly among the urban population and ethnic Russians. This article will explore the role of the Russian language in Uzbekistan and its impact on the maintenance of the Uzbek language. It will also examine the promotion of active bilingualism as a means of language maintenance in a multilingual society.

Key words:

native language / preservation of native languages / history of Uzbek language / national character of language / bilingualism / active bilingualism / intermediary language / social functions of language / multicultural space / linguistic identity / linguistic personality.

The preservation of unique cultures and languages of small groups is a pressing issue in the current era of globalization. It is often argued that the dominance of global languages leads to the disappearance of smaller languages, which in turn leads to the disappearance of the associated people. Language is a crucial aspect of a group's identity, and its loss can have significant consequences on a group's self-preservation. While it may seem simple to discuss the disappearance of languages in the context of a global society, it is important to acknowledge the impact of this process on the people and their distinct cultures.

The History of Language Use in Uzbekistan:

Uzbekistan has a complex history with language use and maintenance, particularly during the Soviet era. The Soviet government used the Russian language as the primary language of instruction in schools, which contributed to the spread of the Russian language in the country. Many people in Uzbekistan learned Russian as their first language, and it became the dominant language for government, education, and media. The widespread use of Russian in Uzbekistan also led to a decline in the use of the Uzbek language, particularly among the urban population. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, Uzbekistan started promoting the use of the Uzbek language and has made significant efforts to revive and maintain the language. The government has introduced policies to promote the use of the Uzbek language in various domains, including education, media, and public services. Today, Uzbek is the official language of Uzbekistan, and the government has made significant efforts to promote its use and maintenance.

The Role of the Russian Language in Uzbekistan:

Despite the promotion of the Uzbek language, Russian remains a significant language in Uzbekistan, particularly among the urban population and ethnic Russians. Many people in Uzbekistan are bilingual, and the ability to speak both languages is considered a valuable skill in the country. The most common form of bilingualism in Uzbekistan is active bilingualism, where both languages are used in different contexts, with the native language serving some social functions and the second language performing others. For example, Uzbek is used for family and cultural matters, while Russian is used for business and official purposes.

The Russian language plays a significant role in Uzbekistan's economic and political life. Many ethnic Russians and other Russian-speaking communities in Uzbekistan work in government, business, and the media, where the ability to speak Russian is often a requirement. The Russian language is also essential for communication with neighboring countries, such as Russia and Kazakhstan, where Russian is widely spoken.

Impact on Language Maintenance:

The widespread use of the Russian language in Uzbekistan has had a significant impact on the maintenance of the Uzbek language. During the Soviet era, the use of the Russian language led to a decline in the use of the Uzbek language, particularly among the urban population. The promotion of the Uzbek language after the collapse of the Soviet Union has led to the revival of the language, but the widespread use of the Russian language remains a challenge for language maintenance.

The promotion of active bilingualism is one of the effective ways to preserve native languages in a multilingual society. Active bilingualism in Uzbekistan involves the use of both the Uzbek and Russian languages in different contexts. The native language serves some social functions, while the second language performs others. The use of both languages in different contexts helps to maintain and promote the use of both languages.

The Promotion of Active Bilingualism in Uzbekistan:

The government of Uzbekistan has introduced policies to promote active bilingualism in the country. One of the key strategies is the promotion of bilingual education, where children are taught in both the Uzbek and Russian languages. Bilingual education provides children with the ability to communicate effectively in both languages, and

provides them with a valuable skill that is increasingly in demand in the job market. Bilingual education has been introduced in schools throughout the country, and there has been an increase in the number of bilingual schools in recent years.

In addition to bilingual education, the government of Uzbekistan has also introduced policies to promote the use of both the Uzbek and Russian languages in the media, public services, and other domains. The use of both languages in these domains ensures that both languages are promoted and maintained, and that people are encouraged to use both languages in their daily lives.

The promotion of active bilingualism is essential for language maintenance in a multilingual society. It ensures that both languages are used and maintained, and

that people are encouraged to communicate in both languages. The use of both languages is particularly important in a country like Uzbekistan, where there are many different ethnic groups, each with its unique language and culture. The promotion of active bilingualism helps to create a more cohesive and multilingual society, where people are encouraged to communicate and understand each other's languages and cultures.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, language maintenance and bilingualism are essential for a multilingual society like Uzbekistan. The Russian language has played a significant role in the country's linguistic history, and it remains an important language in the country today. However, the promotion of the Uzbek language and active bilingualism are necessary to ensure that both languages are used and maintained.

The government of Uzbekistan has introduced policies to promote the use of both languages in various domains, and there has been an increase in the number of bilingual schools in recent years. The promotion of active bilingualism helps to create a more cohesive and multilingual society, where people are encouraged to communicate and understand each other's languages and cultures.

In a globalized world, the maintenance of native languages is becoming increasingly important. The promotion of active bilingualism and the maintenance of native languages are essential for the preservation of cultural and linguistic diversity. In Uzbekistan, the promotion of active bilingualism and the maintenance of the Uzbek language and the Russian language are crucial for creating a more cohesive and multilingual society.

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Improving speaking skills by watching movies.

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Annotation

One of the most important parts of the language is speaking. While learning and after learning a particular foreign language, you should communicate well. Watching movies is also one of the most effective ways for boosting speaking skills. In this thesis I will provide some data about skills which are useful when improving speaking.

Key words: pronunciation, ball, traditional speaking lessons, dialogue, discussions, personality and communication, movie, shadowing technique.

Introduction

Speaking is the hardest and the funniest way to learn a particular language. Many people find it hard to speaking fluently, especially in foreign languages. However, there are some techniques and ways which are useful for all the learners of speaking. First and foremost is pronunciation. Learning to pronounce a language is a very complex learning task, the learning process can be facilitated if the task is structured in some way and if the learner is aware of exactly what is involved. It is difficult for learners to do this for themselves, so it is the teacher`s job. This means dividing task into components, ordering the components in some way (for example, from basic to complex, or easy to difficult) and showing the learner why each component must be learned. For example, one component of tennis is learning how to serve. Serving can be divided into: how to hold the racket; tossing up the ball; striking the ball; placing the ball; varying the speed and direction of the ball, and so on. Similarly, any kind of foreign language speaking consists of various patterns such as sounds, stress, and variation in pitch and the learner needs to understand the function of these as well as their form.

Besides, in the traditional speaking lessons teachers also could give enough tips for the learners of the language speaking. For instance, the technique of reading five times and reciting the article orally. This technique requires students to read the article five times, analyzing, finding new words, learning new collocation and phrases by heart and at the end retelling the article in front of the mirror. With this way the learner`s speaking boosts automatically. In the traditional speaking lessons, teachers might use this method in order to make students more talkative. Organizing small dialogues in class, also one of the effective ways learning speaking. Not only in the classroom, but also in a daily life who wants to speak more might use dialogues as a source of learning speaking.

The third and main technique for speaking is to watch movies, you tube blogs and videos. With the help of watching movies, student firstly, learns the culture, and then the way of speaking, pronunciation, common phrases and collocations. Moreover, the movie consists of many characters and actors, yourself it is very important to use hand and head gestures. The genre of the movie really depends on the learner, because there are so many tastes when choosing a film. One might like romance and one fantasy. So, when choosing a movie be careful, try as much as possible to find the original-language movie. While watching the movie, you face so many new words and phrases. Do not worry, because the real way of speaking is reflected by movies of that language. Try to find more funnier movies if you are learning English. For instance, “Friends” is my favorite movie. I watched and learned so many ways of speaking with the help of this movie. After watching and learning new phrases, discussing it with friends or family members who are learning foreign language is the best way to remember and improve speaking skills. Because, if you talk about something out loud, you could be aware of your mistakes, your flow of ideas and the intonation which you are using.

After reading these techniques you might think that I also learn the public speaking – speaking without any fear in front of the people. When you are learning public speaking, the first and foremost thing is to understand personality and

communication. Your effort to develop communication skills that will contribute to a successful career must start with self- evaluation. Before you go forward, you must look backward. You have already lived a significant span of your life and, in the process, formed a personality that directly influences the way you interact with others. It is necessary that you reflect for a while on just how you became the person you are and why each of you has a personality distinct from one another.

Social scientists define personality as a system of beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that are the particular qualities and characteristics of a person.

There are many theories explaining how personalities develop, but it is not our purpose to present detailed explanations of these theories. That is more the function of a psychology or sociology textbook.

However, we can generalize by noting that these theories take one of two broad approaches: biological determinism or cultural determinism. Simply stated, biological deterministic theories suggest that genetic factors have a greater impact on human behavior than was previously thought. Culturally deterministic theories claim that environment, the things we are exposed to in our lives, is the primary influence that molds our personalities. The truth probably lies somewhere between the two theories and there is still much that we have to learn. We can, however, acknowledge the biological theories and still claim that our personalities are primarily the result of the cultural stimuli we receive during the socialization process.

Conclusion

These methods and ways of acquiring speaking skills help learners to boost their speech. You might choose which methods you like according to your interests. Every way has its own beneficial sides for the users.

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Types according to the scope of the pamphlet genre

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Abstract: The purpose of the work is to study the types of the pamphlet genre according to the scale. Its structure, content, and plot are determined by the nature of the subject, material, and the characteristic of the author`s creative individuality. Pamphlet requires refinement of style, special literary finishing of the material, skill and work ability of the author.

Keywords: journalism, pamphlet, periodical, Battle of the Books, Tale of the Barrel, genre

The concept of journalism has been developing since the first time it appeared in the minds of all mankind until today. It has become a separate, integrated field. We decided to conduct research on one genre and not all its directions. And in this place, we stopped at the "Pamphlet genre", a genre that made its first buds in the 14th and 15th centuries and managed to enter Uzbek journalism today.

We discussed the history of its emergence, its meaning, purpose, features, unique aspects, genres similar to the pamphlet genre and principles differentiating from them, stages of development, as well as information about its introduction and role in Uzbek journalism.

In the process of studying the types of pamphlet genre, we witnessed that until today, genre types have not been studied. When searching for information about this genre through social networks, we cannot find enough information. We are not satisfied with the information found. Based on the situation, demand and need, we decided to study the types of pamphlet genre. Swift`s pamphlet "The Battle of the Books" (1697), a description of the literary customs of the time, and "The Tale of the Barrel" (1704), an anti-religious satire, made him famous and influential. During this period, Swift`s fame as a journalist and pamphleteer was so great that he astonished his political opponents.

These two works of Swift are among the works that criticize the reality of a certain period of the pamphlet. In addition, we can find a lot of pamphlets created

in this type. In particular, it is difficult to find a person who has not read pamphlets written during the Second World War. For example, in Marat`s pamphlets against Mirabeau and Lafoyet, and Belinsky`s against Shevirev, their reactionary views were harshly criticized. During the Patriotic War and after the war, a number of works in the pamphlet genre were created in the press of the Soviet Union.

The pamphlets of I.Erenborg, L.Leonov, K.Simonov, N.Gribachev can be proof of this opinion. In a discussion held in 1947, the famous satirist D. Zaslavsky noted that the philosophical feuilleton and the philosophical pamphlet were being revived as an artistic journalistic genre. The most vivid examples of pamphlets belong to Ukrainian satirist Yaroslav Galan (1902-1949). In his pamphlets such as "Homeless People", "Death Race", "Get Back", "Johim von...", "Cannibals", "Shadow of Alien Gods", "The Last Days of a Fraud" (evil, murder, genocide, nationalism , is covered with scorching satire. For example, the pamphlet "The Last Days of a Fraud" describes the sad scene in the Führer`s office in April 1945: "The basement of the chancellery now resembled a madhouse. Hitler, blackened with anger, was screaming what is wrong, throwing punches at someone. His suffocated and red-faced body was unrecognizable, madness, fear and terror demanded judgment in the basement. Yaroslav Galan`s pamphlets were sharp and sharp. The death of a talented publicist at the hands of a hired assassin also proves once again how formidable a weapon his pamphlets are for his enemies.

Most of the pamphlets listed above belong to the period pamphlet type. After all, there is a critical laugh directed at the war years and bloodthirsty individuals. These works are considered to be the most relevant articles of their time and have their place in today`s journalism because they reflect people`s pain, past, joy and cry in people`s hearts, bitter pain.

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Formulaic sequence and oral fluency in the target language based on Psycholinguistic

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Hasanov Suhrob**

Abstract: due to the high demand for acquiring languages, there are several hypotheses about the comprehension of a second language. It can be seen that L2 (second language) learners face difficulties mostly in speech success. Whether they have well known of all the lexical and grammar rules of languages acquiring it in general communication daily can be complicated and it unconsciously leads learners to disfluencies during speeches. Moreover, Psychology and linguistics are together can show the major disorders of speech like emotions, and the speed of the brain to comprehend language. Initially, Psycholinguistics is one branch of psychology that analyses figuring out L2 and acquiring it. Therefore, psycholinguistic researchers discovered ways of rectifying disfluencies by creating a learning pace that covered formulaic sequences, conceptualizing, approaches, and acquisition relying upon the psychological needs of language learners.

Keywords: Psychology, linguistics, psycholinguistics, formulaic sequence, Target language, L1/L2, language acquisition, authentic material, Grammatical/phonological encoding

Introduction: In learning and comprehending language psychology and linguistics are connected. They together examine how the brain figures out the language and how it works depending on the sounds, words, sentences, and conversations combine to express and create meaning by the monolingual or bilingual student. Therefore, the area of psychology in a language known as “Psycholinguistic” is mostly about the act of the brain of the individual in using and learning a language. Initially, “The Encyclopedia of Neuroscience” (2004) gave Psycholinguistics or psychology of language – “the discipline that describes and conducts an investigation into the psychological processes that make it possible for humans to be adept and use language. Psycholinguists conduct

research on speech development and language development and how individuals of all ages comprehend and produce language”.^[1]

Moreover, professor of psychology B.J. Mac Whinney also mentioned psycholinguistics in the "International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences" (2001) – “It attempts to evaluate the psychological reality and underpinnings of linguistic rules and processes. It also seeks to link word and sentence processing to the deeper expressive processes of message construction and interpretation. Psycholinguistic experiments typically use reaction-time methodology to examine language comprehension and production as online processes. This research has shown that words and sentences are constructed in an overlapping, incremental fashion. This incrementalism allows us to begin producing words – even before we have formulated the details of later parts of our utterances. To construct formal models of this incremental processing, psycholinguists have used both modular accounts that emphasize back-tracking and neural network accounts that emphasize smooth ongoing interactions between constraints. These models are then further elaborated to account for the process of language acquisition, as well as variations in language processing that arise between different languages.”^[2]

Psycholinguistics theory is a key point of language production, perception, and acquisition, and also it can be vividly shown in 4 main approaches of applied language – reading, listening, writing, and speaking. So, regarding the Psycholinguistic sub-disciplines, educational psycholinguistics is acknowledged as the leading aspect of formal education at language schools, including the role of language in reading teaching proficiency, and improving language ability to express thoughts and feelings as well as fluently comprehending the language.

Willem J. M. Levelt in his article highlighted – “Psycholinguists consider the skilled human language used as a complex information-processing system. They considered accounting for the user's acquisition, production, and comprehension of

language in terms of the various components of this system and their interactions”.[8]

Psycholinguistic research demonstrates language users’ sensitivity to the frequencies of occurrence of a wide range of different linguistic constructions and therefore provides a clear testament to the influence of each usage event, and the processing of its component constructions, on the learner’s system. Usage-based theories of language consequently analyze how frequency and repetition affect, and ultimately bring about, form in language, and how this knowledge affects language comprehension and production.[3]

Scholars of University Reading, Tavakoli, Parvaneh, Campbell, Colin & McCormack, and Joan concluded that speech fluency in the second language (L2) studies commonly refers to ease or automaticity in the learner's speech and is manifested in flow, continuity, and smoothness of speech. Despite this simplistic definition, speech fluency is a complex phenomenon that interacts with other aspects of performance and encompasses a multitude of linguistic, psycholinguistic, and sociolinguistic factors Development of speech fluency over a short time involved in speech formulation and production.[6]

Oral fluency is mainly about the speaker who learns the second language and can speak on several topics with a wide range of lexis and grammatical structures without hesitating during a speech. By the side of psycholinguistics, it may explain that learner`s brain can react to L2 as quickly as possible and comprehend it in reality like the speaker`s L1(first language).

Wilga Rivers identifies two levels of language behavior useful for developing fluent communication. The first is “the level of manipulation” and the second is “the level of expression of personal meaning” (Rivers 34). In the first level, language learners focus on specific grammatical or syntactic features of the language. For example, subject/verb agreement or the order in which adjectives come before nouns are focused on at the level of manipulation. These specific closed systems and fixed relationships in the language are best studied intensively

and with determination by the language learner and need to be stored in the memory for automated use.^[4]

Foundations of language could have begun with indivisible sound segments or units that carried meaning, and over time, language became more complicated, more articulate, and eventually more analyzed and studied by its users. This hypothesis could lead to the idea that indivisible units of meaning are the more basic forms of language and that the grammatical divisions imposed upon language in modern times are a complicated and artificial secondary manifestation of language. Therefore, formulaic sequences could be perceived as, if the above hypothesis is considered, more natural and basic forms of language.^[4]

No child fails to learn a native tongue and it is mainly learned before the age of five. Children are not taught language formally, but they all reach the same level of proficiency in using their native tongue by the time school begins. Therefore, the psycholinguistics approach supports the idea that language acquisition is innately determined and is rewired by birth since both acquisition and improvement in language are biological processes. Acquiring a language requires perception skills, cognition abilities, and other mechanisms that are related to language.^[5]

Initially regarding the study of Willem J. M. Levelt figuring out language is commonly seen in the following main component processes:

Conceptualizing – a conscious planning activity in which a communicative intention guides the construction of one or more messages (conceptual structures that can be formulated in the target language).^[8]

Formulating – generating natural language representations for messages. This involves two processes. First, grammatical encoding maps the message onto some grammatical form; this involves retrieving items from the mental lexicon and arranging them in a syntactic frame. Second, phonological encoding transforms this syntactic structure into a phonetic or articulatory plan.^[8]

Articulating – executing the articulatory plan as a sequence of articulatory gestures. The primary execution modes are oral for spoken languages and manual for sign languages. The main secondary mode is writing.^[8]

And also based on the researchers, the formulaic sequence can be made by learners based on their needs and the difficulties they mostly have in comprehending language. Whenever the L2 learner begins learning a new language they will unconsciously have a slow process in improving fluency owing to the lack of created language atmosphere. As a matter of fact, by psycholinguistics, individuals` brains tend to react rely on the outward atmosphere, which is why language acquisition and approaches are an integral part of a formulaic sequence of comprehension fluency.

Initially, there are some techniques by scholars that are needed to use figure out the language in real-life practice:

Activities to raise awareness of different aspects of fluency

- ❖ listen to a non-native speaker of L2, retelling a picture story, and evaluated the speaker's fluency in terms of speed, pausing, and repair measures.^[6]
- ❖ work with the transcript of the picture story retelling and identified where fluency had broken down.^[6]
- ❖ Using authentic materials for extended listening and reading activities and conceptualizing the materials (e.g. listening to podcasts of native speakers and drawing individual conclusions about them orally)

Strategies that can be used for improving fluency

- ❖ using lexical fillers (e.g. well) and longer lexical chunks (e.g. let me think) and practicing them in conversations.^[6]
- ❖ avoiding repetitions and hesitations in conversations where possible.^[6]

Opportunities for practicing fluency

- ❖ retelling the picture story that they had listened to in exercise at home: retelling another picture story and recording their performance; listening to one's

performance to identify fluency problems; recording their performance of the same task again.^[6]

In task-based language learning research, one approach to defining successful L2 performance is to characterize it as complex, both syntactically and lexically, accurate and fluent. Although the focus of the current study is on the development of fluency, it seems essential to examine learners' performance in full and to investigate the inter-relationship between different aspects of performance.^[6]

Psycholinguistic evidence strongly suggests that we operate under tight processing restrictions when handling linguistic material. If this is so, then our tendency to use formulaic language might be the result of expediency – that is, it makes processing shortcuts possible. Conceptualizing a 'processing shortcut' is highly contingent on how to model psycholinguistic knowledge. However, most psycholinguists would agree that the pressure point relates to assembly rather than storage. In other words, the brain seems very able to accommodate as many lexical units as we want to store, but we are very easily thrown off course when formulating an utterance if we try to do too many things at once.^[7]

Conclusion: The researchers' conclusions and findings about figuring out language in communication without disfluencies are the results of making an appropriate language atmosphere and training the brain to acquire the language. Because of long-term studies on developing communicative fluency by scholars, they discover making formulaic sequences by conceptualizing and using L2 in everyday classes is the major solution to disfluencies.

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Аксиологический потенциал социального уровня ценностей

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В статье рассматривается понятие аксиологического потенциала личности на социальном уровне ценностей; выявляются и описываются паремиологические единицы, которые обладают аксиологическим потенциалом; даются функциональные характеристики аксиологического потенциала личности.

Ключевые слова: социальный уровень ценностей, аксиологический потенциал, пословицы и поговорки, функциональные характеристики, речевые взаимодействия.

А.В. Кунин интерпретирует пословицы как афористически сжатые изречения с назидательным смыслом и ритмически организованной формой [1, 432]. Пословицы – это жемчужины житейской мудрости, духовное богатство и культурное наследие народа, проверенное на многовековом опыте [4, 98].

Антропоцентрические пословицы английского и русского языков отражают в себе посредством образов мировосприятие и мировоззрение народа, ибо, как пишет Г.А. Багаутдинова, «образы являются отражением способа мировидения и могут быть определены в рамках культурных кодов» [1, 25].

Оценочное значение в антропоцентрических пословицах может быть заложено уже в самой номинации человека. Следует отметить, что система наименований человека в исследуемых пословицах английского и русского языков очень красочна и многогранна, как красочен и многогранен сам человек. Инвариантной формой наименования человека в антропоцентрических пословицах выступают в английском языке слово human (people), а в русском языке – человек (люди).

Существующее многообразие наименований человека в антропоцентрических пословицах исследуемых языков предопределяется

тем, что в них представлена характеристика человека с разных ракурсов, например, с точки зрения его пола, возраста, социального положения, умственных способностей, черт характера и т.п.

Среди наименований человека в анализируемых пословицах особо выделяются группы, в которых номинация человека производится на основе рода деятельности, качеств характера, особенностей поведения и поступков.

В антропоцентрических пословицах английского и русского языков выделяется ряд наименований, которые описывают человека по роду его деятельности. Примечательно, что эта группа содержит указания как на названия современных и устаревших ремесел и профессий, так и на чин, статусное положение, а также наличие/отсутствие работы, занятость/безделие, пристрастия человека.

Особо отмечаются в антропоцентрических пословицах супружеские связи, при этом учитываются брачные/любовные отношения, наличие/отсутствие детей, женат/неженат, отмечается, если одного из супругов нет в живых.

Большое количество пословиц указывает на важную роль женщины в семье, особенно в ведении домашнего хозяйства: *A woman's work is never done* – У женщин работе по дому конца не бывает; *A woman's place is in the home* – Место женщины – дом. Согласно пословицам, для женщины важно быть хорошей хозяйкой: *All married women are not wives* – Не все замужние женщины – жены. Жена в обеих языковых культурах должна готовить еду для мужа, который не терпит голода: *A hungry belly has no ears* – У голодного брюха нет уха, соловья баснями не кормят. Именно хорошими кулинарными способностями женщина может завоевать любовь мужчины: *The way to a man's heart is through his stomach.* – Путь к сердцу мужчины лежит через его желудок.

Согласно английской и русской паремиологии мужчина – этого глава семьи, лидер: *It's a man's world* – Мир принадлежит мужчине. В современной

английской семье права жены приобретают все большую значимость: Man is the head, but woman turns it. – Мужчина – голова, а женщина – шея (куда захочет повернет). В данных пословицах муж остается главой семьи, его доминирующее положение никак не уменьшается, однако делается акцент на большое влияние жены на принятие им решений.

Номинация человека в антропоцентрических пословицах исследуемых языков может выражать характеристику социального положения и взаимоотношений человека с другими членами общества.

В английских паремиях ярко отражается социальное положение людей и демонстрируется преимущество богатых над бедными: One man may steal a horse while another may not look over a hedge – Что можно одному, нельзя другому; A thief passes for a gentleman when stealing has made him rich – вор сходит за джентльмена, когда становится богатым.

При социальной характеристике человека основанием для номинации служат такие показатели, как дружба, соседство, работа, в особенности бизнес, вероисповедание и др. Еще одним параметром номинации человека в анализируемых пословицах является финансовое состояние человека.

В целом, наименования человека по финансовому его состоянию, с одной стороны, отражают наличие/отсутствие денежного капитала, т.е. бедность или богатость, с другой стороны свидетельствуют о том, что является мерилем благосостояния, богатства человека и как оно оценивается [4, 15].

В качестве немаловажного параметра оценки человека в антропоцентрических пословицах английского и русского языков следует рассматривать социальное положение. В целом, социальный уровень ценностей в антропоцентрических пословицах английского и русского языков представлен аксиологическими пословичными диадами типа «Семья – Одиночество», «Дети – Бездетность», «Коллектив – Индивидуум», «Альтруизм – Эгоизм» и др. Например:

«Семья – Одиночество»: Брат брата не выдаст. В дружной семье и в холод тепло. В своей семье всяк сам большой.

«Дети – Бездетность»: В хорошей семье хорошие дети растут. Дети родителям не судьи. Для внука дедушка – ум, а бабушка – душа. Дочерьми красуются, сыновьями в почете живут [3, 21].

В английских и русских пословицах дети сравниваются с родителями и похожи на них: Like father, like son – Каков отец, таков и сын [2, с. 314] или Like mother, like daughter – Какова мать, такова и дочь [2, с. 630].

Некоторые пословицы противоположно характеризуют родителей и их детей: Many a good father has (hath) but a bad son – В семье не без урода; Miserly father makes a prodigal son – У отца-скряги сын может оказаться мотом.

Родители часто не замечают недостатки своих детей и хвалят их положительные качества: Every mother thinks her own gosling a swan. Дите хоть и криво, а отцу-матери отцу-матери диво.

«Коллектив – Индивидуум»: без актива нет коллектива. Вместе тесно, а розно тошно. Одной рукой и узла не завяжешь. Один палец не кулак. Один в поле не воин.

«Альтруизм – Эгоизм»: не искал бы в селе, а искал бы в себе. Мне хоть весь свет гори, только бы я жив был. В своей сермяжке никому не тяжело. Всякому своя слеза солона.

Доминирующее количество пословиц любого языка связано с описанием внешних и личностных характеристик человека, а также оценками общества к ним. Из поколения в поколения пословицы передают антропоцентрическую информацию, выявляя детальные особенности и «тонкости» человеческой природы во взаимоотношении с обществом.

Действительно, посредством пословиц в сознании человека формируются яркие и неповторимые человеческие образы, раскрываются разнообразные оценки по отношению к окружающему миру и передаются

эмоции и переживания людей во взаимоотношениях друг с другом. Будучи творением народа, но фиксируясь в системе языка, пословицы отражают национальную самобытность или, выражаясь иначе, национальный дух языка.

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А.Чўлпон шеърий асарларида қўлланган антитезанинг структуравий- семантик хусусиятлари

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Аннотация

Бизга маълумки, ҳар қандай стилистик усул бадиий матнда, айнан шеъриятда қўлланганда ҳам ўзига хос морфологик, синтактик ва семантик хусусиятларни намоён қилади. Антитезанинг поэтик асарларда морфологик хусусиятлари шундан иборатки, улар матн таркибида келганда от, сифат, феъл, равиш, сифатдош, равишдош ва ҳатто боғловчилар вазифасида ҳам қўлланиши кўзга ташланади.

Калит сўзлар: стилистик усул, Антитеза, матн, А.Чўлпон, шеърий матн, метафора, метонимия

Тадқиқот ишимизнинг мазкур фаслида А.Чўлпоннинг шеърий асарларида антитезанинг структуравий-семантик хусусиятлари борасида сўз юритамиз.

Мен қочмадим! Нега мени “қочди” деб,

Йўқға бунча шовқун-сурон қилдингиз?

Кучоғини “ўзлиг” ига очди деб,

Оқ исмимга қора занжир илдингиз?

Бу жараёнда А.Чўлпон қаламига мансуб бир қатор шеърлар ва диссертациянинг расмийлаштириш жиҳатидан унинг ҳажмидан келиб чиқиб, шеърларнинг айрим парчаларини таҳлилини амалга оширдик. Кўм-кўк экан, сарғайдилар япроқлар – Оғрик, мағлуб, тутқун Шарқнинг юзидек. Бўронларнинг кўзлари, ким ўйноқлар, Голиб Ғарбнинг қонга тўлган кўзидек. А.Чўлпоннинг ушбу шеърий матнида антитеза ҳодисаси мағлуб Шарқ ва голиб Ғарб бирикмалари орқали ифодаланган. Матнда иккинчи шеърий қатордаги “мағлуб, тутқин Шарқ” бирикмаси от+от+от модели асосида ясалган. Голиб Ғарб бирикмаси от+от кўринишида сўз бирикмасини ҳосил

қиган. “Мағлуб, тутқин Шарқ” ва “Ғолиб Ғарб” бирикмалари синтактик жиҳатдан тобе ҳоким усули орқали ясалган. Мазкур шеърӣ парчада антитеза ҳосил қилган сўз ва сўз бирикмасида метонимия стилистик усули қўлланмоқда. Мағлуб Шарқда метонимия стилистик усули қўлланган бўлиб, Шарқ сўзи орқали “Шарқ ҳалқи” назарда тутилмоқда. “Мағлуб шарқ” га қарама- қарши ифода бу “Ғолиб Ғарб” бўлиб, унда ҳам метонимия стилистик усули қўлланган. Бу шеърӣ тўртликда қўлланган антитезанинг антонимиядан фарқи унда зидланишни билдирувчи “Ғолиб” ва “мағлуб” сўзлари якка сўз вазифасида қўлланмайди.

Бу ерда ушбу сўзларни Шарқ ва Ғарб сўзларига қўшиш орқали ва унда метонимик маъно ҳосил қилиш орқали сўз бирикмаси тарзида қўлланган. Шу орқали ушбу сатрдаги қарама-қарши ифодалар антитезани ҳосил қилган. Мен қочмадим! Нега мени “қочди” деб, Йўқға бунча шовқун-сурон қилдингиз? Қучоғини “ўзлик” ига очди деб, Оқ исмига қора занжир илдингиз? “Мен қочмадим! Нега мени “қочди” деб” ҳада “Йўқға бунча шовқунсурон қилдингиз?” мисраларда қочмади ва қочди сўзларидан бирига -ма а бўлишсизлик қўшимчаси қўшилиши орқали ясаиб, антонимик бирликни ҳосил қилмоқжа. Улар синтактик жиҳатдан гаплар таркибида кириб, антитеза стилистик усулини ҳосил қилган. Ушбу бирликлар гаплар таркибида кесим вазифасини бажармоқда. “-Ма” инкор феълнинг бўлишсиз шарти кўрсаткич сифатида ажратиладиган урғусиз аффиксдир. Бу бўлишсизлик феъли инкор, тақиқлаш, огоҳлантириш, тахмин каби маъноларни англатади: бормади, ёзмади, кўрмади, ўқимади; тегма, яқинлашма каби. Шоир ушбу мисрада Оқ исм ва қора занжир сўз бирикмаларини қўллаш орқали антитеза ҳодисасини ифодалаб берган. Ушбу бирикмалар синтактик жиҳатдан тобе ҳоким муносабати орқали ясалган. Оқ ва қора бир-бирига антоним сўзлар бўлиб, исм ва занжир сўзлари қўшилиши орқали сўз бирикмаси ясаиб, антитезани ҳосил қилмоқда. Ушбу мисрадаги Оқ исм бирикмаси сифат + от шаклида намоён бўлган. Қора занжир бирикмаси ҳам сифат + от шаклида ясалган.

Синтактик жиҳатдан оқ ва қора сўзлари исм ва занжир сўзларини аниқловчиси бўлиб келмоқда. Масалон оқ йўл бирикмаси йўлни бехатар, бешкаст бўлиши учун яхши ниятда айтиладиган ибора ҳисобланади. Оқ билак кўлини совуқ сувга урмайдиган, фақат ўзига оро берадиган (аёл ҳақида), Оқ-қорани таниган – Оқдан қорани (ёки оқ-қорани) ажратмоқ – ёмон билан яхшини, дўст билан душманни, фойда билан зиённи фарқламоқ, тушунмоқ. Кўзининг оқу қораси. “Манглайи оқ бўлсин” яхшилик ниятида тиланган олқиш, дуо, Оқ ювиб, оқ тарамоқ – авайламоқ, асрамоқ. Оқ ўрамоқ этнографик маъно – қиз билан йигитни унаштиришга розилик белгиси, маросими, ҳисобланади. Қора занжир метафора бирикмаси орқали яхши, пок исмга ёмон номни орттириш, ҳаётини барбод қилиш маъноси ифодаланмоқда. Қора сўзи эса кўпинча салбий маънони ифодалаб келган. Масалан қора хат ўлим маъносида, қора либос аъза маъносида ишлатилади.

Зулм олдида ҳар бир нарса,

Эҳтимол, ки бўйнин эгар.

Агар зулм авжга келса,

Кўк боши-да ерга тегар.

Мазкур шеърӣ парчада А.Чўлпон кўк боши-да ерга тегар мисрасида кўк ва ер антонимик сўзларидан фойдаланиб, синтактик жиҳатдан матн таркибида келиб антитеза стилистик услубини ҳосил қилмоқда. Ушбу парча таркибидаги кўк сўзи тобе ва ҳоким муносабатлари орқали боғланган бўлиб “кўк” сўзида ифодаланмаган бўлса ҳам қаратқич келишигининг қўшимчаси “–нинг” маъно жиҳатдан мавжуддир. Шунинг учун бу боғланиш тури мослашув йўли билан ҳосил қилинган сўз бирикмаси дейилади. Синтактик жиҳатдан гап бўлақларига ажратилганида “кўк” сўзи қаратқичли аниқловчи ҳисобланади. Кўк сўзи аслида рангга нисбатан қўлланилиб тиниқ осмон рангидаги; мовий, зангори маъносини билдиради. Кўк сўзи қуйидаги лексик маъноларни ҳам билдириб келади:

1) Ер устида гумбаз шаклида кўриниб турадиган ҳаво қатлами; осмон;

2) Ўсаётган ўт-ўсимлик, ўт-ўлан; майса, кўкат.

Шоир ушбу парчада кўк сўздан осмон маъносини ифодалаш учун фойдаланган. Ўзбек халқида кўк сўзи билан бошланувчи бир қатор иборалар ҳам мавжуд: Боши кўкка етди - жуда мамнун бўлмоқ, хурсанд бўлмоқ, Еру кўкка ишонмаслик-ўта даражада эҳтиётламоқ, Кулини кўкка совурмоқ бирор нарсага нисбатан бекорга сарфламоқ, Кўкка кўтармоқ - тавсифини жуда оширмоқ, ўта мақтамоқ. Тутуни кўкка чиқмоқ - ўта даражада хафа бўлмоқ, хуноб бўлмоқ маъноларини билдириб келади. Мазкур шеърий қаторда кўк сўзига қарама-қарши маънода қўлланган ер сўзи ҳам тобе ва ҳоким муносабатлари орқали боғланган. Бу боғланиш тури бошқарув йўли билан ҳосил қилинган сўз бирикмаси дейилади. Синтактик жиҳатдан гап бўлакларига ажратилганида “ер” сўзи ўрин ҳоли вазифасида келмоқда.

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Т.Элиот шеърӣ асарларида қўлланган антитезанинг структуравий- семантик хусусиятлари

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Аннотация

Т.С.Элиотнинг илк ижодида замон ва маконнинг бадиий вазифалари ўрганилган. Т.С.Элиот инглиз-америка модернизмнинг энг кўзга кўринган намояндаларидан бири бўлиб, у бошқа шоирлардан ўзининг фалсафийэстетик концепсиясини рўёбга чиқарган ҳолда бадиий макон ва замон яратишга алоҳида ёндашуви билан ажралиб туради. Махсус хронотоп яратиш учун Т.С.Элиот турли хил бадиий усуллардан фойдаланади. Шоирнинг дастлабки ижодида уларнинг салмоғи кўп, чунки Элиот фақат ўз услубини аниқлайди, ўз йўналишини излайди.

Калит сўзлар: стилистик усул, Антитеза, матн, Т.С.Элиот, шеърӣ матн, метафора, метонимия

Т.Элиот ижодида макон ва замон образлари марказий ўрин тутди. Шоир мумтоз асарларга тақлид қилишдан аста-секин ўз услубига ўтиб, мифологик онгга хос образлар тизимига мос келадиган қарама-қаршиликлар устида бадиий образлар тизимини қуради. Тасвирлар бир хил бўлгунга қадар турли даражаларда бир-бирига қарама-қарши бўлади. Шу билан бирга, Т.Элиотнинг макон ва вақт тасвирлари ўзига қарама-қаршидир чунки улар универсал категориялардир. Тадқиқот ишимизда мазкур бобнинг биринчи фаслида А.Чўлпон ва Т. Элиот шеърӣ асарларида қўлланган стилистик усулларни таҳлил қилган бўлсак, кейинги фаслларда уларнинг шеърӣ асарларида антитеза қўлланишининг структуравий-семантик хусусиятлари борасида сўз юритишни мақсад қилган эдик. Шу нуқтаи назардан ишимизнинг мазкур фаслида Т.Элиот шеърӣятида қўлланилган антитезанинг структуравийсемантик хусусиятлари борасида сўз юритамиз. Шоир ўз шеърларида антитезадан жуда самарали фойдаланиб, ҳаётдаги турли

ижтимоий вақт ва макон концептларининг ўзаро контрастлаш, улардаги воқеликни қарама-қарши маъноларини ифодалашни мақсад қилинган. Т.Элиот лексик қарама-қаршиликларни яратишда баъзан фалсафий категория сифатида бир хил мақомдаги чексизликни ифодаловчи сўзлардан, жумладан “коинот”, “космос”, “дунё” кабилардан, кундалик маконни ифодалаш учун эса “хона”, “уй”, “кўча” лексик бирликларидан фойдаланган. Унинг шеърий асарларида баъзан макон ва замон ижтимоий қонун-қоидалар, анъаналар ва меъёрлар асосида маълум маънога эга бўлган бир лексема ёки образлар гуруҳи орқали ифодаланиши мумкин.

In my beginning is my end. In succession
Houses rise and fall, crumble, are extended,
Are removed, destroyed, restored, or in their place
Is an open field, or a factory, or a by-pass.

Ушбу шеърий парчада берилган *beginning* va *end* сўзлари бир-бирига антоним сўзлар бўлиб, гап таркибида антитеза стилистик воситасини ҳосил қилмоқда. “*Beginning*” сўзи морфологик жиҳатдан феъл сўз туркумининг шакли ҳисобланган ҳаракат номи ҳисобланиб, инглиз тилида феъл сўз туркумининг герундий шаклига тўғри келади. Синтактик жиҳатдан эса “*beginning*” сўзи эга вазифасини бажариб келмоқда. Изоҳли луғатларда мазкур сўзнинг *dawn*-тонг, *birth*-туғилиш, *inception*-ташқил этиш, *conception* тушунча, *origination*-келиб чиқиш, *genesis*-дунёга келиш каби маънолари мавжуд. Мазкур парчада “*beginning*” сўзига қарама-қарши маънода қўлланган “*end*” сўзи морфологик жиҳатдан от сўз туркумига мансуб. Инглиз тилида ҳам ушбу сўз от сўз туркуми ҳисобланади. Синтактик жиҳатдан эса “*end*” сўзи инглиз тилида ҳам ўзбек тилида ҳам от кесим вазифасида қўлланилмоқда. Мазкур сўзнинг *conclusion*-яқунлаш, *termination*-охир, *ending*-тугатиш, *finish*-тушамок, *close*-итниҳо маънори мавжуд. Шеърий матннинг биринчи қаторида *beginning* va *end* сўзлари ўзаро антоним ҳосил қилиб, “*beginning*” сўзининг “*birth*-туғилиш”, яъни дунёга келиш маъноси

“end” сўзининг “close-итниҳо” маъносига қарама-қарши қўлланиб, матн таркибида антитеза стилистик услини юзага келтирмоқда.

Юқоридаги шеърий парчанинг иккинчи қаторида “Houses rise and fall, crumble, are extended” матнидаги “rise-кўтарилиши” ва “fall-пастлаш” сўзлари ўзаро антоним бўлиб, матнда антитеза стилистик воситасини ҳосил қилмоқда. Морфологик жиҳатдан ушбу сўзлар сифат сўз туркумига тегишли. Синтактик жиҳатдан эса аниқловчи гап бўлаги вазифасида келмоқда “Rise” сўзи stand up-ўрнидан турмоқ, get up-уйқудан турмоқ, jump up-сакрамоқ, increase-ўсмоқ, hike-пиёда сайр қилмоқ, advance-олдинга ҳаракат қилиш, growth-ўсиш, leap-сакраш, upsurge-кўтарилиш, upswing-тўсатдан кўтарилиш каби маъноларга эга. “Fall” сўзи ҳам морфологик жиҳатдан сифат сўз туркумига доир бўлиб, синтактик жиҳатдан аниқловчи вазифасида келмоқда. “Fall” сўзи drop down-тушмоқ, пасаймоқ, drop-тушиш, пасайиш, plummet кескин тушиш, descend-тушмоқ, come down-пастга келмоқ, go down-пастга тушмоқ, fall down-пастламоқ, fall over-йиқилиб тушмоқ, tumble-йиқилмоқ, trip-қоқилмоқ, spill-тўкмоқ, topple-қуламоқ, stumble-қоқилмоқ, қалинмоқ, slip тоймоқ, collapse- қуламоқ, бузилмоқ каби маъноларда қўлланади. Мазкур матнда “rise” сўзининг “upsurge-кўтарилиш” маъноси “fall” сўзининг “collapse-бузилмоқ” маъносига нисбатан қарама-қарши маъно ҳосил қилмоқда. Шунинг натижасида уларнинг ушбу маънолари матнда антитеза стилистик усулини юзага келишига сабаб бўлмоқда. Ушбу шеърий парчада юқорида таъкидланганлардан ташқари, destroyed ва restored каби сўзлар матнда қўлланиб, булар бир-бирига нисбатан антоним сўзлар ҳисобланади ва улар матнда антитеза стилистик воситаси бўлиб келмоқда. Матнда “destroyed” сўзи морфологик жиҳатдан феъл сўз туркумига мансуб бўлиб, феълнинг ўткан замон шакли ҳисобланади. Синтактик жиҳатдан мантда сифатдош вазифасида келмоқда. Изоҳли луғатларда “Destroy” сўзининг demolish-вайрон қилмоқ, knock down синдириш, қулатиш, пастга тушириш, pull down-пастга тортмоқ, tear down-парчаламоқ, level-босқич, даража,

annihilate-йўқ қилиш, бекор қилиш, wipe out-ювиб юбориш, obliterate-йўқ қилиш, ўчириш каби лексик маъноларда қўлланади. Restored сўзи ҳам морфологик жиҳатдан феъл сўз туркумига мансуб бўлиб, феълнинг ўткан замон шакли ҳисобланади ва синтактик жиҳатдан сифатдош вазифасида келмоқда. Ушбу сўзнинг reinstate-қайта тиклаш, put back-орқага қўймоқ, replace-қайта жойлаштирмақ, bring back қайтариб олиб келмоқ, reinstitute-қайта тиклаш, reimpose-қайта юкламоқ, repair- қайта таъмирламоқ, fix-ўрнатмоқ, mend-ямамоқ, refurbish-тамирламоқ, recondition-тузатмоқ, rehabilitate- соғлиғини тикламоқ маънолари мавжуд. Мазкур шеърий парчада “destroy” сўзининг “demolish-vayron qilmoq” маъноси “restore” сўзининг “reinstitute-қайта тиклаш” маънолари ўзаро қарама-қаршиликни ифодалаб, антитеза стилистик усулини ҳосил қилмоқда. Юқоридаги шеърий парчада антитезани қўлланишининг структуравий-семантик хусусиятларини ўрганиш жараёнида шу нарса маълум бўлдики, Т.Элиот антитезадан турли маконларни тавсифлашда кенг фойдаланган. Бу эса унинг шеъриятини бадиий-эстетик жиҳатдан бойитган.

Демак, Т.Элиотнинг шеърий асарларида қўлланилган антитезаларнинг структуравий-семантик хусусиятларини таҳлил қилар эканмиз, шоирнинг шеърий матнларида антитеза антоним асосига қурилагни, антонимик сўзлар морфологик жиҳатдан от, сифат, сифатдошга тегишли эканлиги, синтактик жиҳатдан эса сўз бирикмаси ва гап таркибида қўлланиши, семантик жиҳатдан эса лексик бирликларнинг полисемантик маънолигига эътибор қаратган ҳолда асосан денотатив маънолардан фойдаланилганлигига гувоҳ бўлдик.

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The influence of literature on the formation of the student's personality

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Key words: pupil, national-moral values, people, epics, personality, literature

The role of educational institutions in the formation of the student's personality has increased not only in our country, but also on a global scale in the last century. From this point of view, the determination of the specific content of each of the educational subjects for the state standards is not accidental. Formation of national and international outlook of students has been defined as one of the main directions of that content in the subject of literature. The process of assimilation of international values and formation of worldview in students can also be called the process of formation of planetary thinking in them.

Although the rapid development of scientific and technical progress leads to high achievements and progressive changes in real life, certain tendencies of this process to the cultural development of society and moral and spiritual values are also evident. At such a time, in the field of education of the young generation in the national context, returning to the roots, national self-awareness, moral and spiritual values are of great importance. Protecting the historically formed high moral and spiritual values of the people and directing the cultural development of the society as a whole is regulated both by the policy implemented by the state and by the cultural-intellectual and scientific-pedagogical principles put forward by the social sphere.

Moral and spiritual values, which are the main indicators of the people's existence, are its most valuable wealth. Every nation has a system of national and moral values. These national and moral values are our history, language, religion, traditions, mentality, national characteristics, culture, literature and art. Both the educational system and the cultural and spiritual life of young people should create such an environment that the ability of this environment to react to external influences is strong. That is, there should be a protective area between the person and the external influence. When there are gaps in the protective field between a

person and the cultural-spiritual environment, foreign influences affect memory. At this time, those with a low level of outlook, weak-willed, and those far from moral and spiritual values easily succumb to these influences. In this regard, the work carried out in the direction of raising the moral and spiritual development of the young generation, the level of national self-awareness, and voluntary abilities should be carried out in a systematic manner.

The role of educational institutions in the formation of the student's personality has increased not only in our country, but also on a global scale in the last century. From this point of view, the determination of the specific content of each of the educational subjects for the state standards is not accidental. Formation of national and international outlook of students has been defined as one of the main directions of that content in the subject of literature. The process of assimilation of international values and formation of worldview in students can also be called the process of formation of planetary thinking in them.

In addition to the acquisition of knowledge and skills during the educational activities of the students, the skills of thinking, analyzing, comparing, and making independent decisions are also formed. These cognitive processes encourage students to mature and become perfect human beings. Independent reasoning plays an important role in the formation of "student identity".

Cultivation of students' sense of attachment to the motherland, nation, country, development of their intellectual level, the process of more orderly and systematic formation of cognitive-cognitive and communicative communication skills is directly related to the form and content of instruction and promotion from Literary Examples.

Each work studied can be personalized with a new interesting aspect. Students express their opinions and judgments independently, at the same time in the direction directed by the teacher, compare with the opinions of their peers and finally acquire the ability to make independent decisions.

Creativity should be given ample space in the teaching process. Divide the work into parts, determine the title, put yourself in the place of the hero in the story, change the events, express the attitude of the characters, write an essay, etc. such qualities express the student's creative qualities.

Starting from oral folk literature, students who study examples of literature created until today can distinguish bad from good, straight from crooked. The legend "Mother Deer" taught in the 5th grade teaches students to love nature, and the fairy tale "Yetim Ibrahim" teaches that ingenuity and reason win. It is a great responsibility, duty and honor for every teacher to instill "Love of the Motherland" in young students. Similarly, in the epics "Kitabi Dada-Gorgud" and "Koroglu", our students are instilled with feelings of patriotism, love for the land, motherland, and mother.

While studying proverbs and issues, the student can analyze and compare contrasts between truth and lies, greed and kindness, love and hate. He is able to distinguish the negative and positive qualities of a person. Independently expresses a personal attitude to the image. In the debates, he becomes the representative of the character. It enhances and defends the characteristic features of images. This makes the teacher very happy. In other words, topics stimulate discussions around new problems.

Comparing and analyzing the main examples of our modern literature, analyzing and teaching them within the framework of the literature course of general schools can bring new successes to the Azerbaijani school. Of course, the teaching of literary examples should be treated with a certain sensitivity, the national and moral values that the student carries and the local psychological environment must be taken into account during the lesson. "The literature course has great opportunities to shape the student's personality, intellectual world and aesthetic taste. Pupils acquire an active life position by understanding and evaluating the complex events and life realities that are reflected in the artistic work. In this sense, literature classes should be treated as life and spirituality

classes, as a kind of cognitive activity. Fiction is a special form of spiritual communication. The student reader, reading a perfect example of art, reflects on the moral and aesthetic issues raised there, and comments on the hero's fate, the artist's position, becomes the interviewer of the powerful artist, is spiritually enriched by studying his ideas and thoughts, and allows school children to evaluate their activities, actions and behavior from moral and aesthetic norms.

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PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCE

Processes of urbanization development in eastern nations.

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Annotation. In this article, the origin of the ancient Chinese civilization is more than 6 thousand years, experts call it "the oldest cultural center in the world", the source of the existence of Hong Kong. avv. Issues such as the fact that 100 million farmers are enough to provide the Chinese population with agricultural products, that the price of housing in Hong Kong is considered the highest in the world, and that the city is one of the leaders in the construction of high-rise buildings will be revealed.

Keywords. Business environment, foreign tourists, city infrastructure, shops, museums, cinemas, restaurants, housing speculation, housing, housing.

According to the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, which studies socio-economic and social issues of countries and publishes ratings of urbanization development, the Eastern countries of Hong Kong (100.0%), Singapore (100%) are at the highest level of urbanization.), Kuwait (100 %), Nauru (100 %), Qatar (99.2 %), United Arab Emirates (86.8 %), Oman (85.4 %), Saudi Arabia (84.1 %). After them come Western countries. This fact alone encourages us to study the processes of urbanization development in the Eastern nations, to obtain the necessary experiences, conclusions and recommendations from them. Hong Kong is a special administrative region, a city of China. It was once a British colony. It is because of this factor that Hong Kong has skyscrapers that combine the influence of the East (China) and the West (England), in terms of appearance, reminiscent of high-rise Manhattan (USA) and the City of London (England). In 1997, Hong Kong was transferred to Chinese jurisdiction. The population, as of 2020, is 7.482 million people. 98% of them are Chinese. The ancient Chinese civilization was more than 6,000 years old, which is why experts call it "the oldest center of culture in the world." The source of Hong Kong's existence is land. avv. It dates back to 1,000 years. Although it is an island, it was

influenced by Chinese civilization. China has little arable land, but farming is considered the main social activity. Even the troops were busy planting and harvesting wheat. In recent years, the Chinese government has paid great attention to urbanization development, and in this regard, special state programs and strategies have been adopted. According to them, more than 300 million people were moved from rural to urban areas in the next 20 years. This is a rare event in world history. But still 0.5 billion people live in rural areas. However, 100 million farmers are enough to provide the Chinese population with agricultural products. Housing prices in Hong Kong are the highest in the world. The city is one of the leaders in the construction of high-rise buildings. The Lantau Vision Tomorrow program was launched in 2018, taking into account the business environment, the organization of services for the flow of foreign tourists, the renewal and modernization of the city's infrastructure, and the growing demands of the population for accommodation. According to it, 260,000 residences will be built on 1,000 hectares of land. Some experts call it an environmentally dangerous project. They prefer to use underground facilities, basements. According to them, such experiences exist in Canada and Finland. For example, 10 million square meters in Helsinki. m. lik underground town was built. Large centers, trading centers, heat production and transmission enterprises were built there. In Montreal, towns were built under the streets, where shops serving the population, museums, cinemas, and restaurants were placed. They work day and night⁹. Such experiments gave rise to the idea of creating "smart cities" (Future Cities Catapult). True, there is also the idea and social movement of "Slow Cities" that supports the slow and steady growth of the city. Today, 260 cities of the world are members of it, some of them are from the East (South Korea and India). Administrative measures are not enough to ensure the migration of the population to the cities, first of all, it is necessary to teach people to live in the urban environment with limited mobility, especially in small apartments, build affordable housing, build new quarters,

⁹Look: plus one. rbk. ru / society / urban.

massifs, and establish mortgage loans. The Chinese government began to implement these measures from 2010 to 2011, attracting the private sector to build housing, activating the mortgage credit system, creating facilities for foreign investors, thereby preventing housing speculation and deliberately raising housing prices. .Since 2014, housing prices in cities have started to decrease. As a result, even an ordinary farmer could get a house in the city and engage in activities according to his interest. He used to get a salary of around 200 dollars, but in the conditions of the city, this figure has increased three to four times, even more. Today, the number of millionaires (in US dollars) in China has reached 1 million people, more than 10 million people live in the city and serve in the field of entrepreneurship, business and international trade. The country is expected to experience a "baby boom", that is, young babies, as it happened in the USA in the 1950s and 1960s. Especially after the abolition of the one-child policy, the country`s population growth is natural (Same source. By Long Jing Capital). The sector providing socio-cultural services to the population is supported by various preferences and benefits. For example, kindergartens, schools and educational centers are exempt from taxes for two years, and pay half of the municipal and other taxes imposed for another two years. Small-scale cultural and household institutions, temporary constructions built in places convenient for the population, especially around houses, do not require special permission, they can be built by the decision of the local population, household assembly. Even household sectors can allocate funds from their own account to such cultural-household and educational institutions. In Hong Kong, special fitness lanes and fields have been established for children and the elderly, and they are staffed by fitness, physical culture, and sports instructors. In the morning, people can be seen doing physical education on these corridors and squares.

STATE AND LAW

O`zbekiston va Salvadora elektron pullar.

Jahongir Husainov

Yuqori Chirchiq tuman adliya bo`limi

Davlat xizmatlari markazi direktori

Elektron pullarga doir qonunchilikni tushuntirishdan oldin avvalo, elektron pul nimaligini tushunib olish zarur. Elektron pul bu – bank kartamizdagi pullardir. Biz naqd pulimizni elektron pulga, elektron pulni naqd pulga osongina almashtirish mumkin bo`lgan zamonda yashayapmiz. Markaziy bank ma`lumotlariga ko`ra,¹⁰ O`zbekistonda 2022-yilning aprel oyiga kelib (bular regulyator tomonidan taqdim etilgan oxirgi ma`lumotlar) bank kartalarining soni 32 milliondan, muomaladagi bank kartalarining soni esa 28 milliondan ziyodni tashkil qiladi. Bu shuni anglatadi-ki, voyaga yetgan aholining barchasida bank kartasi mavjud. Shu bilan birga, Respublika hududidagi bankomatlar va infokiosklar soni 13 381tani tashkil qiladi. Bank kartalari va bankomatlarga oid raqamlar O`zbekistonda aholi turmush tarzi davomida doimiy elektron pullar bilan o`zaro munosabatga kirishini ko`rsatadi. Shuningdek, respublikada stipendiyalar, nafaqalar, ish haqlari, pensiyalar, yordam pullari ham bank kartalariga tushirib beriladi. Savdo-sotiq, ta`lim, tibbiyot kabi ijtimoiy xizmatlar, maishiy xizmatlar ko`rsatishda ham elektron pullarni miqyosi zalvorli. Elektron pullar tizimisiz mamlakat iqtisodiyotini tasavvur qilish qiyin. Shunday ekan. elektron pullarning huquqiy maqomini bilish ham elektron pullar bilan bog`liq munosabatlarning huquqiy tartibga solinishida muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Bugungi kunda Salvadorning elektron pul bozori o`sib bormoqda. Voyaga yetganlarning 16 foizi ushbu xizmatdan foydalangan va elektron pulning nomoddiyligi va platforma xavfsizligi haqidagi ba`zi xavotirlarga qaramay, foydalanuvchilar umuman xizmatdan, tranzaksiyalar tezligidan mamnun.¹¹

¹⁰ <https://t.me/centralbankuzbekistan/5342>

¹¹ https://www.afi-global.org/sites/default/files/publications/2017-09/AFI_FILAC_CS_EI%20Salvador_AW_digital.pdf

Elektron pul, ayniqsa, qishloq aholisi uchun uzoq masofalarga chiqmasdan, ish haqi olish, pul o'tkazmalarini jo'natish va asosiy xizmatlar uchun to'lovni mobil telefon orqali amalga oshirishga yordam beradi. Elektron pul vaqt va pulni tejaydi. Kelgusi yillarda bozorga ko'proq elektron pul provayderlari kirishi kutilmoqda va elektron pul ekotizimining o'sishi, tranzaksiyalarni soddalashtirish va mavjud raqamli moliyaviy xizmatlar ko'lamini kengaytirish uchun o'zaro hamkorlik zarur bo'ladi. Ushbu tahliliy maqolada O'zbekistonda elektron pullarga oid qonunchilik va Salvador Respublikasidagi elektron pulalarga doir qonunchilik bilan solishtiriladi.

ASOSIY QISM

1. O'zbekistonda elektron pulning huquqiy maqomi

O'zbekiston Respublikasida elektron pullar "To'lov va to'lov tizimlari to'g'risida"gi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qonuniga¹² muvofiq tartibga solinadi. O'zbekiston respublikasida elektron pullar chiqarilishi va muomalada bo'lishi tarbi "To'lov va to'lov tizimlari to'g'risida" qonun asosida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy bankining "O'zbekiston Respublikasi hududida elektron pullarning chiqarilish va muomalada bo'lishi qoidalarini tasdiqlash" to'g'risidagi qaroriga¹³ muvofiq amalga oshiriladi.

"To'lov va to'lov tizimlari to'g'risida" qonunning 8-bobi elektron pullarga bag'ishlangan. Unda elektron pullar tizimiga tarif beriladi, shuningdek, elektron pullarning emitentlari va egalari kim bo'lishi, elektron pullar tizimi operatori, elektron pullarni chiqarish va realizatsiya qilish, ulardan foydalanish va qoplashga oid tartib belgilangan. Qonunning 39-44-moddasi eelktron pullarga bag'ishlangan. Markaziy bankning elektron pullarni chiqarish va muomalaga kirtiishga oid qoidalari qonunning ushbu moddalariga asoslanib tuzilgan.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida elektron pullarni chiqarish va realizatsiya qilish

"To'lovlar va to'lov tizimlari to'g'risida"gi Qonunning 39-moddasiga ko'ra, O'zbekistonda elektron pullarning emintenti Markaziy bank va banklardir. Xo'sh,

¹² <https://lex.uz/docs/-4575786>

¹³ <https://lex.uz/docs/-4803632>

biz elektron pullar emitenti deganda nimani tushunamiz? Ya`ni biz qo`limizdagi naqd pulni elektron pulga aylantirib kartamizga solmoqchi bo`lsak, bevosita bank orqali munosabatga kirishamiz. Bankomatga boramiz, kartamiz va naqd pulni kiritamiz, bankomat naqd pulni olib, uni elektron pulga aylantirib beradi. Bunda bankomat bank bilan aloqa o`rnatib, bizga pulimizni elektronlashtirib beradi. Elektron pulni tijorat banklariga Markaziy bank chiqarib beradi. Elektron pul Markaziy bankdan tijorat banklariga, tijorat banklaridan esa mijozlarga yetib boradi.

Markaziy bankning elektron pullar muomlasiga oid qoidalarida bu yanada aniqroq tushuntirilgan. Emitent tomonidan elektron pullarning chiqarilishi uchun jismoniy shaxs naqd pul yoki naqd pulsiz shaklda pul mablag`larini taqdim etishi zarur. Ushbu pul mablag`lari emitent tomonidan hisob-kitob bankida ochilgan maxsus hisobvaraqa kirim qilinishi ta`minlanadi. 1-rasmda ushbu jarayonni yanada aniqroq tushunish mumkin. ¹⁴

Elektron pullar tizimining sub'ektlari

1-rasm. Elektron pullar subyektlari. Manba: O`zbekiston Markaziy banki.

O`zbekistonda chiqariladigan elektron pullar faqat milliy valyutada bo`lishi shart.

¹⁴ https://cbu.uz/uz/press_center/news/268796/?sphrase_id=122074

Elektron pullardan foydalanish

Qonunchilikda jismoniy shaxslar, ya`ni elektron pullar egasi elektron pullardan ma`lum to`lovlarni, masalan – kommmunal to`lovlar, chakana savdo shaxobchalariga to`lovlar, maishiy xizmatlarga, yoqilg`i quyish shaxobchalari, mobil operatorlar, internet do`konlar, internet provayderlar, televideniya, ko`ngilochar obyektlardagi xizmatlar va qonunchilikda taqiqlanmagan barcha xizmatlarga to`lov qilishda foydalanishi mumkin. Shu bilan birga yuqoridagi qonun hujjatlarida ishlar va xizmatlarni amalga oshirish uchun O`zbekiston Respublikasi hududida chiqarilgan elektron pullar qabul qilinishi nazarda tutilgan.

O`zbekiston qonunchiligida elektron pulni sotib olgandan keyin elektron pulni sotib olganligini tasdiqlovchi kvitansiya berilishi belgilangan. Oddiy tilda aytadigan bo`lsak, bu bizga bankomat orqali naqd pulimizni plastik kartaga tushirib olganimizdan keyin bankomat chiqarib beradigan chek. Qonunchilikka muvofiq, ushbu chekda (ya`ni kvitansiyada) agent, emitent va operatorning nomi ya`ni bank nomi, operatsiya amalga oshirilgan sana va vaqt, operatsiya tartib raqami, realizatsiya qilingan elektron pullar summasi, elektron pullar egasiga tegishli elektron hamyonning identifikatsiya kodi va vositachilik haqi miqdori ko`rsatilishi shart.

Elektron pullarni qoplash

Ushbu qonunda elektron pullarni qoplash tushunchasi ham bor. Emitent tomonidan o`zi chiqargan, elektron pullar egasi taqdim etgan elektron pullarni ularning nominal qiymatiga teng pul mablag`lari summasiga almashtirish operatsiyasining amalga oshirilishini nazarda tutuvchi to`lov xizmati elektron pullarni qoplash deyiladi. Bunda emitent tomonidan:

1. elektron pullar egasi – jismoniy shaxsning bank hisobvarag`iga tegishli summa kirim qilingan yoki unga naqd pul mablag`i berilgan paytdan boshlab;
2. elektron pullar egasi – yakka tartibdagi tadbirkor va (yoki) yuridik shaxsning bank hisobvarag`iga tegishli mablag` kirim qilingan paytdan boshlab elektron pullar qoplangan hisoblanadi.

Emitent tomonidan elektron pullarni qoplash operatsiyasi amalga oshirilganligi to'g'risida elektron pullar egasiga qog'oz yoki elektron shaklda kvitantsiya beriladi. O'zi elektron pul operatori kim degan savol tug'ilishi mumkin. Qonunga ko'ra, elektron pullar tizimining ishlashini ta'minlaydigan bank va (yoki) tegishli litsenziyaga ega bo'lgan to'lov tashkiloti operator hisoblanadi.

Markaziy bankning elektron pullar tizimi reysteri

Markaziy bank qonuchilikka muvofiq, elektron to'lov tizmlariga litsenziya berish bilan shug'ullanadi. Emitent elektron pullarni chiqarish va realizatsiya qilish bo'yicha faoliyatni boshlashi to'g'risida Markaziy bankka mazkur Markaziy bankning elektron to'lovlarga oid qoidalarida belgilangan tartib asosida xabarnoma yuboradi. Xabarnomada operatorning (tovar belgisining) nomlanishi va operatorga berilgan litsenziya raqami, emitent, operatorning hisob-kitob banki va elektron pullar tizimi agentlari haqidagi ma'lumotlar ko'rsatiladi.

Markaziy bank kerakli hujjatlarni qabul qilgach, ma'lum shartlar asosida elektron to'lov tiziga O'zbekiston Respublikasi hududida faoliyatini amalga osjirish uchun litsenziya beradi. Litsenziya asosida elektron pullar chiqaradigan elektron to'lov tizimlari reysteri Markaziy bank tomonida yuriitiladi.¹⁵

Markaziy bank ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, elektron pullar tizimi reysteriga 12ta to'lov tizimi kiritilgan. Biirnchilardan bo'lib reysteriga kiritilgan to'lov tizimlari bu – Click va E-Card`dir. Clickning emitetni “Agrobank” bo`lsa, operatori ya`ni to'lov tizimi ishlab chiqan yuridik shaxs CLICK MCHJ. E-Catdning emitenti esa Universalbank, operatori esa Inspired MCHJ. Har ikki to'lov tizimi 2020 yilning 21 avgustida reystrga kiritilgan.

Bundan tashqari, Aplesin, Oson, Qiwi Uzbekistan kabi to'lov tizimlari ham bor. Barcha to'lov tizimlarining litsenziya berilgan vaqti, emitent va operatorlari bilan 2-rasmda tanishish mumkin.

¹⁵ <https://cbu.uz/oz/payment-systems/documents-license-applicati/payment-organizations/>

Электрон пуллар тизимлари реестри				
№ т/р	Электрон пуллар тизими номи	Оператор номи	Эмитент номи	Электрон пуллар чиқариш бўйича фаолияти бошланган сана
1.	"OSON"	"BRIO GROUP" МЧЖ	АТ "Алоқабанк"	11.10.2022 й.
2.	"E-CARD"	"INSPIRED" МЧЖ	АТБ "Универсал банк"	21.08.2020 й.
3.	"CLICK"	"CLICK" МЧЖ	"Агробанк" АТБ	21.08.2020 й.
4.	"WOOPPAY"	"WOOPPAY UZ" МЧЖ	"Капиталбанк" АТБ	02.11.2020 й.
5.	"alif.mobi"	"ALIF TECH" МЧЖ	АТ "Алоқабанк"	02.11.2020 й.
6.	"Interpay"	"Interpay sys" МЧЖ	"Bank Apelsin" АЖ	11.10.2022 й.
7.	"A-pay"	"CENTER FOR DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION" МЧЖ	"Bank Apelsin" АЖ	01.07.2022 й.
8.	"QIWI Uzbekistan"	"Payment Aggregation Systems" МЧЖ	"Bank Apelsin" АЖ	11.08.2022 й.
9.	"IHLISW"	"Genesis Innovation" МЧЖ	АТ "Алоқабанк"	17.11.2021 й.
10.	"GlobalPay"	"Global Solutions" МЧЖ	АТ "Алоқабанк"	17.11.2021 й.
11.	"Payway"	"Payway" МЧЖ	"Bank Apelsin" АЖ	29.07.2022 й.
12.	"Apelsin"	"Bank Apelsin" АЖ	"Bank Apelsin" АЖ	29.07.2022 й.
13.	"ExMoney"	"Ўзбекистон Республикаси Товар-хонашў биржаси" АЖ	"Трастбанк" ХАБ	30.08.2022 й.
14.	"АИСТ"	"Ozinterpay" МЧЖ	АТБ "Универсал банк"	30.08.2022 й.
15.	"PAYNET WALLET"	"INSTANT PAYMENT SOLUTIONS" МЧЖ	АТ Халқ банки	30.08.2022 й.

2-rasm. Elektron to'lov tizimlari reysteri. Manba: O'zbekiston Markaziy banki

Salvadora elektron pullarga doir qonunchilik

Salvadora raqamli moliyaviy xizmatlar birinchi marta 2011-yilda paydo bo'lgan, o'shanda telekompaniya bilan bog'liq tashkilot xalqaro pul o'tkazmalari, hisob-kitoblar va P2P o'tkazmalarini taklif qila boshlagan. Tranzaksiyalar soni oshgani sayin, Salvador markaziy banki Banco Central de Reserva de El Salvador (BCR)¹⁶ tartibga solish muammosiga duch keldi: bu turdagi mahsulot amaldagi moliyaviy qonunlar bilan tartibga solinmagan va telekommunikatsiya organi nazorati ostida emas edi.¹⁷

Shundan so'ng "Moliyaviy inklyuziyaga ko'maklashish to'g'risida"gi qonun qabul qilindi. Aynan elektron pul to'g'risida maxsus qonun mavjud bo'lmasa ham, ushbu xizmatlarni taqdim etuvchi tashkilot rioya qilishi kerak bo'lgan qoidalar ishlab chiqildi.

Elektron pul bilan ishlash qoidalarini tasdiqlashga birinchi urinish ba'zi to'siqlarga duch keldi, birinchi navbatda, mamlakat bank sektorining qarshiliklari bo'ldi.

¹⁶ <https://www.bcr.gob.sv>

¹⁷ https://www.afi-global.org/sites/default/files/publications/2017-09/AFI_FILAC_CS_EI%20Salvador_AW_digital.pdf

Salvadorning qonunchilik bazasi moliyaviy tizim barqarorligini saqlashga qaratilganligi sababli, telekommunikatsiya modeli kabi yangi institutlarni yaratish loyihasi konservativ sanoatni ishontirish uchun ko`proq ishni talab qildi.

Ushbu qiyin vaziyat BCRni yangi raqobatchilarga elektron pul yoki elektron hamyon yordamida moliyaviy xizmatlar ko`rsatishga imkon beradigan yangi qonunni ishlab chiqishni muhokama qilishga undadi.

El Salvadordagi elektron pullar depozit hisobvarag`i orqali BCR tomonidan to`liq ta`minlanadi va real vaqt rejimida elektron pullarni boshqarish bank javobgar bo`ladi.

Salvadordagi elektron pulning huquqiy asoslari Lotin Amerikasi mamlakatlari bilan solishtirganda, tartibga solishning noyob hodisasidir.

O`sha paytda mobil telefonlar orqali amalga oshirilgan pul o`tkazmalarini tartibga solish uchun elektron pullarni tartibga solish loyihasini ishlab chiqish uchun BCR va SSF idoralararo guruhi tuzildi, bunda BCRning to`lov tizimlari va moliya agentlariga nisbatan imkoniyatlari hisobga olinai.

Nizom loyihasi 2012-yilda ishlab chiqilgan bo`lib, soha vakillari o`z fikr va mulohazalarini bildirgan. Biroq, ABANSA¹⁸ (Salvador banklar assotsiatsiyasi) qoidalarda (mobil telefonlar orqali pul mablag`larini o`tkazish) amalga oshirilgan va nazarda tutilgan operatsiyalarni ta`kidladi.

“Mamlakatda “Banklar to`g`risidagi qonun va "Kooperativ banklari va jamg`arma-ssuda uyushmalari to`g`risida" gi qonunlarga muvofiq, ushbu muassasalar elektron pullar chiqarishga vakolatli organlar sifatida belgilandi.

Yuqoridagi qonunlarda elektron pullarning xususiyatlarini, elektron pullarni chiqaruvchi tashkilotlarga qo`yiladigan minimal talablar va ushbu xizmatlarni ko`rsatishni avtorizatsiya qilish jarayonini aniq tartibga soluvchi qonunni ishlab chiqish maqsadga muvofiq, degan qaror qabul qilindi.

2013-yil sentabr oyida birinchi qonun loyihasi tayyorlanib, taqdim etildi. Izohlar olindi va yakuniy loyiha 2013-yil dekabr oyida Moliya vazirligiga yuborildi.

¹⁸ <https://abansa.net>

Qonun 2014 yil iyun oyida Milliy Kongressdan qonunchilik tashabbusini oldi va keyinchalik 2015 yil avgust oyida ma`qullandi. Mazkur qonun elektron pul mablag`lari, soddalashtirilgan talablar bilan jamg`arma hisob-varaqlariga omonat qo`yish, shuningdek, ularni taqdim eta oladigan subyektlar faoliyatini amalga oshirishning aniq huquqiy asoslarini yaratdi.

El Salvador Lotin Amerikasida mobil o`tkazmalar va to`lovlar bo`yicha eng yuqori o`shishni kuzatdi. 2011-yilda telekompaniyaga ulangan korxonada raqamli moliyaviy xizmatlarni taklif qildi

Bu Salvador bozoriga elektron pul kelganligining birinchi belgisi edi va bugungi kunda ushbu tashkilotda 2500 dan ortiq agent va 900 000 dan ortiq foydalanuvchi bor, ular elektron pullarda to`laydilar, pul o`tkazadilar va xalqaro pul o`tkazmalarini oladilar va boshqa operatsiyalarni amalga oshiradilar.

Yuqorida aytib o`tilganidek, BCR xalqaro institutlardan katta yordam oldi, bu bankning texnik guruhiga elektron pulning afzalliklari, xavfsizlik jihatlari va potentsial xavflarini, shuningdek, zaxira sxemasi (ishonch fondi) va hisob ochish ishlarining soddalashtirilgan jarayonini taklif qildi.

Salvadorda xalqaro pul o`tkazmalariga keng qaramlik ushbu xizmatni mamlakatning ichki qismida rivojlantirish qaroriga ta`sir ko`rsatdi. 2013 yilga kelib, yuqorida qayd etilgan korxonada oyiga 30–40 million AQSh dollari miqdoridagi tranzaksiyalarga guvoh bo`ldi. bu esa mahsulotni tartibga solish zaruratini tug`dirdi.

2017 yilda Salvadorning uchta elektron pul provayderi SSF tomonidan ruxsat olish jarayonida edi va oylik tranzaksiyalarning umumiy hajmi 50–60 million AQSh dollariga ko`tarildi.

Xulosa sifatida aytish mumkin-ki, Salvadorda O`zbekistonga nisbatan elektron pullarning huquqiy asoslarini ishlab chiqish jarayoni nafaqta erta, balki batamom keng qamrovli izlanish va tadqiqotlar natijasida yuzaga kelganini aytish mumkin. Har ikki mamlakat qonunlarida elektron pullarning xususiyatlarini, elektron pullarni chiqaruvchi tashkilotlarga qo`yiladigan minimal talablar va ushbu

xizmatlarni ko`rsatishni avtorizatsiya qilish jarayonini aniq tartibga soluvchi me`yorlar bor. Ammo Salvador tajribasidagi "Comprehensive model" inklyuzilikka qaratilgan. Ya`ni bank tomonidan mijozlarga qulaylik yaratish uchun texnik guruhga elektron pulning afzalliklari, xavfsizlik jihatlari va potentsial xavflarini, shuningdek, zaxira sxemasi (ishonch fondi) va hisob ochish ishlarining soddalashtirilgan talabi qo`yilgan va qonunlarga kiritilgan. Shu sababli ham Salvadorda oylik tranzaksiyalar qisqa muddatda yuqori tezlikda o`tdi. Milliy qonunchiligimizga, aynan elektron pullarni tartibga soluvchi qonunlarimizga Slavador mamlakatlarning tajribasini o`rgangan holda o`zgartirish va qo`shimchalar kiritish mamlakatda elektron pullar almashinuvining jadallashuviga hissa qo`shgan bo`lardi degan fikrdamiz.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

<https://t.me/centralbankuzbekistan/5342>

https://www.afi-global.org/sites/default/files/publications/2017-09/AFI_FILAC_CS_EI%20Salvador_AW_digital.pdf

<https://lex.uz/docs/-4575786>

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https://www.afi-global.org/sites/default/files/publications/2017-09/AFI_FILAC_CS_EI%20Salvador_AW_digital.pdf

<https://abansa.net>

Geografik ko`rsatkichlarning huquqiy tabiati.

Jahongir Zokirov

Yuqori Chirchiq tuman adliya
bo`limi yetakchi maslahatchisi

Geografik ko`rsatkichlar - bu ma`lum bir geografik kelib chiqishga ega bo`lgan va asosan ushbu kelib chiqishi sababli o`ziga xos sifat, mavqega ega yoki boshqa xususiyatlarga ega bo`lgan tovarlarni aniqlaydigan belgi hisoblanadi. Milliy qonunchiligimizda geografik ko`rsatkichlarga quyidagicha ta`rif berilgan, geografik ko`rsatkichlar tovarni muayyan geografik obyekt hududidan kelib chiqqan tovar sifatida identifikatsiyalovchi belgi geografik ko`rsatkich deb e`tirof etilib, unda tovarning sifati, nom qozonganligi yoki boshqa xususiyatlari (bundan buyon matnda tovarning xususiyatlari deb yuritiladi) uning geografik jihatdan kelib chiqishiga sezilarli darajada bog`liq bo`ladi. Mazkur geografik obyekt hududida tovarni ishlab chiqarishning tovarning xususiyatlarini shakllantirishga jiddiy ta`sir ko`rsatadigan bosqichlaridan loaqal bittasi amalga oshirilishi kerak¹⁹. Bizning fikrimizcha geografik ko`rsatkich – bu muayyan geografik kelib chiqishi bor va kelib chiqishi o`sha joyga xos xususiyatlarga yoki obro`ga ega bo`lgan tovarlar bo`yicha ishlatiladigan belgi. Umuman olganda, geografik ko`rsatkichlar tovarlarning kelib chiqish joyi nomidan iborat. Bu xususiyatlari ishlab chiqarilgan joy, iqlim va tuproq kabi geografik omillar bilan belgilanadigan qishloq xo`jaligi mahsulotlaridir. Belgining geografik ko`rsatkich sifatida faoliyat ko`rsatishi milliy qonunchilik va iste`molchilik idroki bilan belgilanadi. Ularning asosiy vazifasi mahsulotlarni bir biridan farqini aniqlashdan iborat va hozirgi kunda iste`molchilar tovarlarning geografik kelib chiqishiga ko`proq ahamiyat berishmoqda. Ko`p hollarda, iste`molchilarga, ishlab chiqarilgan joy mahsulotning ular uchun qadrlı bo`lgan ba`zi bir sifatlarga yoki xususiyatlarga ega ekanligini ko`rsatadi.

¹⁹ O`zbekiston Respublikasining Geografik Ko`rsatkichlar To`G`Risida Qonuni, 03.03.2022 Yildagi O`Rq-757-Son

Shuni ta'kidlab o'tishimiz kerakki, sanoat mulkini himoya qilish to'g'risidagi Parij konvensiyasida "geografik ko'rsatkich" tushunchasi mavjud emas²⁰. Bu "kelib chiqish ko'rsatkichlari" va "kelib chiqish nomlari" bilan bog'liqligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Kelib chiqish belgisi ushbu mamlakatda joylashgan mamlakat yoki joyning mahsulot ishlab chiqarilgan mamlakati yoki joyi sifatida ko'rsatilishi deb nomlanuvchi ta'riflarga ega bo'lishi mumkin. Kelib chiqish belgisi mahsulotning geografik nuqtai nazardan kelib chiqishi to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarni taqdim etadi. Lekin geografik ko'rsatkich tomonidan belgilanadigan mahsulotning har qanday o'ziga xos sifati yoki xususiyatini anglatmaydi²¹.

"Tovar kelib chiqqan joy nomi" tushunchasi kelib chiqqan joy nomlarini himoya qilish va ularni xalqaro ro'yxatdan o'tkazish to'g'risidagi Lissabon bitimida²² mamlakat, mintqa yoki joyning geografik nomi sifatida belgilangan bo'lib, u ma'lum bir mamlakatdan, mintaqadan kelib chiqqan mahsulotni belgilashga xizmat qiladi. yoki mahsulot va obro'ga ega bo'lgan tabiiy va inson omillarini o'z ichiga olgan mahalliy yoki sifati va xususiyatlari faqat yoki asosan geografik muhitga tegishli bo'ladi.

Intellectual mulk huquqlarining savdo bilan bog'liq jihatlari to'g'risidagi bitimda ya'ni Intellectual mulk huquqini savdo sohalarida qo'llanish bitimi (TRIPS) bo'yicha geografik ko'rsatkichlarga ega mahsulotlarni Jahon Savdo tashkilotigaga a'zo bo'lgan hududlardan yoki ushbu hududlarning ma'lum bir sifati, obro'si bo'lgan hududda yoki joydan kelib chiqishini belgilovchi belgilar sifatida

²⁰ Sanoat mulkini himoya qilish bo'yicha Parij konvensiyasi (1883 yil): Парижская конвенция по охране промышленной собственности от 20 марта 1883 года, пересмотренная в Брюсселе 14 декабря 1900 г., в Вашингтоне 2 июня 1911 г., в Гааге 6 ноября 1925 г., в Лондоне 2 июня 1934 г., в Лиссабоне 31 октября 1958 г. и в Стокгольме 14 июля 1967 г. и измененная 2 октября 1979

²¹Ludwig Baeumer, Protection Of Geographical Indications Under WIPO Treaties And Questions Concerning The Relationship Between Those Treaties And The TRIPS Agreement, В Работе Symposium On The Protection Of Geographical Indications In The Worldwide Context, Eger, Hungary, October 24/25 1997, P.12, WIPO Publication No. 760(E), Geneva, 1999.

²²Geneva Act of The Lisbon Agreement on Appellations of Origin and geographical indications (as adopted on May 20, 2015)

ta`riflanad, yoki mahsulotning boshqa o`ziga xos-xususiyatlari asosan uning geografik kelib chiqishi bilan bog`liq bo`ladi.

Geografik ko`rsatkichlar turli xil qishloq xo`jaligi mahsulotlari bilan bog`liq holda ishlatilishi mumkin. Shuningdek, geografik ko`rsatkichlar qishloq joylarini rivojlantirishga o`z hissasini qo`shishi mumkin. Geografik ko`rsatkichdan foydalanish huquqi odatda mahalliy ishlab chiqaruvchilarga tegishli bo`lib, barcha ishlab chiqaruvchilar ham ushbu ko`rsatkich bilan yaratilgan qo`shimcha qiymatdan foydalana oladilar²³. Geografik ko`rsatkichlarning aksariyati qishloq xo`jaligi mahsulotlari, oziq-ovqat, sharob va spirtli ichimliklarni shaxsiylashtirish vositasi sifatida ishlatiladi. Misol uchun, geografik ko`rsatkich «Rokfor» faqat Frantsiyaning ma`lum bir viloyatida ishlab chiqarilgan pishloq uchun ishora qiladi. Bundan tashqari, shampan so`zi Frantsiyaning shampan mintaqasida ishlab chiqarilgan o`ziga xos ko`pikli sharobga nisbatan ishlatilgan. Boshqa misollarni keltirish mumkin: Yamayka Moviy tog`idagi kofe, Darjeeling choyi, Gavana tamaki, Parmigiano Regiano pishloqi va boshqalar.

Geografik ko`rsatkichlar bilan bog`liq mahsulotlarning o`ziga xos xususiyatlarini, asosan uning kelib chiqish joyiga xos bo`lgan inson omillari bilan bog`liqligini ta`kidlashi mumkin. misol, tajriba, mahorat va ishlab chiqarish an`analari. Bu asosan hunarmandchilikka tegishli (Tailand ipagi, Chulucanas Peru seramika, Bohemiya shishasi). geografik ko`rsatkichlar sanoat mahsulotlarini (masalan, Shveysariya soatlari) belgilash uchun ham ishlatiladi. Shunday qilib aytganda, biz quyidagi misollarni keltirib o`tishimiz mumkin: Tekila, Kampot Pepper yoki Argane. Ushbu nomlar, brendlar butun dunyo bo`ylab o`zlarining geografik kelib chiqishiga qarab o`ziga xos xususiyat va sifatga ega mahsulotlar bilan mashxur, eng taniqli geografik ko`rsatkichlardan biri hisoblanadi.

Bundan tashqari, geografik ko`rsatkichlar nafaqat ish o`rinlari yaratish va daromadlarning o`sishiga yordamlashishi orqali, hamda butun mintaqaga e`tiborni o`ziga jalb qilish orqali mintaqaning rivojlanishini va farovonligini ta`minlashi

²³ I.B.Yakubova. Xalqaro Intellektual Mulk Huquqi. O`quv Qo`llanma. – Toshkent: TDYU Nashriyoti, 2021. – 202 B.

mumkin. Geografik ko`rsatkichlar an`anaviy bilimlarni va an`anaviy madaniy ifodalarni saqlashning bir usuli hisoblanadi, chunki geografik ko`rsatkichlari belgilangan mahsulotlar ko`p hollarda ma`lum bir mintaqada jamoatchilik tomonidan qabul qilingan an`anaviy jarayonlar va bilimlardan foydalangan holda ishlab chiqariladi.

Geografik ko`rsatkichlar va tovar belgisi o`rtasidagi farqlarga to`xtalib o`tadigan bo`lsak geografik ko`rsatkichlar va savdo belgilar ham bozorda tovarlarni yoki xizmatlarni aniqlash va ular o`rtasidagi farqlarni farqlash uchun ishlatiladigan o`ziga xos belgi hisoblanadi. Ular iste`molchilarga ma`lum bir mahsulot, tovar yoki xizmat turini ma`lum bir sifat yoki obro` etiborga bog`lash imkon beradi. Savdo belgilari mahsulot yoki xizmat ma`lum bir kompaniya nomidandan olinishini, geografik ko`rsatkichlar esa ma`lum bir joydan kelib chiqishini anglatadi. Tovar belgisi ko`pincha egasi yoki bunga ruxsat berilgan boshqa shaxs tomonidan ishlatilishi, amalga oshirilishi mumkin bo`lgan hayoliy yoki o`ylab topilgan belgi hisoblanadi.

Mahalliy bo`lmagan ma`lum bir mintaqaga mansub bo`lmagan, balki ma`lum bir kompaniya nomi bilan bog`liq bo`lgan savdo yoki tovar belgisi dunyoning istalgan burchagida har qanday shaxsga berilishi yoki litsenziya berilishi mumkin. Savdo belgilaridan farqli o`laroq, geografik ko`rsatkichlar odatda tovar kelib chiqqan joyning nomi yoki ushbu joyda ishlab chiqarilgan tovar nomini o`z ichiga oladi. Ular belgilangan ishlab chiqarish uslubiga muvofiq tovarlarni ishlab chiqarilgan joyda ishlab chiqaradigan barcha shaxslar tomonidan foydalanilishi mumkin²⁴.

Qo`shimcha qilib aytganda, geografik ko`rsatkichning kelib chiqish joyi bilan bog`liqligi sababli geografik ko`rsatkichlarni tegishli hududda bo`lmagan yoki vakolatli bo`lmagan ishlab chiqaruvchilar shaxslar guruhiga tegishli bo`lmagan boshqa shaxslarga berish yoki litsenziya asosida o`tkazish mumkin emas hisoblanadi. Masalan, GU Bordo va Shampan vinosi Bordo va Shampan hududiy mintaqalarida joylashgan barcha sharob ishlab chiqaruvchilari tomonidan

24 "Geographical indications An introduction, 2nd edition". www.wipo.int. Retrieved 2021-09-17.

ishlatilishi mumkin, ammo faqatgina Moet & Chandon shampanini Moet & Chandon deb atashga haqlidir, chunki bu uning savdo belgisi hisoblanadi²⁵.

Tovar kelib chiqqan joy nomlari geografik ko`rsatkichning o`ziga xos farqlariga to`xtalib o`tadigan bo`lsak, tovar kelib chiqqan joy nomlari geografik ko`rsatkichning o`ziga xos turlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Aslida, kelib chiqish joy nomlari - bu mahsulotning sifati yoki xususiyatlari bilan uning geografik kelib chiqishi, shu jumladan har ikkala tabiiy masalan, tuproq sifati, iqlim va insoniy ya`ni nou-xau omillar o`rtasida yanada mustahkam bog`lanishni talab qiladigan, foydalanish uchun yanada qat`iy mezonlarga ega bo`lgan geografik ko`rsatkichlar hisoblanadi.

Masalan, tovar kelib chiqqan joy nomlaridan foydalanish shartlari xomashyo manbai kelib chiqadigan joyda joylashgan bo`lishi kerakligini hamda mahsulotni u yerda qayta ishlashni talab qiladi. Bu ko`p hollarda qishloq xo`jaligi mahsulotlariga nisbatan qo`llaniladi. Bunga misol uchun Rokfor pishloqini keltirib o`tishimiz mumkin bo`ladi. An`anaviy, o`zining qadriyatlariga mansub bo`lgan usulda boqiladigan, parvarish qilinadigan mahalliy qo`y zotlari sutining o`ziga xos xususiyatlari, pishloq pishadigan mahalliy grottolarning tabiiy xususiyatlari va uni ishlab chiqarishning har bir bosqichida qo`llaniladigan odatda qo`llaniladigan an`anaviy usullar - uning o`ziga xos xususiyatlarini va shu bilan birga o`ziga xos ta`mini aynan shu pishloqda mujassam bo`ladi²⁶.

Agar ma`lum bir shaxs boshqa maxsus qoliplarda, uskunalarda pishloq tayyorlashning bir xil usullaridan foydalansa, u boshqacha ta`mga ega pishloq oladi va u endi Rokfor pishlog`i deb atalmaydi. Xuddi shu holat sharob ishlab chiqarish uchun uzunning pishishiga ta`sir qiluvchi tabiiy sharoitlarga ham tegishli, masalan, iqlim, tuproq sifati va boshqalar omillar tegishli bo`ladi.

Yuqoridagi keltirib o`tilgan misollardan kelib chiqadigan bo`lsak, tovar kelib chiqqan joyning nomi - bu mahsulot ishlab chiqarilgan joyning nomi hisoblanadi.

²⁵I.B. Yakubova. Xalqaro Intellektual Mulk Huquqi. O`quv Qo`llanma. – Toshkent: TDYU Nashriyoti, 2021. – 202 B.

²⁶ Tosato, Andrea (2013). "The Protection of Traditional Foods in the EU: Traditional Specialities Guaranteed". European Law Journal

Lekin, geografik ko`rsatkichlarda bo`lgani kabi, joy nomlari bo`lmagan, lekin ma`lum bir joy bilan bog`liq mahsulotlarni belgilaydigan ba`zi an`anaviy holatlar kelib chiqishi nomlari sifatida himoyalangan masalan, Reblochon pishloq yoki Vinho Verde yashil sharob bunga misol bo`la oladi.

Tovarlarning kelib chiqish nomlaridan farqli o`laroq, geografik ko`rsatkichlar bo`yicha, ular tegishli bo`lgan mahsulotlarning belgilangan sifat, obro`-e`tibor yoki boshqa xususiyatlarga ega bo`lishi, asosan ularning geografik kelib chiqishi bilan bog`liq. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, xom ashyoni ishlab chiqarish, shuningdek mahsulotni o`zi yaratish yoki qayta ishlash faqat bitta geografik hududda amalga oshirilishi shart emas hisoblanadi.

Asossiy farqli jihatlariga to`xtalib o`tadigan bo`lsak:

Geografik ko`rsatkichlar - mahsulotning ma`lum bir sifati, obro`si, mavqeyi yoki boshqa xususiyatlariga nisbatan uning geografik kelib chiqishi bilan bog`liq bo`ladi;

-Tovarlarning xususiyatlarini shakllanishiga qarab sezilarli darajada ta`sir ko`rsatadigan tovarlarni ishlab chiqarishi hamda bosqichlarining kamida bittasi tegishli geografik ob`ekt hududida amalga oshirilgan bo`lishi kerak;

-Ro`yxatga olish to`g`risidagi arizada vakolatli organning ya`ni tashkilotning tovar ishlab chiqarishga mo`ljallangan talablarga mosligini tasdiqlovchi, bildiruvchi xulosasini taqdim etishga majbur emas hisoblanadi.

Tovar kelib chiqqan joy nomlari

-Tovarlarning maxsus o`ziga xos-xususiyatlari faqat ma`lum bir geografik ob`ektga mos bo`lgan tabiiy sharoitlarda hamda inson omillari orqali tayyorlanishi bilan belgilanadi;

-Tovarlarning maxsus o`ziga xos-xususiyatlarini shakllantirishga sezilarli darajada ta`sir qila oladigan tovarlarni ishlab chiqarishning barcha bosqichlarida tegishli geografik obyekt hududida amalga oshirilishi talab etiladi;

-Ro`yxatga olish to`g`risidagi arizaga hukumat tomonidan vakolat berilgan ijro etuvchi organning yoki u yo`q bo`lganda – ijro etuvchi organining yoki davlatning

yuqori organi vakolat bergan tashkilotning xulosalari va tegishli geografik obyekt joylashgan hududda davlat tashkil etgan obyektining kuchi, tovarlarni ishlab chiqarishga qo'yiladigan talablarga mosligini bildiruvchi va boshqa hujjatlar taqdim qilinishini talab qiladi²⁷:

Geografik ko'rsatkichlarning himoyalanganligiga va muhofazasiga to'xtalib o'tadigan bo'lsak, turli xil huquqiy madaniyatlarni, an'analarni, shuningdek tarixiy va iqtisodiy sharoitlarni hisobga olgan holda ishlab chiqarilgan geografik ko'rsatkichlarni himoya qilish masalasida ko'plab usullar, yondashuvlardan foydalaniladi. Ba'zi yurisdiksiyalarda geografik ko'rsatkichlar faqat ular uchun ajratilgan sui generis tizimi deb ataladi va bu to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yoki faqat geografik ko'rsatkichlar yoki kelib chiqish joylariga tegishli bo'lgan maxsus qonunlardan iborat. Bunday tizim boshqa intellektual mulk huquqlaridan ajralib turadigan geografik ko'rsatkichlarga maxsus huquqni joriy qilishini nazarda tutmoqda. Sui generisni himoya qilish tizimi, xususan, Yevropa Ittifoqi, Hindiston, Rossiya Federatsiyasi, Shveysariya, Tailand, va Afrika intellektual mulk tashkilotida mavjudligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Geografik ko'rsatkichlar jamoaviy yoki sertifikatlash belgilarini ro'yxatdan o'tkazish tartibi orqali savdo belgisi to'g'risidagi qonunlarga asoslangan holda himoya qilinishi mumkin. Ushbu yondashuv, misol uchun, Avstraliya, Kanada va Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlarida qo'llanilishini kuzatishimiz mumkin. Ushbu turga tegishli belgilar bir nechta shaxslar yoki guruhlar tomonidan foydalanilishi mumkin, agar ushbu foydalanuvchilar tovar belgisining egasi tomonidan belgilangan qoidalarga rioya qilishlari shartili ravishda belgilangan bo'lishi bilan, bu belgidan faqat ma'lum bir geografik ko'rsatkich kelib chiqishi yoki o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga ega bo'lgan tovarlarga nisbatan foydalanish huquqini talab qilishi mumkinligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Kollektiv belgilardan faqat ular tegishli bo'lgan tashkilotlar a'zolari foydalanishi mumkin va sertifikat belgilaridan har kim foydalanishi mumkin, tovar egasi

²⁷https://ru.wikibrief.org/wiki/Lisbon_Agreement_for_the_Protection_of_Appellations_of_Origin_and_their_International_Registration

tomonidan belgilab qo'yilgan talablarga rioya etilgan holda, ushbu holatda ushbu belgidan foydalanish huquqini belgilovchi shaxs. ushbu talablarga muvofiq belgilangan bo'ladi. Masalan, Aydaho kartoshkasidan faqat shu kabi foydalanish qoidalariga rioya qilgan ba'zi fermerlar foydalanishi mumkin.

Qo'shimcha qilib aytganda, geografik ko'rsatkichlarni insofsiz raqobatdan iste'molchilarning huquqlarini himoya qilish yoki mahsulotlarni individuallashtirish to'g'risidagi qonunlar orqali himoya qilinadi. Bunday turdagi qonunlar geografik ko'rsatkichlar uchun alohida sanoat mulk huquqini yaratishni talab qilmaydi. Biroq, ular geografik ko'rsatkichlarning ruxsatsiz, qonunga xilof tarzda foydalanishiga olib kelishi mumkin bo'lgan ba'zi bir holatlarni, harakatlarni taqiqlash yoki cheklash orqali bilvosita himoya qila oladi. Tegishli mintaqadan kelib chiqmagan mahsulotga geografik ko'rsatkichdandan foydalanish insofsiz raqobat hamda adolatsiz savdo amaliyotiga misol bo'la oladi.

Geografik ko'rsatkichlarni tartibga soluvchi va himoya qiluvchi xalqaro shartnomalarga to'xtalib o'tadigan bo'lsak, birinchi navbatda Sanoat mulkini himoya qilish bo'yicha Parij konventsiyasi haqida ma'lumot berib o'tamiz.

Parij konventsiyasi sanoat mulki sifatida manbaning kelib chiqishi va kelib chiqishi nomlarini belgilash bilan bog'liq qoidalarini o'z ichiga olgan birinchi xalqaro shartnomadan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu shartnomada a'zo davlatlar noto'g'ri geografik ko'rsatkichlaridan va nohaq, nohalol raqobatdan masalan, tovarlarning asl kelib chiqishi to'g'risida jamoatchilikni chalg'ituvchi mahsulotlardan samarali himoya qilishlari zarurligi ta'kidlab o'tilgan²⁸.

Ikkinchi xalqaro shartnoma bu - Tovar kelib chiqqan joy nomlarini himoya qilish va ularni xalqaro ro'yxatdan o'tkazish to'g'risidagi Lissabon bitimining asosiy qoidalari (1958) hisoblanadi²⁹. Lissabon shartnomasi kelib chiqish nomlarini himoya qiluvchi shartnoma hisoblanadi, ya'ni, "Ma'lum bir mamlakatdan,

²⁸Парижская конвенция по охране промышленной собственности от 20 марта 1883 года, пересмотренная в Брюсселе 14 декабря 1900 г., в Вашингтоне 2 июня 1911 г., в Гааге 6 ноября 1925 г., в Лондоне 2 июня 1934 г., в Лиссабоне 31 октября 1958 г. и в Стокгольме 14 июля 1967 г. и измененная 2 октября 1979 г.

²⁹Geneva act of the Lisbon agreement on appellations of origin and geographical indications (as adopted on May 20, 2015)

hududdan, mintaqadan yoki ma`lum bir joydan kelib chiqadigan, sifati va xususiyatlari faqat yoki asosan geografik muhitga, shu jumladan tabiiy va inson omillariga bog`liq bo`lgan mahsulotni belgilashga xizmat qiladigan mamlakat, mintaqa yoki joyning geografik nomi" deb Lissabon shartnomasining 2-modda ta`rif berilgan. Bunday nomlar Ahdlashuvchi Davlatning vakolatli organining iltimosiga binoan Jenevadagi BIMTning Xalqaro byurosi tomonidan ro`yxatdan o`tkaziladi. Xalqaro byuro tovar kelib chiqadigan joylarning xalqaro reestrini yuritadi va boshqa davlatlarga ro`yxatdan o`tish to`g`risida rasmiy ravishda ma`lumot beradi.

Qo`shimcha qilib aytganda, ularni Lissabonning kelib chiqishi tizimining rasmiy gazetasida e`lon qiladi. Lissabon bitimining 5 moddasining 3 qismiga asosan ro`yxatga olish to`g`risida xabarnoma olingan paytdan boshlab bir yil ichida Ahdlashuvchi Davlat o`z hududida ro`yxatdan o`tgan nomni himoya qila olmasligini e`lon qilish huquqiga ega hisoblanadi. Bunday deklaratsiyada himoya qilishni rad qilish uchun yetarli darajada asoslarni ko`rsatishi kerak bo`ladi. Ahdlashuvchi Davlatlar keyinchalik bunday voz kechishni Lissabon tizimida ko`zda tutilgan tartibda bekor qilishi mumkin. Lissabon bitimining 3 – moddasiga ko`ra ro`yxatdan o`tgan ism tarjimada ishlatilgan bo`lsa ham yoki "tur" yoki shunga o`xshash boshqa so`zlar bilan qo`shilgan bo`lsa ham, uni noqonuniy tarzda ishlatishdan yoki taqliddan himoya qiladi va Lissabon bitimining 6 – moddasiga ko`ra tovar kelib chiqish mamlakatda himoyalaniishi tugamagunga qadar, uni hech qanday tarzda umumiy xarakterga ega deb belgilash mumkin emas hisoblanadi.

Lissabon shartnomasi 1958 yilda tuzilgan va 1967 yilda Stokgolmda qayta ko`rib chiqilgan va 1979 yilda unga o`zgartirishlar kiritilgan. Lissabon shartnomasi bilan birgalikda Assambleyaga ega bo`lgan ittifoq tashkil etildi. Stokgolm qonunining hech bo`lmaganda ma`muriy va yakuniy qoidalarini ratifikatsiya qilgan ittifoqning har bir a`zo davlati Assambleyaning a`zosi hisoblana boshlangan. Shartnomaga erkin qo`shilish huquqi Sanoat mulkini himoya qilish to`g`risidagi Parij konvensiyasining ishtirokchilari bo`lgan davlatlarga berilgan. Tasdiqlash yoki a`zo

bo`lish to`g`risidagi hujjatlarni BIMTning Bosh direktoriga topshirilishi kerakligi belgilab qo`yilgan.

Tovar kelib chiqish joyini yolg`on yoki chalkash, chalg`ituvchi belgilardan oldini olish uchun Madrid bitimi Parij konvensiyasining manbani sifatida noto`g`ri berilgan geografik ko`rsatkichlardan himoya qilish doirasini kengaytiradi hamda uni geografik ko`rsatkichlarni himoya qilish bilan to`ldiradi³⁰.

Intellectual mulk huquqini savdo sohalarida qo`llanish bo`yicha bitim TRIPS Shartnomasiga muvofiq, Jahon Savdo Tashkilotining barcha a`zo davlatlari geografik ko`rsatkichlardan foydalanish yo`llarini chalg`itadigan yoki nohaq, insofsiz raqobat xattiharakatlaridan himoyalanganligi darajasini ta`minlashga xizmat qiladi. Sharoblar va spirtli ichimliklar bo`lsa, geografik ko`rsatkichlarning chalg`ituvchi yoki insofsiz raqobat bo`lmagan taqdirda ham himoya qilishi belgilab qo`yilgan³¹. Tovar kelib chiqqan joylarning nomlarini himoya qilish bo`yicha Lissabon bitimi va ularni xalqaro ro`yxatdan o`tkazish tovar kelib chiqqan joy nomlarini xalqaro ro`yxatga olish tizimini o`rnatadi va Ahdlashuvchi davlatlar ro`yxatdan o`tgan tovar kelib chiqqan joylarini har qanday noto`g`ri foydalanish yoki taqliddan himoya qilishga majbur hisoblanadilar.

Xorijiy mamlakatlarda geografik ko`rsatkichlarni himoya qilishni ta`minlash masalasiga to`xtalib o`tamiz. Xorijiy mamlakatlarda geografik ko`rsatkichlarni himoya qilishning to`rtta asosiy usuli mavjud, ular quyidagilardan iborat:

- To`g`ridan-to`g`ri tegishli yurisdiksiyada himoya bilan ta`minlash.
- Tug`ilgan joy nomlarini himoya qilish bo`yicha Lissabon bitimi va ularni xalqaro ro`yxatdan o`tkazish Lissabon shartnomasi orqali himoya qilishni ta`minlash, bu BIMT tomonidan boshqariladi. BIMTga bitta ro`yxatdan o`tish orqali (boshqa ro`yxatga olish xalqaro deb nomlanadi) barcha boshqa a`zo davlatlarning hududida bitta a`zo davlatda joylashgan tovar kelib chiqqan joy nomini himoya qilishga imkon beradi. Faqatgina kelib chiqadigan mamlakatda tan

³⁰ https://www.wipo.int/treaties/ru/ip/madrid/summary_madrid_source.html

³¹The TRIPS Agreement, which came into effect on 1 January 1995, is to date the most comprehensive multilateral agreement on intellectual property. https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/trips_e/intel2_e.htm#generalprovisions

olingan va muhofaza qilinadigan tovar kelib chiqadigan joy nomi xalqaro ro`yxatga olish uchun ariza bo`lishi mumkin. 2015 yil may oyida samaradorlikni oshirish va Lissabon kelishuvini yangilash uchun Lissabonning kelib chiqishi va geografik ko`rsatkichlari nomlari to`g`risidagi bitimning Jeneva qonuni Lissabon shartnomasining Jeneva akti qabul qilindi. Bu nafaqat tovar kelib chiqqan joy nomlarini, balki GI larni ham xalqaro ro`yxatga olishni ta`minlaydi.

➤ 3. BIMP tomonidan boshqariladigan Belgilarni xalqaro ro`yxatdan o`tkazish uchun Madrid tizimi orqali himoya qilishni ta`minlash. Ba`zi mamlakatlarda GI ni jamoaviy yoki sertifikat belgisi sifatida himoya qilish mumkin, bu to`g`ridan-to`g`ri milliy yoki mintaqaviy savdo belgi idorasiga (kelib chiqish idorasiga) xalqaro talabnoma topshirish va ushbu belgi ro`yxatdan o`tgan (yoki arizachining kerakli aloqasi bo`lgan (amaldagi va soxta sanoat yoki tijorat korxonasi) bo`lgan Ahdlashuvchi tomonning savdo markasi ofisida ro`yxatdan o`tish uchun ariza berilgan. Talabnoma beruvchi xalqaro arizada hududida muhofaza qilish so`ralgan shartnoma tuzuvchi tomonlarni ko`rsatadi.

➤ 4. davlatlar yoki tijorat sheriklari o`rtasida ikki tomonlama shartnomalar tuzish. Xulosa qilib aytga, geografik ko`rsatkichlarning huquqiy tabiatini milliy va xalqaro qonun hujjatlarga asoslarga holda qiyosiy tahlil qilish usuli orqali muhokama qildik va o`rgabdik. Bundan tashqari geoagrafik ko`rsatkichlarni tovar belgilari, tovarning kelib chiqqan joy nomlari o`rtasidagi asosiy o`ziga xos farqlarni va o`xshashliklarni huquqiy jihatdan tahlil qildik.

O`zbekiston Respublikasi va xorijiy davlatlarda nou-xauning huquqiy tabiati va uning huquqiy muhofazasi

Oybek Buriyev

Yuqori Chirchiq tuman
adliya bo`limi boshlig`i

Aslini olganda Nou-xau, tijorat sirlari va konfidensial ma`lumotlarning barchasi savdoda foydalaniladigan, raqobatdosh ustunlikni ta`minlaydigan mulkiy ma`lumotlar yoki materiallarni tavsiflash uchun ishlatiladigan atamalardir.

NOU-XAU so`zi asli to know how to do it — qanday bajarishni bilmoq so`zidan olingan bo`lib, nou-xau deganda ushbu mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish yoki foydalanishga topshirish bilan bog`liq texnik ma`lumotlar yoki yordamning har qanday shakli tushuniladi. Bu, shuningdek, biron bir amaliy maqsadga erishish uchun zarur bo`lgan har qanday amaliy bilim, texnika va ko`nikmalarni anglatadi. Bu huquqlarni sotib olish va sotish mumkin bo`lgan nomoddiy mulk hisoblanadi. Nou-xau, shuningdek, insonlarning katta guruhlari keng ko`lamli moliyalashtirilgan tajriba va hamkorlik orqali ega bo`ladigan texnik mahoratni anglatadi.

Quyida nou-xauni belgilaydigan sud amaliyotida keltirilgan nou xauning qisqacha mazmuni:

Nou-xau odatda aniq, alohida tavsiflashga qodir bo`lmagan faktik bilim sifatida ta`riflanadi. Biroq, to`plangan shaklda foydalanilganda, sinov va xatolik natijasida qo`lga kiritilgandan so`ng, uni qo`lga kiritgan kishiga tijorat muvaffaqiyati uchun zarur bo`lgan bir xil aniqlik yoki aniqlik bilan qanday ishlab chiqarishni bilmagan narsalarni ishlab chiqarish qobiliyatini beradi. [Hooker Chemical Corp. v. Velsicol Chemical Corp., 235 F. Supp. 412 (W.D. Tenn. 1964)]

Ko`pgina korxonalar patent, tovar belgisi yoki mualliflik huquqi bo`lmagan intellectual mulkni alohida toifaga birlashtiradi, va ularni "nou how" deb hisoblaydilar. Darhaqiqat, "an`anaviy" intellectual mulk bilan bog`lab bo`lmaydigan hamma narsani qo`lga kiritishga urinish uchun shartnomalarda

mudofaa sifatida ta`riflangan "know how" atamasi ko`pincha uchraydi. Bunday atamalar quyidagicha tushuniladi:

"Know How" degani: jarayonlar, usullar, kompozitsiyalar, formulalar, protseduralar, protokollar, dasturiy ta`minotni ishlab chiqish va takomillashtirish, texnikalar, tajriba va sinov natijalari, umumiy ma`lum bo`lmagan ma`lumotlar, foydalanish orqali ishlab chiqarilgan yoki ishlab chiqarilgan mulklarni nazarda tutadi.

Mazkur masalani AQSH qonunchiligi bilan ko`rib chiqsak:

Ma`lumotlar hujjatlarda bo`lishi mumkin, odamlarda ko`nikmalar shaklida paydo bo`lishi yoki materiallar bo`lishi mumkin. Nou-xau yoki materiallar o`z qiymatini saqlab qolishi uchun ular kompaniya uchun maxfiy bo`lib qolishi va chiqarilishi cheklanishi kerak. Nou-xauni himoya qilishning birinchi qadami uni aniqlay olishdir. Mumkin bo`lgan joylarda ma`lumotlar, protseduralar, g`oyalar, rejalar va boshqalar hujjatlashtirilishi kerak. Hujjatsiz ma`lumotni boshqarish mumkin emas va agar ma`lumotlar kompaniya bo`ylab erkin uzatilsa, xodimlar nima maxfiy ekanligini va nima maxfiy ekanligini tushunishlarini ta`minlash ancha qiyin. Muhim hujjatlarga "maxfiy; nusxa ko`chirilmasligi kerak, agar tarqatilgan bo`lsa, raqamlangan va kuzatilgani ma`qul va xodimlarga hujjatlar muhimligi va ish beruvchi qimmatli deb hisoblagan ma`lumotlar mavjudligini tushunishlari uchun kirish cheklangan. Barcha qoramalar yo`q qilinishi kerak.

Tijorat siri bu maxfiylikning natijasi hisoblanib, deyarli har qanday sir bo`lib, uning egasiga moddiy qiymat beradi. Tijorat siri sifatida himoya qilish o`z ichiga formulalar kabi texnik va ilmiy ma`lumotlar, ishlab chiqarish usullari va spetsifikatsiyalari, dizaynlari, kompyuter kodi va shunga o`xshash narsalarni oladi. Tijorat va moliyaviy ma`lumotlar ham shunday tijorat siri bo`lishi mumkin. Mijozlarning ro`yxati, xaridorning xarid qilish afzalliklari va talablari, shaxsi mijozlar qaror qabul qiluvchilar, narx ma`lumotlari, marketing va biznes rejalar, ichki xarajat tarkibi, yetkazib beruvchilar kelishuvi va shunga o`xshash boshqa ommaviy bo`lmagan ma`lumotlar himoyalangan bo`lishi mumkin.

Hatto "salbiy" deb ataladigan ma`lumotlar ham tijorat siri sifatida himoyalaniishi mumkin.

Masalan, formuladagi muammolarni bartaraf etish bo`yicha muvaffaqiyatsiz harakatlar tafsilotlari yoki ba`zi mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish, tadqiqotda duch keladigan boshi berk ko`chalar, texnikdan voz kechish, yechimlar yoki savdoni yakunlash yoki turli mijozlarni qiziqtirish uchun muvaffaqiyatsiz urinishlar kompaniya mahsuloti yoki xizmatini sotib olayotganda, har biri savdo sifatida himoyalaniishi mumkin bo`lgan sir bo`lishi mumkin. Bunday "salbiy" ma`lumotlar raqobatchi uchun nima qilmaslik kerakligi haqida ko`rsatma sifatida qimmatlidir.

Patentlangan texnologiyadan farqli o`laroq, tijorat siri yangi bo`lishi shart emas. Aslida, tijorat siri, mavjud ma`lumotlar mijozlar ro`yxati sifatidako`rinishga ega bo`lishi ham mumkin. Patent yoki mualliflik huquqini himoya qilish, odatda, biron bir oshkor qilishni yoki ma`lumotlarning nashr etilishi talab qiladi. Keyin vaqtinchalik himoya bir qancha muddatga taqdim etiladi va yillar o`tgach, ma`lumotlar jamoatchilikka bepul taqdim etiladi. Tijorat sirida esa himoya egasi maxfiylikni saqlab qolishda muvaffaqiyat qozongan vaqtgacha mavjud ma`lumot saqlanadi va oshkor etilishiga yo`l qo`yilmaydi.

Biroq, tijorat siri to`g`risidagi qonunlar egasiga maxfiy ma`lumotlar bo`yicha eksklyuziv huquqlardan foydalanish huquqini bermaydi. Boshqalar ma`lumotni mustaqil ravishda ishlab chiqishi mumkin.

Tijorat sirlarini litsenziyalash

Tijorat siri egasi eksklyuziv, yagona yoki eksklyuziv bo`lmagan litsenziyalarni berishi mumkin. Litsenziya muayyan hududlar, mijozlar yoki mahsulot bozorlari bilan cheklanishi va boshqa yo`l bilan ruxsat etilishi mumkin. Litsenziar ushbu sohalarda litsenziat bilan birga tijorat siri bilan ishlashni davom ettirishi litsenziatga xos emas. O`zaro litsenziya shartnomalarida ham tomonlar tijorat sirlarini almashadilar deb keltirilgan bo`lishi mumkin.

Litsenziat tomonidan tijorat siridan foydalanganlik uchun to`lov ham turli shakllarda bo`lishi mumkin.

Nou-xauni almashish va uzatish imkoniyati uni iqtisodiy baholashning asosi bo`lib, sarflangan xarajatlarning kelajakdagi foydaliligini, ulardan yengilligini prognoz qiluvchi qo`shimcha metodologiyalar litsenziya bo`yicha royalti yoki ichki ekspluatatsiyadan olingan differentsial daromadga asoslanadi.

Asosiy va amaliy tadqiqotlarga investitsiyalar bozor asosida amalga oshiriladi imkoniyatlar, olish mumkin bo`lgan mablag`lar, jumladan, davlat mablag`lari va qonuniylik darajasi himoya qilish mumkin bo`lgan himoya.

Milliy qonunchiligimizda esa mazkur soha Fuqarolik kodeksi VI bo`limi, 1031-, 1095-moddalarida keltirilgan bo`lib, oshkor etilmaydigan axborotlar, intellektual mulk obyekti sifatida keltirilgan. Biroq qonunchilikda know how tushunchasiga batafsil to`xtab o`tilmagan, bu esa yuqoridagi AQSH talili kabi ko`plab muammoli vaziyatlarni know how deb tavsiflashga ham olib keladi. Mazkur sohada O`zbekiston Respublikasining 2014-yil 11-sentabrdagi O`RQ-374-son “Tijorat siri to`g`risida”gi Qonuni, O`zbekiston Respublikasining 2003-yil 30-avgustdagi 530-II-son “Bank siri to`g`risida”gi Qonunlari mavjud bo`lib, tijorat siri va bank siri normalari keltirilib, umumiy jihatidan ushbu sirlar himoyasini tavsiflaydi.

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CHEMICAL SCIENCE

Visual model of the liquid phase`s separation surface for the multicomponent alloys

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Abstract: The paper analyzes an alternative to 3-D method for visualization of the Liquidus surfaces for multicomponent systems using the Cu-Pb-Tl alloy as an example.

The relevance to select the optimal parameters of production processes is one of the main factors that shape the direction of scientific research. The main subject of investigation is addressed to choosing the optimal parameters from a visualized palette of values, ranging from the concentrations of alloy components to boiling temperatures in relation to the processes of phase transformations of multicomponent alloys. The scientific substantiation of this issue is based on the facts that in the production processes there is a spontaneous achievement of the maximum temperature. In the reviewed scientific works the dependence of the spontaneous achievement of the maximum firing temperature from the totality of acting factors, such as air consumption, sulfur content in substandard copper concentrates, was studied. At maximum firing temperatures, undesirable shaping may occur in alloys, up to bubbles and defects, deformations of casting product samples. The advantages of visualized temperature distribution maps with highlighted near-boundary areas of phase separations consist of possibilities to select the optimal concentrations of alloy components corresponding to Liquidus or Solvus temperatures close to the maximum values in order to avoid loss of product quality.

Mapping of phase diagrams of multicomponent alloys provides an opportunity at the design stage of the technological process to select the optimal parameters of alloy composition and temperature, close to the theoretical parameters of boiling, crystallization, and other phase transformations of alloys to minimize defects.

The developed author's software module, implemented in the Excel environment using the VBA package, is used to build maps of the temperature distribution of the Liquidus surface of the mixture. The module is developed to track the coordinates of the parameters of the layering boundary with specified precision, as well as to segmenting the areas with predetermined conditions. The problem of interactive control of visualization of 3D surface of 2-parameter dependence in the boundaries of the separation of liquid alloys is solved. In the visualization module in order to conduct the calculation of the Liquidus surfaces, the function of the internal thermodynamic stability of the homogeneous phase was used. As applied to the Cu-Pb-Tl system, an analytical expression for the function of the layering of the ternary system was used. From obtained maps it is possible to select a wide range of data, both from the liquid alloy's separation boundaries and from the border areas, with the assistance of the visualization in the color resolution of the mentioned areas. Highlighting the selected areas by specified color is carried out in the body of the macros by entering conditions on the parameters of the equation. A comparative picture of sections with characteristic slopes of isothermal lines from the phase diagram of the alloy and the visualized response surface was also analyzed. The identity of the slopes of the Liquidus lines indicates the reliability of the proposed method, in the case that the phase diagrams are reliable.

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Thermodynamics of reducing roasting of titanomagnetite concentrates with natural gas

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Keywords: thermodynamic analysis, natural gas recovery, titanomagnetite, carbon dioxide, Gibbs energy.

During the reduction of titanomagnetite concentrate, a number of impurity components of the concentrate may interact with soda. The temperature dependence ΔG_T^0 of these reactions is higher than 1050K, the value ΔG_T^0 for all reactions is negative. In real conditions in the gas phase $P_{CO_2} < 1\text{atm}$. Then the second term on the right side of the equation

$$\Delta G_T = \Delta G_T^0 + RT \ln P_{CO_2}$$

will be a negative value, and the value of ΔG_T becomes less than the value of ΔG_T^0 . Therefore, reactions can take place at even lower temperatures.

The main gaseous reducing agent of the system is methane, which simultaneously undergoes partial thermal decomposition and conversion at high temperatures with direct participation in reduction reactions. An analysis of the temperature curves of the change of ΔG_T^0 of these and other gas phase reactions shows that at temperatures above 700°C (973K) for all the reactions presented – decomposition and conversion of methane, carbon black gasification and CO conversion – the value of $\Delta G_T^0 < 0$. If we take into account the partial pressure ratios of the components of the gas phase, then ΔG_T for these reactions will be a more negative value than ΔG_T^0 .

Fig.1 Dependences of the Gibbs free energy of reactions on temperature

It follows from Fig. 1 that at low temperatures, the reduction of iron by natural gas in the presence of soda proceeds through sodium ferrite and iron (II) oxide. With an increase in temperature to 850–930⁰C, the reaction proceeds at high speed, the resulting sodium ferrite is reduced to metal with the regeneration of soda.

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Colloid-chemical properties of bentonite samples depending on dye concentration

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Bentonite clays are among the most important non-metallic minerals and are widely used in various industries and agriculture. The volume of production of bentonite clays in the world over the past years has been consistently about 10 million tons annually.

Clay minerals are highly dispersed systems formed mainly in the process of chemical weathering of rocks. The high dispersion of clay minerals and their specific properties are achieved due to the peculiarities of their crystal chemical - structure and the ability of basal faces and microcrystals to actively interact with water molecules.

One of the promising methods for cleaning industrial wastewater from hydrocarbons is the electroflotation method. The complex physicochemical processes occurring in this case indicate a significant difference between the electroflotation method and other flotation methods. It has been established that anodic oxidation of dispersed hydrocarbons occurs under the action of molecular chlorine and oxygen. In the process of water treatment, aggregates are formed, consisting of a large number of hydrocarbon globules. The units have a developed surface. The formation of aggregates is explained by oxidative processes that reduce the surface charge, which leads to a decrease in aggregative stability.

This report presents the results of studies of the effect of dye concentration on the colloid-chemical properties of Dash-Salakhlin bentonite and its cation - substituted forms. When using sorbents in sorption processes of waste water purification from cationic dyes , one of the important conditions is the control of their physicochemical and colloidal chemical properties.

To study the above characteristics, we used monocationic forms (H^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+}) of bentonite from the Dash-Salakhinskoe deposit, which we obtained by the method of ionic exchange.

After that, experimental studies were carried out to reveal the role of the concentration of cationic dyes on the colloid-chemical properties of monocation - - substituted forms of bentonite.

In a series of suspensions, the initial bentonite, Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} cation -substituted forms, an increase in colloidal fractions is observed in comparison with H^+ , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} cation- substituted forms .

To reveal the effect of the concentration of dyes on the colloid-chemical properties of bentonite samples , solutions of dyes with concentrations of 5, 10, and 15 mg/l were taken. For their comparison , distilled water was used. It was found that in distilled water the content of the colloidal fraction of the studied bentonite and its Na^+ , K^+ samples are 65.6-94.0%, and in Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} cation- substituted forms, due to an increase in their charge and ionic radius, their dispersion and hydration in an aqueous medium decrease, and this leads to a decrease in the content of their colloidal fraction, which is 2.4-5.2%.

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Influence of natural bentonite and zeolite on the process ventilation air cleaning from acid vapor

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When cleaning ventilation air with zeolites from vapors of various acids, over time, especially at their elevated concentrations, aluminum atoms are washed out from the crystal lattice of zeolites and bentonites. At the same time, ion-exchange processes occur, in which sodium, potassium, calcium, and magnesium ions are replaced by acid hydrogen. Also, in order to study the effect of vapors of aggressive acids: sulfuric, hydrochloric and nitric acids, on the adsorption capacity of materials obtained on the basis of natural zeolites and bentonites, the pattern of changes in their concentration was studied. When studying the process of cleaning ventilation air from acid vapors, depending on the duration of work, the derifatographic research method was used, since these studies provide valuable information about changes in the physicochemical properties of zeolite and bentonite samples.

Rice. Scheme of a turbulent-contact absorber: 1 - inlet pipe; 2 - outlet pipe; 3 - body; 4 - movable nozzle; 5 - pump

As a result of the research, it was found that the ability of zeolites and bentonites to absorb substances of various breeds makes it possible to use them to solve various technological issues and the possibility of repeated use of these materials in sorption and desorption cycles; therefore, they are often referred to as "eternal"

reagents. It is shown that the experience gained as a result of research contributes to the correction of promising directions in the field of the use of zeolites and clay materials in the process of cleaning ventilation air from vapors of toxic substances.

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Obtaining of the greases using soapstoks

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Soaps of higher fatty acids of synthetic and natural origin are the most common thickeners for obtaining greases. Considering that in the process of cotton cleaning at the cotton cleaning plants of our republic, the named soapstock, containing a significant number of fatty acids, is obtained as an intermediate product. This fact is interested in the preparation of lubricants for various purposes using soapstock. Neutralization of fatty acids of soapstocks with calcium oxide hydrate in mineral oil with kinematic viscosity 35-45mm²/s at temperature of 50°C has produced a grease of the solidol type G (natural fatty acids). As a result of research, the optimum ratio of the components used has been established and the technology for obtaining this lubricant has been developed. The possibility of using a higher viscosity oil base as a dispersion habitat has been also revealed. It has been established that oil-based solidol of medium viscosity with solidol US-2 G (a mixture of petroleum acids thickened with calcium soap fatty acids) is a general-purpose antifriction grease, which is characterized by working temperatures of 60-70°C.

By introducing into the composition of the prepared grease type solidol G - 10%, widely used in the rubber industry furnace soot of TM-10 brand, grease similar in physical and chemical properties to the graphite grease USeA, used at temperatures up to 60°C in the rough heavy-loaded mechanisms was obtained. With the use of soapstock, complex calcium greases of the UNIOL-1 type were also prepared, in which both 97-98% acetic acid and sodium diethyldithiocarbamate were used as complex-forming components. The dispersion agents were high viscosity oils, such as viscosine or residual oils from Baku refineries. Obtained greases of UNIOL-1 type have high dropping point, little change in strength limit with increasing

temperature, low vaporizability and can be recommended for lubrication of various mechanisms working at temperatures above 100°C.

Key words: greases, soapstock, fatty acids soaps, solidol

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CULTUROLOICAL SCIENCES

“STREET ART” ёки шаҳар муҳити санъати

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Аннотация

“Street art” ҳозирги кунда энг актуал ва кам ўрганилган санъат тури ҳисобланади. Ушбу мақолада кўчаларда пайдо бўлган тасвирларнинг ҳаммаси ҳам “Street art” бўла олмаслиги ва унинг оддий тасвир ўртасидаги фарқи таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: “Street art”, граффити, кўча санъати муҳити, мурал, стрет арт объекти, шаҳар макони, шаҳар услуби.

Аннотация

“Street art” в настоящее время является наиболее актуальным и малоизученным видом искусства. В данной статье была предпринята попытка проанализировать отличие “Street art” от обычных изображений, что не все изображения, появляющиеся на улицах, могут быть “Street art”.

Ключевые слова: “Street art”, граффити, уличное искусство, мурал, объект стрет арт, городское пространство, городской стиль.

Annotation

“Street art” is currently the most relevant and little-studied art form. In this article, an attempt was made to analyze the difference between “Street art” and ordinary images, that not all images appearing on the streets can be “Street art”.

Keywords: “Street art”, graffiti, street art, mural, street art object, urban space, urban style.

“Street art” - бу шаҳарнинг маданий, ижтимоий-сиёсий ва бошқа кесимлари билан ишлайдиган тасвирий санъат йўналиши ҳисобланади. “Street art” нинг келиб чиқиши ва ривожланиш тарихини кўриб чиқишдан

олдин “Street art” атамасига, унинг маъно шаклларига эътибор қаратсак. “Street art” (инглизча “Street art” – кўча санъати,) - бу махсус алоқа воситаси яъни, рассом ўз-ўзини ифода этиш, кўрган нарсангиздан фикр чиқаришга мажбур қилиш, субмаданиятни ифодалаш ва шунингдек, меъморий тузилманинг декоратив элементидир.³² Шу билан бирга бу ҳодисага, ижтимоий бирлаштириш билан боғлиқ бадиий, қатъий илмий таърифда қийинчиликлар мавжуд атама дейиш мумкин. “Street art” муаммоларини ўрганадиган турли изланувчилар “кўча санъати ўзи нима?” каби саволни қўядилар.

“Street art” нинг замонавий шакли 1960-йилларда Филадельфияда (АҚШ) ривожланган. Бу жой ҳанузгача граффити маданиятининг тарихий маркази ҳисобланади. 1970-йилларда бу ҳаракат Нью-Йоркда тарқала бошлади. Манхэттеннинг Вашингтон Хейгс ҳудудида ушбу турдаги санъат ёзувлари пайдо бўлган. Айнан ўша пайтда “теглаш” - муаллифнинг исми ёки тахаллусини ўз ичига олган белгилар ихтиро қилинган. Шу билан бирга, тахаллусдан олдин эса кўча рақамларини ёзиш одат эди.

Шундай қилиб, дунёнинг турли бурчакларида шаҳарсозликнинг ривожланиши билан кўча санъати ҳам ривожланиб, замонавий шаҳар ҳаётининг ажралмас қисмига айланди. 2012 йилда Санкт-Петербургда биринчи марта “Street art” музейи очилди. Ушбу музейнинг асосий мақсади кўча санъати ва граффити ҳақида маълумот беришдир. Музей замонавий лойиҳаларни ташкил этишда ҳам ёрдам беради ва ёш рассомларни қўллаб-қувватлайди. Музей вакиллари шаҳар марказидан олисда жойлашган саноат объектларидан фойдаланган ҳолда ижодкорликни ривожлантиришга янгича ёндашувни жорий этишга ҳаракат қилмоқда.

Аввало, шунини таъкидлаш керакки, ҳозирги вақтда кўча санъати тушунчасининг кўча рассомлари учун ҳам, ушбу ҳодисани тадқиқотчилари учун ҳам мос келадиган ягона таъриф мавжуд эмас: “Атроф-муҳит ва унинг

³²Крылов С.Н. К вопросу формирования стрит-арта как направления в искусстве. URL: <https://sibac.info/author/krylov-sergey-nikolaevich>

атрофида яқинда содир бўлган фаол ҳаракатлар мавжуд. Бу “кўча санъати муҳити” деб номланади³³. Кўча санъатининг асосий шакллари - теглар (инглизча “тег”дан – ёрлиқ ҳисобланади. Исм, тахаллус, жамоа номи), граффити, мурал (инглизча “мурал” - фрескадан олинган деворий расмлар), трафаретлар, плакатлар, мозаикалар, стикерлар (ёпишқоқ асосли олдиндан тайёрланган тасвирлар), перфоманс (инглизча “performance” дан - сценарийга асосланган томоша), ҳаппенинг (инглизча “happening” дан - аниқ сценарийга эга бўлмаган рассом иштирокидаги спектакль), “partizaning” (шаҳарни қайта режалаштирувчилар ҳаракати) ҳисобланади. Кўча санъати объектлари шаҳар маконида яратилади ва ишлайди. Шу муносабат билан ҳодиса инсон ҳаётининг турли соҳаларига аралшиб, фанлараро хусусият касб этади. Унинг таърифи билан ишлашнинг асосий муаммоларидан бири унинг “санъат” атамаси билан боғлиқлигидир. Бунинг сабаби шундаки, кўча санъати объекти ижодий ҳаракат бўлиб, унинг натижаси кўпинча эстетик идрокни ўз ичига олган ва бадиий таҳлилни талаб қиладиган қандайдир тасвир, ҳайкал ёки ижро ётади. Кўча муҳитидаги у ёки бу ижоднинг санъат билан қандай боғлиқлигини аниқлашга имкон берадиган мезонларнинг йўқлиги кўча санъати феноменини аниқлашда қийинчиликлар туғдиради.

“Кўча санъати - бу нафақат шаҳар маконининг тажрибаси ва у билан доимий ўзаро таъсир қилиш, балки шаҳардан ўз баёнотлари учун майдон сифатида фойдаланишдир”³⁴. Рус кўча рассоми Т.Радя кўча санъатида томошабин ролига катта аҳамият беради: унинг фикрича, нафақат муаллиф, балки томошабин ҳам умумий санъат деб ҳисоблаган нарса “Street art” деб ҳисобланиши мумкин³⁵. Кўча санъатининг бевосита иштирок этадиган одамлар томонидан таърифланишидаги асосий нукта - бу тасвир, атроф-муҳит ва томошабиннинг ўзаро таъсиридир.

³³Серкова Н. «Стрит-арт»: движение без сопротивления. URL: <http://partizaning.org/?p=9919>

³⁴Поносов И. Искусство и город. Граффити, уличное искусство, активизм. Москва, 2016. 208 с.

³⁵Radya T. All i know about street art URL: <http://t-radya.com/street/39/>

Замонавий жамиятда кўча санъати кўпинча қонунийлаштирилади, лекин аслида у ҳали ҳам ноқонуний ижоддир. Бунинг сабаби шундаки, аксарият мамлакатларда шаҳар маконидаги ҳар қандай номувофиқ дизайн вандализм бандига киради.

Бошқа томондан, кўча рассомлари орасида ҳақиқий кўча санъати - бу ҳокимият билан олдиндан келишилмаган бўлиб, фақат бу ҳолатда рассом ўз ғоя ва қарашларини ифодалаш учун тўлиқ эркинликка эга ва ҳеч қандай рамкага мослашмаслиги керак деган фикр кенг тарқалган. Ноқонуний тасвирлар учун бу атама кейинчалик, уларнинг сони кўпайиб, давлат тузилмалари томонидан назоратни йўқотиб бўлгач, тарқала бошлади.

Европа стрет арти Америка граффитисидан кўпроқ образли ва рамзийлиги билан фарқ қилади. Шаҳарнинг бепоён худудидаги мажозий тасвирни “Street art” объектига айлантирадиган нарса подтекстдир. Баъзи мамлакатларда “Street art” - айниқса граффити - сиёсий ва ижтимоий норозилик шакли бўлганлиги сабабли, жамоатчилик онгида уни фақат исёнкор кесим билан таъминлаш тамойили мавжуд эди. Кўчаларнинг очик жойларида ҳақиқатдан ҳам бизнинг давр кундалик ҳаётини акс эттирувчи “Street art” объектлари мавжуд бўлиб, уларнинг баъзилари кинояга тўла, бошқалари эса карикатурадир. Бироқ, кўпинча “Street art” объектлари тор сиёсий йўналишдан маҳрум бўлган эркин ижод актига айланади ва баъзан улар декоратив элементлар сифатида ишлайди. Ҳозирда стрет арт деганда давлат тузилмалари билан келишилган ва келишилмаган ҳар қандай ижодий лойиҳалар тушунилади, улар шаҳар маконида амалга оширилади ва шаҳар муҳитини ўзгартиришга ва томошабин билан мулоқот қилишга қаратилган.

Шаҳар муҳитидаги санъат ижодий механизм бўлиб, у мавжуд белгилар тизимини йўқ қилиши мумкин, аммо унинг мақсади шаҳар маконини сифат жиҳатдан ўзгартиришдир.

Бу назарияларни Inkuzart таҳаллуси остида ижод қилувчи тошкентлик рассомнинг энг машхур асари Тошкент шаҳри, Чилонзор туманидаги

АҚШнинг собиқ элчихона биноси деворига ишланган “Монополия” тасвири хисобланади. Асарда автомобиль харид қилиш учун узундан узун навбатлар, навбатда биринчи бўлиб турган одам эса ҳаммадан ажратилган холда қизил рангли бош кийимда тасвирланган. Қизил рангдаги бош кийим бу инсоннинг машинани норасмий тўлов, бошқача айтганда коррупция орқали навбатсиз қўлга киритаётганига ишорадир. Бу тасвир ортида рассомнинг Ўзбекистонда Chevrolet бренди остида автомобиллар ишлаб чиқарадиган “UzAvto Motors” компаниясининг монопол мавқеига қарата “отилган” киноялари мужассам бўлган. Айтиш мумкинки, бу киноялар нафақат рассомнинг шахсий фикри балки, бутун мамлакатдаги автомобиль ишқибозларининг нозик нуқтасидир. Бу асар ижтимоий тармоқларда кўплаб муҳокамаларга сабаб бўлди, тасвир ҳақидаги мулоҳаза ва муҳокамалар кўпайди. Шундан кўриниб турибдики, бу асарни ҳақиқий “Street art” деб аташ мумкин. Чунки, бу тасвирда халқнинг дарди намоён бўлган.

Яна мисол қилиб, Тошкент шаҳри, Яшнабод туманидаги тўрт қаватли турар жой биноси фасадига ишланган граффитини келтириш мумкин. Бу асарда қуёшли осмон, Ўзбекистон байроғи, юртимизда бўлаётган қурилишлар фонида қурувчи, тиббиёт ходимаси ва ўқувчи қиз тасвирланган. Юртимиз тинчлиги тимсоли эса оппоқ кабутарлар орқали очиб берилган. RenaroBrush номли арт-студия рассомлари томонидан яратилган ушбу граффити шаҳримиз жозибасига кўрк қўшиб турибди. Лекин ушбу асарни чин маънода “Street art” деб аташ нотўғри бўлади. Чунки бу граффитида юқоридаги асар каби халқни қийнаётган муаммо ёки умумий маънода “подтекст” мавжуд эмас. Бу асар фақатгина Яшнабод туманидаги уй-жой биносининг декоратив элементидир.

Хулоса қилиб айтганда, кўча санъати тасвирий санъатнинг шаҳар услубидир. Кўп одамлар учун жамоат жойлари, кўчалар, хиёбонлар, ер ости йўллари, метро ва темир йўл кесишмаларида граффити вахшийлик ва зўравонлик каби кўринади. Лекин ҳақиқатан ҳам шундайми? Кўча санъати

тарафдорларига кўра, галерея, музей ва шахсий коллекцияларда сақланадиган санъат асарларини ҳамма ҳам кўра олмайди. Шунинг учун стрит-арт рассомлари санъатнинг демократик табиати учун курашадилар, яъни у ҳамма учун очиқ ва ҳар ким ундан баҳраманд бўлиш имкониятига эга бўлади.

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Ўзбекистон замонавий бадиий жараёнида орол мавзуси талқини

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Аннотация

Мақолада Марказий Осиёнинг бугунги кундаги глобал муаммоларидан ҳисобланган Орол денгизи қуришининг нафақат экологик томондан балки, тасвирий санъат йўналишида фаолият юритаётган ижодкорлар асарлари орқали фожеанинг нечоғлик долзарблигини тасвирий санъатнинг рангасвир, контемпорари арт каби турлари орқали томошабинларга етказиб беришга қаратилган.

Калит сўзлар: пленер, иллюстрация, контемпорари арт, лойиҳа, портрет жанри, инсталляция, импрессионизм, экспозиция, кўчма кўрғазма.

Аннотация

В данной статье представлена актуальность трагедии Аральского моря, которая сегодня считается одной из глобальных проблем Центральной Азии не только с экологической точки зрения, но и через творчество художников, работающих в сфере изобразительного искусства, донести до зрителя значимость трагедии через виды изобразительного искусства, такие как живопись и современное искусство.

Ключевые слова: пленэр, иллюстрация, контемпорари арт, проект, портретный жанр, инсталляция, импрессионизм, экспозиция, передвижная выставка.

Жамият ҳаётида тасвирий санъат бор эканки, унда ўз-ўзидан ушбу жамият маданий ҳаёти, ундаги ўзгаришлар, турли талофатлар, эпидемиялар ва албатта глобал муаммолар замонавий санъат намоёндалари ва мохир мўйқалам усталари томонидан талқин этилади. Турли даврларда глобал муаммолар ҳар хил бўлган. Лекин сув муаммоси доимо ўз актуаллигини

сақлаб қолган. Ўрта Осиёда сув танқислиги 1970-йилдан хўжалик экинларини суғориш учун тежалмай сарфланиши натижасида қисқа муддатда қурий бошлаган Орол денгизи орқали намоён бўлган. Бу эса илк бор маҳаллий ва кўчма рассомлар ижодида ўз аксини топган. Авваллари ирмоқлари тўлиб, мавж урган дарё тасвирланган картиналар яратилган бўлса, эндиликда янтоқзорга айланган, сувсизликдан қурий бошлаган сахро сифатида гавдаланади. Бундай асарлар айниқса, Қорақалпоқ рассомлари ижодида кўп учрайди.

1990-йиллар сўнгидан Ўзбекистон бадиий ҳаётига “контемпорари арт” тушунчаси кириб келганидан сўнг ижодкорлар Орол фожеасини томошабинларга янада оддийроқ тарзда етказиб бериш учун кундалик турмушда фойдаланиладиган сопол буюмлар, туз, кум, тош жисмлари ва шу каби буюмлар орқали ифодалаб берганлар. Масалан, 2001-йил Тошкент Марказий Кўرғазмалар залида ўтказилган кўрғазмада икки актуал санъат вакиллари Вячеслав Ахунов ва Жамол Усмонов Орол мавзусига бағишланган инсталляцияларини омма эътиборига ҳавола этишади. Жумладан, Ж.Усмонов Орол муаммосини думалоқ шаклда тупроқдан ташкил топган майдонда, марказда Орол тимсолини билдирувчи бўш хумни жойлаштирган. Хумнинг атрофига эса сополдан ясалган 30 дан ортиқ сувсизликдан оғзи очиқ ҳолда осмонга қараб тирмашаётган балиқчаларни жойлаштириш орқали мавзуни очиб берган. В.Ахунов эса, Орол денгизини буткул чўл кўринишида тупроқ, кўмир ва тош ёрдамида, жун толаларидан оқ ва қора рангдаги уюмлар ясаб ўз инсталляциясини тақдим этган.³⁶

Ўзбек тасвирий санъати ривожига ўз ижод намуналари орқали ҳисса қўшиб келаётган Абдуҳаким Турдиев талабалик йилларида илк марта Қорақалпоғистонга амалиёт ўташ учун боради. Ташрифи чоғида у Ф.Мадгазин ижоди билан яқиндан танишиб унинг мўйқаламига мансуб 24 та

³⁶ Ахмедова Н. Живопись Центральной Азии XX века: традиции, самобытность, диалог. Т 2004. 173-180 С

этнодларини сотиб олади. Бу эса келажакда А.Турдиевда Орол денгизига аталган инсталляция яралишининг ғоясини уйғотади. Ўз фаолияти давомида турли Европа мамлакатларида бўлган рассом Голландиянинг Гаага шаҳрида яшаб ижод қилган чоғида маҳаллий галереяларда асарларини намойиш қилиб кўрғазмалар уюштиради, тасвирий санъат мактабларида дарс беради. Шу орада унга галерея раҳбарлари ва маҳаллий санъатшунослар томонидан бирор бир миллий, лекин шу қаторда актуал санъат асари намойиш қилиши таклифи берилади. Рассомда ҳеч иккиланмай Орол мавзусини олиб чиқиш фикри пайдо бўлади. Бунинг учун у талабалик йиллари кўлга киритган Ф.Мадгазин эскизларидан фойдаланади. Ижодкор ўзи учун ажратилган зал фонини Орол ирмоқлари тўлиб оқаётган муҳитни қайтариш истагида оқ рангга бўйяди. Голландиянинг ўзгарувчан табиатидан келиб чиққан ҳолда зални ўн тонна туз кристаллари билан тўлдириб чиқади. Бу эса куннинг турли пайтида қуёш нури туфайли тузларнинг товланиб денгиз тўлқинлари тасаввурини уйғотишига хизмат қилади. Шу тариқа медитатив руҳда яратилган инсталляция голланд томошабинларига манзур бўлади.

2006-йилда Тошкент Фотосуратлар уйида навбатдаги рассомлар ва фото рассомлар асарларидан таркиб топган “Борса-келмасдан Уйғониш давригача” номли кўрғазма бўлиб ўтади. Кўрғазма экспозициясида рассомлардан Ф.Мадгазин, Р.Матевосян, Б.Серекеев, Ж.Изентаев, С.Байбусинов, А.Еримбетов, М.Антонов каби рангтасвир усталари, В.Ан, В.Вяткин, Ш.Каримбобоева, Турсун Али, Э.Куртвелев ва асли Италиялик лекин беш йил давомида Марказий Осиё тарихини ўрганиб ижод қилиб келётган фото рассом Матео Моденинг фотоасарлари намойиш этилади.³⁷ Айниқса, кўрғазма залининг марказига ўрнатилган қуриб қолган қамишли замин кўйнида акс эттирилган қайиқ инсталляцияси ташриф буюрувчиларда макон муҳитини яратиб беришга хизмат қилган.

³⁷ Тўхтабоева Р. Борса-келмасдан, уйғониш давригача. САНЪАТ. 2006 №2 46-47.

Навбатдаги Орол денгизини мадх этувчи қорақалпоқ ёш рассомлари иштирокида 2022-йилнинг май ойида ташкил этилган кўргазма “We are Арал” (Биз Оролмиз) деб номланади. Асли бу ном қорақалпоқ ёш янги тўлқин рассомлари гуруҳининг номи бўлиб, бу гуруҳга Темур Шардеметов, Бахтияр Серекеев, Саламат Бабажанов ва Наврўз Айтмуратовлар мансубдирлар. Уларнинг ҳар бири ўзига хос услубга эга ижодкорлардир. Қорақалпоқ ёш янги тўлқин вакиллари ўзларидан аввалги анъанавий рангтасвир услублари ва мавзуларини такрорламасдан асосан, ўз ички “мен”ига таянган ҳолда асарлар яратадилар. Масалан, Т.Шардеметов ва С.Бабажанов ижодида портрет йўналишидаги асарлар етакчилик қилса, Б.Серекеев (асарларида асосан кум, кўмирдан фойдаланади) ва Н.Айтмуратов ижодида маиший ва лирик-драматик йўналишлар доминантлик қилади. “We are арал” кўргазмасида ҳам ёш рассомларнинг Орол денгизи қуришига доир ва юқорида келтириб ўтилган жанрдаги асарлари намоёиш этилган.

Бугунги кунга қадар Орол денгизига бағишланган энг йирик кўргазма сифатида 2022-йилнинг октябр ойидан буён ўтказилиб келинаётган “Арал Дреам” (Орол орзуси) ҳамкорлик кўргазмасини мисол қила оламиз. Мазкур кўчма кўргазма Ургенч Замоनावий санъат музейи, Маданият ва туризм вазирлиги ҳамкорлигида ташкил этилган. Кўчма кўргазма Ургенч Замоनावий Санъат музейи директори рассом Ширин Ташова ташаббуси ва раҳбарлиги остида бўлиб ўтмоқда. Кўчма кўргазмада етти нафар қорақалпоқ ва ўзбек миллатига мансуб ижодкорлар асарлари намоёиш этилмоқда. Булар, Сарсенбай Байбусинов, Саидбек Сабирбаев, Икрам Матчанов, Василий Хапов, Собир Кутлимуратов, Абдулла Раджабов ва бевосита Ширин Ташовалардир. Кўчма кўргазманинг ўзига хослиги шундаки унда рассомлар кўргазма экспозициясида намоёиш этиш учун махсус Мўйноқда сафарда бўлиб, у ерда пленерда янги асарлар яратишди. Бу албатта рассомларда Орол қуриши фожасини чуқурроқ англашига хисса қўшди. Лойиҳа қатнашчилари

асосан кемалар қабристонидаги кемалар тасвирини, қуруқликдан азият чеккан табиат ва Орол муаммоси қорақалпоқ миллати аҳолисининг ташқи кўринишига соғлиғига етказган салбий оқибатларини импрессионизм, экспрессионизм, реализм каби йўналишлардаги картиналари орқали очиб беришган. Кўчма кўргазма доирасида Камолиддин Бехзод номидаги Миллий рассомлик ва дизайн институти “Маҳобатли рангтасвир” йўналиши катта ўқитувчиси В.Хапов билан бўлган суҳбат давомида рассом “Биз пленэрда асар яратиш учун 4 соат машинада йўл юрдик. Белгиланган манзилга етгач машинадан тушиб оёқларимиз тагида майда чиғаноқлар ва балиқларнинг суяк қолдиқларини кўрдик. Бу эса қачонлардир биз босаётган ер сув билан тўлиб тошганлигидан далолат берар эди. Мазкур ҳодисанинг ўзиёқ биз рассомлар муаммонинг туб моҳиятини англашимизга яна бир бор туртки бўлди” дейди. “Арал дреам” лойиҳасининг илк кўргазмаси Қорақалпоғистоннинг “Кемалар қабристони” манзилида, сўнг И.В.Савицкий номидаги Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси Давлат санъат музейида бўлиб ўтди. Лойиҳа очилишида АҚШлик Оролшунос олим Роберт Виллард бевосита иштирок этди. Ҳозирги кунга қадар кўчма кўргазма Бухоро, Навоий, Шаҳрисабз, Термиз каби вилоятларда бўлиб ўтди. Тошкент шаҳрида “Арал дреам” лойиҳаси июль-август ойларида бўлиши режалаштирилмоқда. Хулоса қилиб айтиш мумкинки, бугунги куннинг долзарб муаммоларидан бўлмиш Орол денгизининг қуриши нафақат мутасадди ташкилотлар ва экологик қўмиталар орқали балки тасвирий санъат йўналишида фаолият юритаётган ижодкорлар асарлари орқали кенг омма эътиборига хавола этилмоқда. Бу эса ўз навбатида оддий халқ муаммонинг қанчалик долзарб эканлигини кенгроқ англашига яна бир бор ўз ҳиссасини қўшиб келмоқда. Ўтказилган чора тадбирлар, кўргазмалар, Оролшунос олимлар мақолалари ва “Орол денгизини муҳофаза қилиш ташкилоти” саъй ҳаракатлари натижаси ўлароқ Орол денгизи сатҳи ярим метрга кўтарилди. Умид қиламизки бу натижа келгусида ҳам ўсишда давом этади.

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PHYSICAL AND MATHEMATICAL SCIENCE

Об одной обратной динамической задаче пороупругости для слоистой среды

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Аннотация. Рассматривается обратная динамическая задача пороупругости кусочно-гладкого коэффициента сдвига по дополнительной информации колебаний точек свободной поверхности. Считается, что выполнена гипотезы Гупилла о равном времени распространении возмущений по слоям насыщенной жидкостью пористой среды. Получены рекуррентные формулы для восстановления неизвестного коэффициента сдвига.

Ключевые слова: пороупругости, прямая задача, обратная динамическая задача, слоистой среды, гипотезы Гупилла, образы Фурье, комплексной плоскости.

В данной работе нас будет интересовать задача, связанная с распространением волн в изотропной слоистой пористой среде, опирающейся на однородное полупространство. Будем рассматривать плоскопараллельные слои. Рассматривается одномерная обратная динамическая задача пороупругости в диссипативном приближении для слоистых сред.

Рассмотрим процесс распространения колебаний в неоднородном по переменной x полупространстве, описываемый системой уравнением [20-24]

$$\rho_s(x) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\mu(x) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) - \rho_l(x) b(x) \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} \right), x > 0, t > 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = b(x)(u - v), \quad x > 0, t > 0 \quad (2)$$

при следующих нулевых начальных условиях:

$$u|_{t=0} = 0, \quad u_t|_{t=0} = 0, \quad v|_{t=0} = 0, \quad x > 0 \quad (3)$$

и граничном условии

$$u_x|_{x=0} = H(t), \quad t > 0 \quad (4)$$

В формулах (1) и (2) функция $\mu(x)$ кусочно-постоянна и может иметь разрывы в точках $a_1 < a_2 < \dots < a_k$, функции $\rho_l(x)$, $\rho_s(x)$, $b(x)$, т.е. полагая $a_0 = 0$, можно записать равенство

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} \mu_m & \text{для } x \in (a_{m-1}, a_m), m = 1, \dots, k \\ \mu_{k+1} & \text{для } x > a_k \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

$$\rho_l(x) = \begin{cases} \rho_{lm} & \text{для } x \in (a_{m-1}, a_m), m = 1, \dots, k \\ \rho_{lk+1} & \text{для } x > a_k \end{cases}, \quad (6)$$

$$\rho_s(x) = \begin{cases} \rho_{sm} & \text{для } x \in (a_{m-1}, a_m), m = 1, \dots, k \\ \rho_{sk+1} & \text{для } x > a_k \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

$$b(x) = \begin{cases} b_m & \text{для } x \in (a_{m-1}, a_m), m = 1, \dots, k \\ b_{k+1} & \text{для } x > a_k \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

где $b_m, \mu_m, \rho_{lm}, \rho_{sm} = const.$

В точках разрыва a_m коэффициента $\mu(x)$ к условиям (3), (4) добавим условия сопряжения

$$[u]_{x=a_m} = [\mu(x)u_x]_{x=a_m} = 0, \quad m = 1, \dots, k \quad (9)$$

Задачу определения функции $u(x, t)$ и $v(x, t)$ удовлетворяющей равенствам (1)-(4), (9) при заданной функции $b(x)$, $\mu(x)$, $\rho_l(x)$, $\rho_s(x)$ вида (5)-(8), принято называть прямой задачей.

Основной предмет исследования настоящей работы составляет

Обратная задача A_μ^1 . Определить коэффициент $\mu(x)$ уравнения (1), т.е. найти набор из $2k + 1$ чисел $\{\mu_1, \dots, \mu_{k+1}; a_1, \dots, a_k\}$, если относительно решения задачи (1)-(4), (9) известна информация

$$\Phi(\omega) = - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u_t(0, t) e^{-i\omega t} dt, \quad \omega \in \Omega, \quad (10)$$

причем Ω – отделенный от нуля конечный интервал и функции $b(x)$, $\rho_l(x)$, $\rho_s(x)$ заданы. Далее будем для простоты считать, что функции $b(x)$, $\rho_l(x)$, $\rho_s(x)$ заданными постоянными.

Известно (см., например, [1, 4]), что прямая задача (1)-(4), (9) в случае слоистой среды связана следующей задачей для уравнения Гельмгольца с параметром:

$$U_{xx} + \omega^2 \tilde{B}^2(x, \omega) U = 0, \quad (12)$$

$$U_x(0, \omega) = h(\omega), \quad U_x - i\tilde{B}\omega U \rightarrow 0 \text{ при } x \rightarrow \infty, \quad (13)$$

$$[U]_{x=a_m} = [\mu U_x]_{x=a_m} = 0, \quad m = 1, \dots, k. \quad (14)$$

Здесь $U(x, \omega)$, $h(\omega)$ – образы Фурье соответственно функций u и H :

$$U(x, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u(x, t) e^{-i\omega t} dt, \quad h(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt,$$

$$\tilde{B}(x, \omega) = \frac{\sqrt{(1 + \rho_l(x) / \rho_s(x)) b(x) - i\omega}}{c(x) \sqrt{b(x) - i\omega}}.$$

Дополнительная информация (10) для обратной задачи A_{μ}^1 определения коэффициента $\mu(x)$ будет соответствовать равенству

$$\Phi(\omega) = i\omega U(0, \omega), \quad \omega \in \Omega \quad (15)$$

Таким образом, решение обратной задачи A_{μ}^1 связано с решением следующей задачи.

Обратная задача A_{μ}^2 . Определить коэффициент $\mu(x)$ вида (5)-(8) уравнения (12), если относительно решения задачи (12)-(14) известна информация (15).

Следуя [12] введем следующее

Определение. Обратную задачу A_{μ}^2 об определении функции $\mu(x)$ вида (5) по дополнительной информации (10) в рамках гипотезы (11) назовем k -слойной.

Если это не оговорено особо, всюду в дальнейшем будем рассматривать k -слойную задачу.

Теорема. Пусть выполнены равенства (11), полином (27) $g_0^{(k)} + g_1^{(k)}z + \dots + g_k^{(k)}z^k$ не имеет корней в круге $|z| \leq 1$ и образ Фурье $h(\omega)$ функции $H(t)$ не обращается в нуль для $\omega \in [\omega_0, \omega_0 + \pi/\tau] \subset \Omega$. Тогда для построенной по решению задачи (12)-(14) функции $F_k(z)$ (27) справедливы формулы

$$F_k^{(m)}(0) = m! \left[2\gamma_m \prod_{p=1}^{m-1} (1 - \gamma_p^2) - \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} \frac{h_p^m}{(m-p)!} F_k^{(m-p)}(0) \right]. \quad (33)$$

Причем коэффициенты γ_m , h_p^m вычисляются согласно формулам (31), (32), $m = 2, \dots, k$.

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PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCE

Ўз-ўзини идентификация қилишнинг ижтимоий-психологик механизми

Социально-психологический механизм самоидентификации

Socio-psychological mechanism of self-identification

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада педагогларнинг ўз-ўзини англаш моҳиятан махсус жараён бўлиб, ташқи дунёни таҳлил қилиш, мазмуни ва аҳамиятини фарқлаш, аниқланган объектларни умумлаштиришга қаратилган ақлий фаолият эканлиги, ўз-ўзини аниқлаш ва англаш шахснинг мустақил фаолият субъекти сифатида мавжуд бўлишининг бир усули сифатида қаралиши, чунки у нафақат ўзига нисбатан қиймат позициясининг намоён қилади, балки бошқаларга ҳам намоён бўлади, мана шу динамиклик, ўз-ўзини идентификация қилишнинг ижтимоий-психологик механизми учун асос эканлиги ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: процессуал, механизм, идентификация, ижтимоийлашув, эпигенетик, касб-ҳунар, мен тушунчаси, шахс, психодинамик, психоаналитик.

Аннотация: самосознание по своей сути особый процесс, это мыслительная деятельность, направленная на анализ внешнего мира, выделение его содержания и значения, обобщение выявленных объектов, самоопределение и осознание следует рассматривать как способ существования человека как субъекта самостоятельной деятельности, поскольку он не только по отношению к себе проявляет ценностную позицию, но и проявляет себя к другим, объясняется, что эта динамика является основой социально-психологического механизма самоидентификации.

Ключевые слова: процессуальный, механизм, идентичность, социализация, эпигенетический, профессия, Я-концепция, личность, психодинамический, психоаналитический.

Annotation: self-consciousness is inherently a special process, it is a mental activity aimed at analyzing the external world, highlighting its content and meaning, generalizing the identified objects, self-determination and awareness should be considered as a way of human existence as a subject of independent activity, since he not only manifests in relation to himself value position, but also manifests itself to others, it is explained that this dynamics is the basis of the socio-psychological mechanism of self-identification.

Key words: procedural, mechanism, identity, socialization, epigenetic, profession, self-concept, personality, psychodynamic, psychoanalytic.

Жадаллик билан тараққий этиб бораётган жамиятда баркамол шахс маънавий оламига боғлиқ бўлган масалаларга қизиқишни кузатмоқд. Зеро педагог бўлиб, комил инсон сифатида ўз-ўзини англашида жамиятдаги инсонлар билан ҳамда гуруҳлар билан идентификация жараёнида, турли урф-одатларга, анъаналарга дуч келиши мумкин.

Ўз-ўзини идентификация қилишнинг назарий ва методологик асосларига таянган ҳолда, унинг моҳиятини ва бошқа унга яқин ҳодисалар билан алоқасинигина аниқлаш билан бирга унинг ижтимоий-психологик механизмини очиш ҳам муҳимдир.

Тадқиқот муаммолари бўйича илмий адабиётларни таҳлил қилиш шунинг кўрсатадики, биринчи навбатда ўз-ўзини аниқлаш моҳиятан махсус жараён бўлиб, ташқи дунёни таҳлил қилиш, мазмуни ва аҳамиятини фарқлаш, аниқланган объектларни умумлаштиришга қаратилган ақлий фаолиятдир.

Шахсият, ҳаёт йўлини қуриш, инсон ҳаётининг узок муддатли тартибга солинишига асосланган ўтмиш, ҳозирги ва келажак ҳақидаги ғоялар тизими томонидан бошқарилади. Инсоннинг ички дунёси доимий зиддиятлар ҳолатида бўлиб, улар кескинликларда намоён бўлади. Классик психодинамик ва психоаналитик ёндашувларга кўра, бундай стресснинг манбаига инсон учун муҳим аҳамиятга эга бўлган ички қураш, қарама-қарши позициялар ва фикрларга киради.

Тадқиқотлар натижаси шуни кўрсатадики, шахс кўпинча ички қарама-қаршиликларини тушунмайди, лекин улар ўзининг ҳаётий фаолиятидаги бошқа соҳаларига тааллуқли ортиқча ташвиш ҳиссини туғдиради ва одатда хатти-ҳаракатларга ҳалокатли таъсир кўрсатади. Бундай тартибсизликларни фақатгина позицияларни таққослаш ва тегишли қарорлар қабул қилиш орқали бартараф этиш мумкин. Ушбу ёндашув ўз-ўзини идентификация қилиш ўзгаришларини амалга оширадиган мавжуд ижтимоий-психологик механизмларни тушуниш ва ажратишга ёрдам беради.

Моҳиятга кўра, юқоридаги ҳолат ўз-ўзини идентификациялашни ўрганиш учун процессуал ёндашувни акс эттиради, турли тушунчаларни ўз ичига олади. Уларнинг бири динамик тизим ва ривожланиш моменти давридир.

Динамик тизим тушунчаси ўз ичига ўз-ўзини идентификация қилиш ходисасидаги мавжуд хусусиятларни, хусусан, шахс ва дунё ўртасидаги муносабатларнинг янги турларининг пайдо бўлиши сифатида уларнинг миқдор ва сифат ўзгаришларини қамраб олади.

Ривожланиш моменти концепцияси ўз-ўзини идентификация қилишнинг муайян босқичи бўлиб, шахсият ўзгаришини тавсифловчи босқични ўзида акс эттиради.

Динамик тизим сифатида ўз-ўзини идентификация қилиш идентификация қилиш тушунчасида акс эттирилган бўлиб, у асосан шахснинг ҳаракатини, унинг идентификациясини шакллантириш механизмини англатади. Идентификация тушунчаси ҳаракат моментини, идентификация жараёнида шахс томонидан эришилган ҳолатни ифодалайди.

Идентификация ва идентификациялашнинг моҳияти, бир томондан, уларнинг бирлиги ва бошқа томондандан эса, зиддиятдир.

Идентификация ва идентификациялаш шахсни ижтимоийлаштириш йўлининг ягона жараёни экан иккита нисбатан мустақил томонини ташкил этиши ва бир-бирисиз мавжуд эмаслиги билан намоён бўлади. Бу икки томон бир бутун бирлик деб қаралиши мақсадга мувофиқ.

Идентификация қилиш идентификациялаш жараёнидаги асосий хусусият моментни акс эттиришидир. Момент ва зиддият жараён сифатида идентификация қилиш ривожланиш бирликлари сифатида бир-бирисиз бир лаҳзасиз мавжуд эмас. Ўзга шахслар билан идентификациясиз идентификациялаш мумкин эмас.

Идентификация ва идентификация қилиш, биринчи навбатда, ўз-ўзини идентификациялашнинг яхлит ижтимоий-психологик ҳодиса сифатида намоён бўлишидир. Ҳар бир инсон жамият билан идентификация қилиш орқали ижтимоийлаштирилади, бу унга тегишли ижтимоий тажрибани ўрганиш имконини беради.

Шахсни гуруҳ билан идентификация қилиш истаги унинг изоляция қилиш истаги кимлар билан боғлиқ бўлади? Инсоннинг мулоқотга бўлган эҳтиёжи унинг шахсиятига бўлган эҳтиёжидан ажралиб туради. Жамиятда фақат ўзи билан мулоқотда, ўз-ўзини ўз ҳукмлари, хулосаларини кўпроқ англай бошлайди. Аммо кейинги босқичларда уларга чекловлар қўйилади, кейинчалик эркин индивидуалликнинг ривожланишига тўсқинликлар бошланади. Инсон ўзини танитган жамоаларнинг эскирган шакллари шахсни ижтимоийлаштириш учун янги имкониятлар очадиган жараён ва воситалар, тушунчалар билан ўзгариши ва тўлдирилиши керак. Ривожланиш босқичлари ўртасидаги алоқаларни кузатиш ушбу жараённинг динамикасини тушуниш имконини беради ва бу босқичлар ўртасидаги ўзаро боғлиқликнинг ўзига хос хусусиятлари шахсни ўз-ўзини идентификация қилиш ҳаракатини ташкил этувчи асосий фикрларни жойлаштиришни ўз ичига олади.

Идентификация ва идентификациялашнинг бирлиги фақатгина идентификациялаш даражасини рўёби қиймат муносабати сифатида ва «мен»га қиймат нисбати сифатида идентификация қилиш даражасига мос келиши лозим. Шахснинг ривожланиши учун бу жараён динамик мувозанат ҳолатида бўлиши керак. Доимий равишдаги талаб ва шартлар, шахс манфаатлари, имкониятлари, истаклари билан ажралиб турадиган янги

шароитлар мувозанатнинг юзага келиши деб белгиланади. Бундай ҳолатда, шахс ўз-ўзини идентификация қилиш доирасида идентификациялаш ва идентификацияни уйғунлаштириш шартлари зарур бўлган мувозанатга эришишга интилади.

Ўз-ўзини идентификация қилиш инсоннинг ўзига хос хусусиятларини шакллантиришда жуда муҳим ва аҳамиятлидир. Зотан, у инсоннинг хоҳиш-иродаси ва имкониятларини билиш даражасини, муайян жамиятга қўшилишини англатади. Шу нуқтаи назардан, ўз-ўзини аниқлаш бир вақтнинг ўзида ва ижтимоиятнинг қиймат-мотивацион воситаси сифатида намоён бўлади.

Ижтимоийлашув шундай жараёнки, ўз-ўзини аниқлаш, инсон ҳаётининг дастлабки кунларидан бошланади ва шахс доимо ўз муносабатларини, ташқи дунё билан алоқаларни яхшилайдиган узуликсизликда бўлади.

Ижтимоийлашув манбалари – оила, таълим-тарбия муассасалари, адабиёт, санъат, оммавий ахборот воситалари ва бошқалар ҳисобланади.

Бошланғич ижтимоийлашув жараёнида оила ва атроф-муҳит шароити шахсиятнинг шаклланишига таъсир этувчи омиллардан биридир. Иккиламчи ижтимоийлашув жараёни инсоннинг ўзини ўзи идентификация қилиш жараёнида иштирок этиши, жамият ижтимоий хулқ-атвор турларини танлаш имкониятини англатади. Бу шахснинг ахлоқий ва эстетик қадриятларга қараб, ўз хоҳишига кўра, имиджини яратиш имкониятидир.

Ижтимоийлашув жараёнининг ривожланиши билан идентификациялашнинг бошқа механизмларга нисбатан роли (масалан, тақлид) ортиб боради. Шунга кўра, шахс тушунчалари кўлами кенгаяди ва чуқурлиги ортган ҳолда ўзгаради. Оғзаки рўйхатга олишдан профессионал гуруҳга (мослашув босқичида) ушбу гуруҳ манфаатларига мувофиқ онгли фаолият, ўз мақсадлари ва меъёрларини ўзиники деб қабул қилиш сифати ижобийлашади.

А.А.Бирюков, А.И.Матвеева жамият доирасида ўз-ўзини идентификация қилиш доимий ижтимоий ёрдамга муҳтожлигини таъкидлайдилар. Инсон

бошқа шахсларсиз инсон бўлиши мумкин эмас, чунки жамиятсиз идентификация қилиш мумкин эмас. Муаллифлар шахсий идентификацияни шахсинг жисмоний, психологик ёки ахлоқий хусусиятларини, унинг мақоми, роль белгиларини шахсинг шахсий манфаатлари асосида, жамоатчилик билан биргаликда аниқлашни таклиф қиладилар.

А.А.Бирюков, А.И.Матвеева фикрича, ижтимоий идентификациялашнинг яна бир тури шахсни муайян ижтимоий тоифаларга (ёшлар, элита, махсус йўналиш, соҳалар) ташкилий чегараларга эга бўлмаган, баъзи мезонларга кўра фарқ қилувчи гуруҳларга бирлаштириш орқали амалга ошириш ҳисобланади.

Унинг белгилари:

ёш;

жамиятдаги вазият;

шахс мавқеи ва бошқ.

Ўз-ўзини аниқлашнинг ташқи йўналиши инсоннинг атроф-муҳит билан муносабатларини онгли равишда амалга оширилиши турли даражадаги қобиляти билан узвий боғлиқ бўлади. Шу нуқтаи назардан, ўз-ўзини идентификация қилиш тадқиқотчиларга шахсдан гуруҳга қадар бўлган йўл сифатида тақдим этилади:

гуруҳни қидириш, яъни. шахсга ишончни таъминлайдиган ёрдам;

гуруҳнинг бир қисми сифатида ўзини англаш, яъни «биз» билан интеграция қилиш;

идентификация ҳис-туйғуларини шакллантириш умумийлигига, ҳамжиҳатликка боғлиқлиги;

гуруҳ ғоялари, қадриятлари, манфаатлари, эҳтиёжлари, мақсадлари, норма – меъёрларини қабул қилиш;

жамият олдидаги масъулият туйғусини шакллантириш.

Атроф-муҳит, ижтимоият қуршов шахсинг ўзи учун кимлигини билишга ёрдам берадиган ҳал қилувчи омил ҳисобланади. Шу билан бирга, ҳар қандай ходиса, жумладан, унинг афзалликлари ва камчиликларини, унинг бир ёки бир

нечта кишиларга тегишлилиги, фақатгина мос белгилар нуқтасини ёки ўлчов бирлигини белгилаш орқали аниқланиши мумкин. Бунда шахс ўзини бошқа шахс билан ёки унинг ўзига хос хусусиятларини бошқасининг хусусиятлари билан таққослайди. Шундан сўнг бир киши ўзи ҳақида бирор нарса айтиши мумкин, яъни бу одамлар учун ўзига хос умумий хусусиятларни қабул қилган ва умумлаштирган тоифадагиларнинг идентификациялашдир.

Барча идентификация қарорлари мен инсонман, мен фуқароиман, мен бахтлиман каби шахсиятга хос хусусиятларнинг тўпламини аниқлашга асосланган бўлиши мақсадга мувофиқдир. Ушбу ҳукмларда шахсий хусусиятлар акс этишининг мавзуси («бахтли», «яхши», «ақлли», билвосита шаклда – «инсон», «фуқаро») юзага чиқади. Шубҳасиз, бу ҳукмларни қабул қиладиган контрагент «инсон», «фуқаро», «инсон», «фуқаро»дан фарқли ўлароқ қандай хусусиятларга эга эканлиги ҳақида тасаввурга эга. Шу билан бирга, ўз-ўзини аниқлаш жараёнида шахснинг хусусиятларини аниқлаш «мен» ва бошқалар ўртасидаги муносабатни тушунишдан ажралиб туради. Бошқа томондан тан олинishi ва тасдиқланиши инсоннинг хатти-ҳаракатларида етакчи мотивига айланади. Ўз-ўзига эътибор бериш, кўриш ва эшитиш учун инсон ўзининг «мен»ни жамият томонидан илгари сурилган талабларга нисбатан белгилаши керак бўлади. Ички ҳолатнинг ташқи талабларга мос келмаслиги ички можарога ва шахснинг ноқулай ҳолатларга тушишига, жамоадан бўлинишига олиб келиши мумкин.

Шу муносабат билан, шахс жуда кўп ижтимоий шахсий хусусиятларшга эга бўлиши лозим, чунки уни бошқа кўплаб шахслар уни таний бошлайдилар.

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TECHNOLOGICAL SCIENCES

Studying yarn incorpectiveness operated on the improved exhaust extractor

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Annotation. This article studies the friction force field and the design of the exhaust cylinder of drafting devices, the effect of the design of rollers and corrugated cylinder on the friction force field. New designs of a corrugated cylinder are proposed that improve the field of friction forces. The optimization parameters of the new fume hood are determined and proposed. In existing designs of drafting devices and devices, improved control over the movement of fibers is achieved in various ways, for example, by installing additional straps, rollers, clutches, guides, trays, etc. A common drawback of this design is that by correcting one drawback, others are promoted, for example, the design of the assembly becomes more complicated or maintenance is difficult, etc.

KEYWORDS: Ring Spinning Machines, Fibers, Flatness, Exhaust Device, Grooved Cylinder, Pressure Roller, Field of Friction Forces, Roller, Strap.

The world's leading machine-building enterprises are conducting research in search of improving ring spinning machines and its individual parts, increasing its reliability and productivity, and the quality of products [1].

When designing ring spinning machines, the choice of the design spinning line, i.e., lines of passage of sliver-yarn from the drafting device to the spool. In some ring spinning machines, the front pressure roller is tilted forward by about 5° to reduce the sweep angles the streamline angle γ for different types of ring spinning machines is different depending on the rise of the ring strips, For main ring spinning machines with a stroke of 220 mm, $\gamma_1 = 2^\circ - 3^\circ$, $\gamma_2 = 17^\circ$ [2].

The installed rollers in this form increase the angle of wrap around the fibrous masses, and (he installation of the magnet in the exhaust zone, being attracted to the lower bar, presses the straps to each other, thereby improving the field of friction forces (Fig. I). For this purpose, the drafting system was equipped with a double pressure roller on the exhaust cylinder and a pressure magnet on the straps [3, 4, 5].

FIG.I. DOUBLE-BELT DRAFTING DEVICE

1-supply pair; 2,3-exhaust pairs; 4-bottom cylinder; 5, 5'-rollers; 6, 6'-saddles; 7, 9-straps; 8- planks; 10-guide; 11-plate; 12-permanent magnet.

For the experiments, the method of full factorial experiment was used [6, 7]. Analysis of literature data and our experiments made it possible to establish the main factors influencing the unevenness of the yarn. 1 factor - the value of the load on the pressure roller of the exhaust pair; 2 factor - the distance between the rollers in the double pressure roller; Factor 3 - the clamping force of the straps with a permanent magnet. The coded values of the factors will be designated X_1 , X_2 , X_3 - respectively - the load on the pressure roller, the distance between the rollers in the double pressure roller, the pressing force of the straps with a permanent magnet. For the optimization parameter “Y” we take the unevenness of the pulled product.

Preliminary experiments in production conditions have shown that the minimum load on the pressure roller should not be less than 100 H. because with a double roller, the rubber coating is put on the cylinders, and the rollers are metal. According to the recommendation of the SKF company, for the load lever of the RK-225 type, the load is taken from 100 II to 180 II. Therefore, in our experiments, the minimum load is 100 H. and the maximum load is 180 H. The distance between the rollers in the double pressure roller is selected for design reasons in the range of 15 - 19 mm.

On the basis of the previous analysis, intervals and levels of variation of factors were established (Table I), as well as the optimization parameter. Therefore, we will compose a planning matrix for a full factorial experiment for linear yarn densities of 25 text and 10 text. Accordingly, all experiments were carried out in triplicate.

TABLE 1 levels and intervals of variation of the stl'diep factors

Identification of factors	Name Factors	Variation level			Variation interval
		- 1	0	+ 1	
X ₁	Exhaust steam load, H	100	140	180	40
X ₂	Distance between two rollers, mm	15	17	19	2
X ₃	Clamping force of the straps, H: to obtain yarn with a linear density of 25 text	1,1	1,16	1,22	0,06
	for yarn with linear density of 10 text	0,82	0,88	0,94	0,06

The minimum unevenness of the pulled product is achieved with the following values of the investigated factors:

For yarn 25 text: P₁ = 180 H; L = 15 mm; P₂ = 1,22 H;

For yarn 10 text: P₁ = 180 H; L = 19 mm; P₂ = 0,94 H;

Analysis of the obtained values allows us to conclude that the load on the pressure roller and the distance between the rollers affect the unevenness of the pulled product in different ways. Thus, when producing different types of yarn

(25, 10 text), it is recommended to select the appropriate values of load P_2 and distance L .

TABLE 2 The optimal condition for reducing the unevenness of the pulled product in the hood

Linear density yarn, text	Designation of factors	Factor values are coded	Natural values of factors
25	$X_1(P_1)$	+1	180 H
	$X_2(L)$	-1	15 mm
	$X_3(P_2)$	+1	1,22 H
10	$X_1(P_1)$	+1	180 H
	$X_2(L)$	+1	15 mm
	$X_3(P_2)$	+1	0,94 H

As you can see from the table 2, the optimal values found by calculation and experiment is close to each other. As a result of experiments, on the existing drafting device, the following parameter values were obtained: for 25 text - 21.7%, and for 10 text - 20.8%, which confirms the effectiveness of using a magnet to clamp the straps in the exhaust zone and a double pressure roller in the exhaust pair of the machines.

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CONTENTS

CULTURAL SCIENCE

Қодирова Сарвиноз Муҳсиновна. - Полвон Качал - ўзбек анъанавий кўғирчоқ театрининг қахрамони.3

ECONOMICAL SCIENCE

Абдуллаева Матлуба Нематовна, Фарходова Шохиста Журъат қизи. - Корхоналарнинг ишлаб чиқариш фаолиятини баҳолаш услублари.6

Очилова Дилобар Караматовна. - Туризм хизматлар бозори самарадорлигини оширишнинг йўллари.11

Khalikova Lola Nazarovna. - Economic thoughts of great people.15

HISTORICAL SCIENCE

Madina Abdullayeva. - The history of development of Turkic tribes.23

MEDICAL SCIENCE

Babadzhanov A.Kh., Abdullazhanov B.R., Kuchkarov M.Yu. - Results of new domestic hemostatic film usage for spleen injuries.29

Khodjiyeva Dilbar Todjiyevna, Bozorov Uktam Naim ugli. - Optimization of treatment methods for herniated discs.32

Kuchkarov M.Yu., Babadzhanov A.Kh., Abdullazhanov B.R. - Results of new domestic hemostatic film usage for liver injuries.34

Saliev G.Z., Abdullazhanov B.R., Babadzhanov A.Kh. - Composite hemostatic plate for parenchymatic bleeding from the liver.37

Алиев Ш. М., Каюмов А. Р., Султанов Н. Х. - Сравнительный анализ результатов линейного протезирования и экзопротезирования восходящего отдела аорты в сочетании с заменой аортального клапана.43

Г.Х. Исканова, Г.А. Юсупова, Н.А. Исроилова. - Синдром лоу у детей.45

Мирзакаримов Б.Х. - Хирургическая лечения килевидной деформации грудной клетки у детей.48

Xudayberdiyeva D.A. - An integrated approach to the diagnosis of prostate cancer.50

Mirraximov Jamshid Abdullayevich, Maxmudova Nilufar Maxamadjonovna. - Surunkali gastrit kasalligini davolash va profilaktik tadbirlarini tashkil etishda xalq tabobatining o`rni....52

У.Т. Омонова, М.Ф. Холматов, К.К. Бобониязов. - Клиническо-неврологические особенности микроцефалии различного генеза.55

K. Z. Yakhyaeva. - Observation in dynamics of children who have undergone intrauterine blood transfusion for hemolytic disease due to the Rh factor.57

Kasimov Khayotbek Kabulovich. - An approach for detection acute sinusitis and its features occurred on the effect of allergic rhinitis.59

S. Tojiboev, T. Kamalov, Ya.Kh. Turakulov. - The dynamics of growth in the frequency of Charcot foot in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2012 - 2021 years.61

Tashmatova G.A., Imuradova M.A. - Clinical and immunological characteristics of bronchial asthma in children against the background of atypical pathogens.63

Б.А. Тоиров, Е.В. Лигай. - Состояние андроген чувствительных рецепторов при иммуногистохимическом анализе больных с акне.66

Орипова О.О. – Дилятацион кардиомиопатияларда морфологик ўзгаришлар.68

Эргашева Наргиза Обиджоновна, Аvezов Муроджон Хайитбой ўғли. - Ишемик инсултни ўтқир даврини реабилитация қилишда акупунктуранинг аҳамияти.71

Umirov S.E., Umirzakov Z.B., Mirzajonova D.B., Mirzakarimova D. B., Yuldashev K.Kh. Тиббиёт ходимларида covid-19 кечишининг айрим клиник эпидемиологик жиҳатлари. ..76

Fattakhov R.A. - Autonomic nervous system dysfunction in dentists with burnout syndrome..82

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCE

- Husainova Gulhayo Baxtiyorovna.** - Abu Nasr Forobiyning ta`lim-tarbiyaga oid qarashlari...84
Рахимова Ш. Б. - Чет тилларини ўқитишда суггестопедия методининг афзалликлари...90
Azamov Jasurbek Murodovich. - Structure of boards of trustees in otmls in malaysia.94
Ibragimova Nazokat. - Sociolinguistic Competence as a Linguistic Problem in Teaching Foreign Languages to B2 Level Students.97
Olimov Temir Hasanovich. - Ilmiy tadqiqot mavzusini tanlash va uning dolzarbligini asoslash.....102
Nadirova M. Shirinbeyim. - The influence of literature on the formation of the student's personality.106

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCE

- Alisher Rustamov Abduhakimovich.** - Language Maintenance and Bilingualism in Uzbekistan.....110
Axmadova Durdona Axror qizi. - Improving speaking skills by watching movies.114
Gulshoda Khusniddinova. - Types according to the scope of the pamphlet genre.117
Yunusova Shoista, Nurova Maftuna, Hasanov Suhrob. - Formulaic sequence and oral fluency in the target language based on Psycholinguistic.119
Турғунбоева Диёра Алишер қизи. - Аксиологический потенциал социального уровня ценностей.126
Nigorakhon Ruzibaeva. - А.Чўлпон шеърй асарларида қўлланган антитезанинг структуравий-семантик хусусиятлари.131
Nigorakhon Ruzibaeva. - Т.Элиот шеърй асарларида қўлланган антитезанинг структуравий-семантик хусусиятлари.135
Nadirova M. Shirinbeyim. - The influence of literature on the formation of the student's personality.139

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCE

- Sayidov Kahramon Bekturdievich,** Processes of urbanization development in eastern nations.....143

STATE AND LAW

- Jahongir Husainov.** - O`zbekiston va Salvadorda elektron pullar.146
Jahongir Zokirov. - Geografik ko`rsatkichlarning huquqiy tabiati.153
Oybek Buriyev. - O`zbekiston Respublikasi va xorijiy davlatlarda nou-xauning huquqiy tabiati va uning huquqiy muhofazasi.166

CHEMICAL SCIENCE

- M. Shabanova, Huseynova F.A., Hasanova N.H., Medjidova D.S.** Visual model of the liquid phase`s separation surface for the multicomponent alloys -170
A.M. Qasimova, A.N. Mammadov U.N., Sharifova, F.S. Ibrahimova, I.Q. Sharifova. - Thermodynamics of reducing roasting of titanomagnetite concentrates with natural gas.172
Abdullaeva L.A., Cabarov E.E., Veliyeva N.V, Askerova T.N., Agayeva Z.R. - Colloid-chemical properties of bentonite samples depending on dye concentration.174
Bayramova S.S., Mamedova S.G., Ilyasova X.N., Rafieva H.L., Akhmedova G.N., Hasanova N.Q., Agayeva Z.R. - Influence of natural bentonite and zeolite on the process ventilation air cleaning from acid vapor.176
T.N. Gulubayova, D.S. Valiyeva, I.R. Rushinaz, Z.S. Safaraliyeva, S.D. Dadashova. - Obtaining of the greases using soapstoks.178

CULTUROLOICAL SCIENCES

- Дилзода Алимкулова, Муҳамедова Эъзога “STREET ART” ёки шаҳар муҳити санъати.....180
- Дилзода Алимкулова, Дилафруз Пирназарова. - Ўзбекистон замонавий бадиий жараёнида орол мавзуси талқини.186

PHYSICAL AND MATHEMATICAL SCIENCE

- З.Ш. Янгибоев, Ш.А. Абдимуродова, Д.М. Жовлиева. - Об одной обратной динамической задаче пороупругости для слоистой среды.192

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCE

- Тўраханов Умматали Давлатович. - Ўз-ўзини идентификация қилишнинг ижтимоий-психологик механизми.198

TECHNOLOGICAL SCIENCES

- Dadakhanov Nurilla Karimovich, Ortikov Durbek. - Studying yarn incorpectiveness operated on the improved exhaust extractor.203